

I. 5D METRICS OF SPACE-TIME ORGANISMS APPLIED TO PHYSICAL SYSTEMS: MAX. S X T |s=t

As all the papers on 5D sciences, the 'jump' of logic complexity and depth of thought compared to our 'Euclidean, Aristotelian' 4D requires a lot of introductions. What is 5D physics in a nutshell? A huge expansion on the properties humans recognize to nature to start with. A new dimension of scalar space-time. A relational relative model of space=form and time=motion, that gets rid of the single absolute space-time of Newton. A Unification theory of charges and masses that resolve all the conundrums of present physics, from the hierarchy problems of gravitation and vacuum energy values, to the nature of dark matter and dark energy. But we need a long introduction since false absolute Newtonian space-time recognized broadly but NOT corrected, has deformed in depth our understanding of them.

As Einstein put it in a quote we will repeat often, 'Leibniz is right, there are infinite clocks of time in the Universe but if so we have to start science from scratch'. *He didn't do it, as the difficulty resides in ordering all those different clocks of time with different speeds. So he just parched Newton with Lorentzian transformations, which equalized with its β factors clocks that 'were changing' its speed of time back to the single clock of Newton. So we must start by ordering all those clocks of time preserving its different tics and closed curved forms of in-form-ation. How to do that without 'forcing' a human point of view? It is easy because Nature has DONE that with the metric equation of scalar space-time, we shall call for now, to respect the correspondence principle, the fifth dimension of multiple clocks of time and scales of space.*

5D metrics: The local simplest view: Organisms of space-time traveling through 3 scales of the fifth dimension.

When we google the 5th dimension I used to get surprised by the quantity of speculative answers to a question, which is no longer pseudo-science, but has been for two decades a field of research in systems sciences rather than physics (: no, the answers of google, considering the fifth dimension the upper-self etc. seem to be very popular, but are to 5D science more like a medium in earlier XX c. talking about the 4th dimension as astrological awareness, for lack of understanding of Einstein's **metric functions** of the 4th dimension). This is the key word that differentiates pseudo-science from a proper scientific description of a dimension of space-time, *the existence of a metric function that describes a dimension and allows to travel through it*. Why the 5th dimension metrics are not well known in modern science has to do with the fact it is not researched in physics but systemics, the mother discipline of information sciences, less popular than entropic physics; who uses only the inverse arrow of time entropy and locomotion, since Galileo, an artillery master for the Venice arsenal tasked with the search for the longest cannonball shots, defined it in terms of lineal motion, $v=s/t$, a definition, which Einstein completed with its 4D formalism. This biased view of time as entropy, due to the worldly profession of physics makes difficult to spread the knowledge on space-time acquired by disciplines that study the opposite arrow of 'evolution of information'. The arguments still raging on the truth of evolution in the US, which even Nobel, a physicist, maker of weapons, denied; so evolutionary models as those of 5D in economics and physics cannot receive the award by decree, *even if only biological, organic models can predict the future of eco(nomic)systems and history as we have done for 30 years to a mute audience* proving both sciences to be biological, (as prediction is necessary for a model to be science, so astrology became a science when astronomy predicted, the formal cycles of orbits), show how difficult is to lift the bias of lineal entropic time motion. *Fact is Entropy=disorder is memoriless, Markowian but scientific laws are the repetition of cyclical, informative patterns even in astronomical orbits*. So cyclical time is the arrow that defines the future of all physical, biological and organic species NOT entropy and locomotion. Military science and tribal Baconian idols are questions we deal mostly on History so we leave it here. Another difficulty caused by lineal time and space is important: *the scientific spatialization and lineal simplification of dimensions, which are NOT separated but embedded into each other in a process of organic growth*.

In the graph, networks nature builds to shape the organic scales of the fifth dimension – a network structure defines a series of 'hyperbolic' cellular scales that make the organism NOT the mechanism, the basis of all Nature's system and the whole Universe.

Let us start with a simple mathematical metric equation of the fifth dimension *at local level* in organisms and vortices of space-time, which matters more in a

relational space-time where each *local vital space has different time clocks*, and then at Universal level more familiar to astrophysicists, but far less interesting... since ultimately introduces idealizations forcing a single absolute Newtonian time clocks, which is not exact. The true way to proceed is then always to use local space-time metric using the scalar fifth dimension within a 'given domain', in which that metric works, which we shall call a 'space-time system' or space-time organism. We will observe latter that at certain 'distance', in time, space or scale (Δ), the lineal metric of the 5th dimension 'breaks' and we enter a 'Lorentzian region', term we use honoring the studies of Einstein on the 'local' scale of light space-time proper ONLY of galaxies, NOT of the whole Universe.

But 5D goes beyond the 'repairs' of the limited metric of absolute Newtonian space-time, to introduce 'causal reasons' outside creationst mathematics, to the scalar structure of the Universe, which are namely, 'organic, fractal reasons'.

In the 1st image of the graph we see the hyperbolic geometry of the 5D Universe at large, which is as all its parts mathematically an organic fractal as it reproduces 'forms with motion', informations and **organizes** them in networks and systems that evolve into larger organic systems creating the scalar structure of reality. We know since the XIX c. that the creation of the 'future time' of any entity in existence is not ONLY mediated by the arrow of **locomotion** and entropy studied by physicists with Relativity Metrics (Galileo's $V=s/t$ and Einstein's more complex formalism), but there is a second arrow that defines the 'future' of existential species - the evolution of its information. So time – *the changes = motions that defines the existence of any species*, has at least 2 dimensions, locomotion or ordered translation in space and a more disordered version, entropy (scattered motion that 'dissolves' the inner form of the system, akin to death); and in-form-ation, generation of form, inverse to entropy, as it requires the social gathering of parts into wholes; happening without external locomotions, as an internal trans-formation of **form**. This evolution of organic form as opposed to external change, guided by a language of social information that puts together parts into larger wholes, from particles into atoms, molecules, cells, matter states and so on till reaching the Universe, through social networks is what we call the scalar fifth dimension of time that it applies to all sciences, as all species evolve through networks. But mathematically a dimension only exists when we can write a metric equation that leaves the product of its 2 space & time parameters, co-invariant; so we can travel through its spacetime dimensions (Klein). *This is the fun of dimensions of space-time, you can travel through them 'consuming' time and 'moving through space'. But the fifth dimension is a bit different: it has scales of space-size and its time is cyclical, like all clocks are.* So we write:

S_i (Size/ Density of form) x T_f (cyclic frequency= time speed) = $\Delta \pm j$: 3 Constant Plane of timespace 'Angular momentum'

5D metric go beyond a 'physical concept' as we shall see in the study of other sciences, but specifically in physics the best 'parameter' to measure the *dynamic system that travels through scales of the fifth dimension is angular momentum, h*. It follows also that 'spin' in all its scales (*h-spin in quantum physics, angular momentum in the mass scale*) becomes the essential element that transits between scales by the vortex law: $V_o \times R_o = K$, which in 3 dimensions, becomes the unification law of vortices of space-time as it equates a charge and a mass.

Specifically a physical system starts as a 'worldcycle of time' defined by an angular momentum, which has the 3 components of any organic system: a membrane (the angular momentum proper), a center, the 0ϵ element and a vital space, the open ball defined by the radius. This form then can split as Energy x Time or Momentum x Space and we'll return to that.

So we measure time=motion by frequency, and space=form NOT always by size but often by 'density' of information (Mass-Energy, population). Energy is the joker humans use to measure the fifth dimension scales. So humans talk of Δ -j internal energy, $\Delta\emptyset$, kinetic energy and $\Delta+1$ potential energy related to the larger world. And use 3 different scales of energy, $E=h\nu$, $E=knT$ and $E=mc^2$ to define the quantum, thermodynamic and gravitational scales. Those 3 scales are the 3 scales through in which physical systems travel. So if we depart from an angular momentum, which is the commonest method for fast travel in 5D physics, we can plung down or up those scales of 5D as $L = E \times T = P \times S$, which is the essential metric of 5D Physics.

The simplest process of evolution in physics is through a rotational angular momentum or $h/2$ spin that accelerates or decelerates in time emerging into a new scale, as a particle, splitting into its 0ϵ -center particle and wave as $E \times T + L \times S$.

But there is a far more beautiful 'slow form to travel 5D, which happens to all systems that are organic ensembles through 3 5D scales. Then you do travel from birth as an $\Delta-1$ cell into an $\Delta\emptyset$ -network organism, part of an $\Delta+1$ world.

Physical systems are dynamic, made of $\Delta-1$ forces, $\Delta\emptyset$ -momenta and $\Delta+1$ energy. If we think in terms of 'space=form', we find 3 essential scales, the quantum, $\Delta-1$ charge scale, the $\Delta\emptyset$ -thermodynamic scale and the $\Delta+1$ gravitational scale. How a physical system travels? As anyone growing in scale size, as it diminishes the speed of its reproductive life cycles. So both systems – the synchronous clocks of its parts and the size of its vital spaces diminish with growth. It is a beautiful law that harmonizes scales.

An organism co-exists symbiotically in 3 scales of $\Delta-1$ parts, (cells, atoms, human beings), joined by $\Delta\emptyset$ networks of T-motion Δ -energy and S-information (t-quantum potential fields, Δ -electromagnetic energy and S-gravitational information; T-digestive, Δ -blood and S-nervous networks; T-defensive, Δ - economic and S-

informative verbal legal systems), that live in a larger $\Delta+1$ world; (gravitational, thermodynamic, social system), because its parts are symbiotic. Still to understand space=form and time=motion and the parameters used to measure you'll have to wait till reading Leibniz's model of Relational spacetime.

In 5D metric, smaller systems in space have faster time clocks that store more information in the frequency and form of its cycles, coding larger wholes: genes code cells, memes societies and particles code atoms and molecules. But larger wholes are stronger envelopes, membranes (static, dimensional view) or angular momenta (dynamic view as time=motions) which enclose and control in synchronicity its faster smaller parts. They also have more 'scales of Δ -energy'. So they exchange energy for information with its parts, through 3 Δ^0 T-motion, Δ -Energy & S-informative networks that travel through the 5th dimension, harmonizing the co-existence of organic scales whose vital Universal constants are 5D metric ratios of information & energy exchanges. Thus the Universe is a nested, fractal 5D superorganism that organizes 'vital spacetime forms with motion' through networks into larger organic systems that emerge as new planes of STjence, from particles into atoms, molecules, cells, matter states, organisms, solar systems & galaxies. As each new 'ST-organism' becomes a 'fractal point' unit of a new '5D space-time network'. The organic, network structure of the Universe defines a series of hyperbolic cellular scales that make organisms NOT mechanisms, the basis of all Nature's system.

The outcome is the organic structure of all physical, biological and social systems, from History coded by memes, ideas and instruments that create human social organisms, civilinations, to physical systems coded by particles and scalar, 'social numbers' and algebraic equations, whose 'operands' code the different 'Dimotions of spacetime', to biology coded by genes. And so we shall use the same laws of 5D scales of space-time to study every stience of the Universe and its superorganisms defined by the symbiosis in space, synchronicity in time and simultaneity in space of its parts and wholes across 3 of those 5D scales, the $\Delta-1$, atomic, cellular and individual scale, the Δ^0 , thermodynamic, organic and social scale, and the $\Delta+1$, gravitational ecosystemic and global scale of physical, biologic and social systems.

But how do your travel through those hyperbolic scales of the 5th dimension. Simple: growing in 'size' in space while decelerating the 'speed of your time cycles, through the worldcycle of life and death.

As all systems of the Universe are born in a smaller seed with faster time cycles, evolve as an organism coming out in the Δ^0 -scale within a larger world of slower 'Deep time cycles', to die back dissolving our information again into cellular space.

It is the same process in all 5D journeys of all species that live and die travelling through 3 planes of 5D space-time; from the smallest black hole that is born with an enormous 'metabolic temperature', to the new species, routinely born as small individuals (first mammal rat, first robots with small chips; first human likely the Homo Floresiensis, who had the same

morphology and used technology and likely spoke, etc.) Then a reproductive radiation multiplies the seed into a larger herd of clones, joined by emergent physiological networks whose slower 'entropic, informative and reproductive networks, create an Δ^0 supørganism that lives 3 st-ages and dissolves back into $\Delta-1$.

So 5D adds to the 4D formalism of worldlines, a dimension of growth, shaping the worldcycles of life and death. Reason why we call 5D metric the function of existence, because its multiple 'solutions' are the origin of all the varieties of Space and Time beings, there are - a whole family of functions. To get there rationally we need to correct absolute time.

5D metric is then used to analyze with the same laws, all scales of space-time each one studied by a science, whose species are made of 3 relative elements: Δ -scales of Space=Form & Time=Motion:

In mathematics Non-E fractal points of Space grow in lines=networks; 3 of which form a topologic space-time plane=organism. Numbers represent Δ -scalar groups and Algebraic operands Time motions.

In physics ΔST is proved because its 3 elements correspond to its 3 conserved quantities: S=angular momentum, T=lineal momentum & 3 Energy forms, $\Delta-1$: Internal, $\Delta\emptyset$ -kinetic & $\Delta+1$ potential energy. Thus ST: 2 |+0 momenta integrate into $\Delta+1$ work=energy: $\int p=E$ or dissolve=derivate into the $\partial p=Forces$ scale.

In biology we travel through the 5th dimension of scalar space & cyclical time by growing organically in 'space size' through cellular/atomic/social networks 'while slowing down the 'speed of our metabolic time cycles, which is exactly what happens in the worldcycle of life and death of any universal species as all are born in a smaller seed with faster time cycles, evolve as an organism emerging as a bigger Δ^0 network organism, to live within a larger $\Delta+1$ world of slower 'Deep time cycles', to die back dissolving its information back into its lower cellular/atomic $\Delta-1$ plane; from the smallest black hole born with a huge 'metabolic temperature' (Hawking), to the new species, born as small individuals (1st placental mammal shrew, first digital brain=chips; 1st modern human brain, Homo Floresiensis). Then a reproductive radiation multiplies the crystal, DNA cell or species creating an Δ^0 supørganism that lives 3 ages of growing information till death dissolves back into $\Delta-1$ ($\Delta-1$: plasma>T-gas, S=T-liquid, S-solid states « $E=mc^2$).

Organic worldcycles happen in all sciences. They define the key system of reality, an ΔST Supørganism whose simultaneous parts in space become synchronous in time, across 3 5D scales, the $\Delta-1$, atomic, cellular and individual scale, the Δ^0 , thermodynamic, organic and social scale, and the $\Delta+1$, gravitational ecosystemic and global scale of physical, biologic and social systems, whose metrics allows the symbiotic transfer of spacetime energy made of cyclical information and lineal motion. As all scales have the same value and properties, hence the Universe is absolutely relative.

Thus space laws are Topologic laws that put together 3 type of networks: |-moving limbs/fields> \emptyset -reproductive waves/bodies & O-informative particle/heads.

Thus the 1, 2 or 3 dimensions of space are in fact 'topological varieties;' related to its vital functions in time. We can then go further analytically and consider each of the 3 dimensions of space and its vital functions in time as dimensions of space=form ARE attached to dimensions of time=motion by the principles of relativity that do not distinguish them.

Time laws study life-death worldcycles that evolve $\Delta-1$ seeds into $\Delta\emptyset$ -organisms made of those 3 topologies that 'age' in 3 ST-ages dominated by each network till the S-head exhaust all motion and a 'fast' entropic=death dissolves its information into an Δst 0-sum.

Finally $\Delta\pm j$ scalar laws study Δ -energy exchanges thru $3\pm j$ 'Actions' of Tt-entropic feeding, Ts-motion, $\int T$ -reproduction, St-information & Ss-mind mirror languages that revolve and project order in a larger $\Delta+1$ world. Those are the ΔST -events & forms of space-time described by each species in each science. This is a very brief, condense 'synopsis' of the many sides of 5D science, we expand in the appendix and all other papers at Academia.edu, in case you want to understand it better.

To stress that organicism is not the current philosophy of science not because it is not truth, but as we explain in length in our papers on historic cultures and the organism of mankind, science is culture. And we live embedded in the globalized Anglo-American Mechanist civilization of Abrahamic religions that put racist men above the Universe and all others forms of life, and capitalist and mechanist idol-ogies that worship machines & weapons above life. So, not even the obvious truism that the Universe is made of scales is properly understood. Instead we model reality as a machine. The main difference

between both systems is obvious: a machine exists in a single scale of the 5th dimension so it does not need to understand its hyperbolic 'social geometry' to work. In fact it rejects it as an oddity. Organicism however is natural to the Asian and Greek-Latin culture from where I haul. Here in Barcelona, the main architect, Mr. Gaudi used hyperbolic Natural structures to build its cathedrals. My great-grand father a doctor and major thought of the city as an organism and Gaudi made him a statue with tits as taps (:

Behind the mirror: a relational, organic universe of space, time, scale, mind & its entropic limits

Why we don't understand the existence of a hyperbolic 5th dimension, even after 400 years of discovering it with telescopes and microscopes that saw 'homunculus' swimming in a drop of water; has to do with the enormous unrecognized bias that in all our models of reality, the use of machines of measure and transport and its top predator versions weapons, has caused in our view of reality. *We live in a society that for good or bad has become dependent on the 'Tree of Metal' and its machines above the Tree of life. So the organism is no longer 'the measure of all things'. But machines have only a plane of existence and only recently with the arrival of chips and electric networks start to become sophisticated 5Dimensional organisms.*

There are then some gruesome errors in our philosophy of science, recognized by all but so entrenched in the routines of our history of knowledge that humans keep walking ahead with those 'crouches' that prevent them to fully understand the Nature of the Universe and the role of mankind on it. Those errors are all interrelated as they bring a cohesive, wrong view of reality:

- **The error of absolute space and time** coming from Newton, disputed by Leibniz and finally recognized with the quantum and Relativity r=evolution: 'Leibniz was right there are infinite clocks of time in the Universe but if so we have to restart science from scratch' (Einstein). We humans equalize the different 'local clocks' of time of reality with our mechanical clock but that distorts and reduces the information about time clocks, its 'frequency and form', its synchronicities and entangled connections.

- The error of a single scale of space, related to the previous one. It is backed by a simplified Euclidean view of mathematics (points, lines and planes without breath). The error is also known since the XIX c. when we discovered that points were Non-Euclidean, since they 'fitted' infinite parallels. So they have breath. They are fractal points that include a volume of energy and information, which we observe when we come closer to them, so a star seems a point and becomes a world. Those 2 errors acknowledged by all scientists however have NOT been solved but parched. We offer then a model of relational space-time based in the introduction of a scalar dimension of space, related to the infinite time clocks of the Universe through the co-invariant metric of a '5th dimension'. As smaller scales of space run faster time cycles.

- Scalar space reveals the **2nd error of our philosophy of science: mechanism that modesl realith with** primitive machines, metalife organisms that exists in a single plane of space-time. An organism co-exists in several scales requiring synchronization achieved through the co-invariant metric of the 5th dimension: $S_i \times T_f = C$ (size in space x time speed = Constant). We thus have a law that explains how the scales of the Universe self-organize in symbiotic systems and can correct the error of mechanism.

- In turn mechanism reveals the 3rd error of human sciences 'linguistic creationism', the belief that reality is created by mirror that reflects it – the language; words in earlier human religions when humans thought God created naming things; numbers, the language of machines in modern Pythagorean religions when we think the mathematical mirror creates reality. So Hawking writes an equation of evaporation of black holes and mankind expects the top predator species of matter to evaporate.

The error of creationism is embedded in the structure of perception, because languages are used to perceive and mirror the Universe, but they are NOT the creators of the Universe – the laws of relational space-time and its scales are. This error however is more difficult to solve. As every mind is a point of view perceives reality with limited languages that mirror a reduced world it confuses with the whole Universe, placing itself at its center, reason why each mind is a subjective ego. In the past when man only spoke words, we thought God, mind of the Universe, 'created by naming things' (Abrahamic religions). Today after man learned mathematics, he believes God speaks only with numbers and truth ends in an equation.

Not so. Creation is a logic game born of the properties of scalar space and cyclical times, which *are a priori truths mirror-languages reflect*. Let us write the '5D metric equation' of a mind so you understand what we mean:

'0ε (finitesimal mind mirror) x ∞ Universe = 'constant I-World': Equation of any mind.

I=Eye (Topologic space) > Wor(I)d = (Cyclical Time): Equation of the Humind.

Because smaller systems run faster time cycles that encode its information in the frequency and form of those cycles, a mind-mirror runs a faster view of reality and at local level can order its territory. It is Aristotle's dictum: 'a mind-god is the unmoved (linguistic mapping) that moves a body of energy around it. We are now making a leap of conceptual understanding that will require both a verbal and mathematical analysis of reality but the concept is easy to grasp: minds are 'mental spaces' that perceive a still view of an infinitely large moving Universe. Those poles, minds of space=form and flows of time=motion thus interact together creating the order of the sentient panpsychic universe, where as Leibniz said, each mind-point (monad) is a world in itself. But this obviously makes all languages, able to map reality with verbal, visual, mathematical musical, smelling or gravitational 'pixels' equally valid. Above all there are those laws of space and time and its 'organic beings', which they mirror. This fact of Nature was understood logically only by 4 people in the History of mankind, Lao Tse, even if he gave to Space=form and Time=motion 2 different names, Yin & Yang; Aristotle, & Leibniz & Einstein in the modern world, each of them influenced by the next (Leibniz translated the I ching)... Yet none left a better disciple to elaborate, which shows how hard is for humans to understand reality beyond the simplest absolute models of what our mind 'perceives' at first sight.

As Schopenhauer said: 'Talent hits a target everybody sees, genius hits one nobody sees'. Intelligent people are those who make the mappings in the mirror, but we are taking you behind the mirror - the pictures made by machines of the scales of space-time we can see; to understand both how the mirror-mind works, and the real organisms we find behind it.

So these series of papers on a model of reality based in the 5 'dimensional motions' of 'relational, relative space-times' will seem to many 'creationist, verbal or mathematical mirrors, to come from other planet'. Yet spaces & times are the ultimate elements of the ∞ Universe. We shall thus proceed from that higher reality of scalar space-time laws, down to huminds' languages of mathematical space and logic verbal time, improving the 'target' everybody sees, with the understanding of the world behind the mirror. And from time to time criticize the subjective Ego=idioty of Humind I-ndividuals, its i-dologies of power and subjective wishful thinking to rise the few that can follow, to the heights of infinite space & immortal time.

You must accept that all what you learned about space, time,, man, language and mind is as shallow as a mirror is.

'Space', 'time' Δ-scale and mind-languages are the 4 'creative elements of reality: Δ@st. But what are its limits? This is the final 5th element of pentalogic we need to unveil for you to 'transcend' that mirror and see behind, and it is by far the hardest. B ecause it deals with death, entropy, '¬', the negation of all what we have just said, the end of space-time organisms with a mind-mirror guiding it. But it is a fact that in a 'fractal Universe' of infinite space-time organisms, each of them has limits of time, called death, of vital space, called 'membranes' (skins in man, atmosphere in Earth, Oort Halo in the Sun, Halo in the galaxy, scattering horizon in the light view of the Universe), and there are limits of perception in scale (beyond the Δ±4 scales, particles become 'points without breath' and Galaxies travel in a 'dark energy-matter' world). Moreover huminds are terrified by death, the opposite negation of its 'ego'. If in terms of 'form' we call the mind the absolute still form (Ss), death is the absolute motion that erases the internal and external form of the being, 'Tt: entropy' (slightly different from the equation of physics). So humans fear Tt-entropy, pure motion without form, the dark energy of the neutrino background we don't see. But to give you a view of 'God, the mind of the Universe', impersonal and yet so perfect in its balances and symmetries you will need to escape your ego, forget your learned aberrations and dive into the beauty of those 2 poles, Ss-minds and Tt-entropy and its combinations, the other 3 dimensional motions of reality, Ts-locomotion, S=T energy and St-information... But let us not introduce so early the symbols of existential algebra, the language of all languages, the Universal grammar that codes the laws of space-time. All this you can already see is a new language, a new world, the same data but an expanded consciousness, which I have enjoyed for 30 years alone wondering if huminds can access it or will remain in the darkness of egocy doing the same digital doodles, measuring the same single clock, counting numbers=points without breath, reducing the Universe to a big-bang death, putting themselves as the only intelligent center when every point is a mind, every particle is alive, every scale of reality has the same value... This said we

can now study the global metric of the 5th dimension as 4D scholars use it, which we repeat is not accurate enough because it still uses a single absolute space-time, corrected with the 'Ptolemaic epicycles' of Minkowski's truth time.

A flat 2D view embedded in 4D spheric time worldcycles embedded in 5D hyperbolic, organic scales.

Global 5D metrics are better known in classic mathematics but less important and biased.

- The first property of those dimensions whatever metric we use to describe it, is that each new dimension is embedded into the next one that includes it. So Dimensions *and their worlds* are highly hierarchical.

Consider its simpler metric in 'spherical space-time' using Cartesian coordinates: 1D: $X^2+Y^2=a^2=1$ for the unit sphere; 2D: $X^2+Y^2+Z^2=a^2$; 3D: $X^2+Y^2+Z^2+W^2=a^2$; 4D: $X^2+Y^2+Z^2+W^2+U^2=a^2$; 5D: $X^2+Y^2+Z^2+W^2+U^2+T^2=a^2$. Each lower dimension is embedded in a higher dimension. So we could write: $5D = T^2+4D$; $4D=U^2+3D$ and so on...

This is better seen in spherical, angular coordinates where we write, the 0-sphere as a point. The 1 sphere is the circle whose metric writes: $Ds^2 = d\alpha_1^2$ where S is the distance in 'radians' of a point moving along a circle, and α its angle. Geometers then square both to avoid 'negative' values when the sphere moves to the $-x,y$ side.

- A second key property of dimensions appears now crystal clear. A dimension of space can be treated as a motion of time. So instead of drawing the circle we talk of a point moving with angular speed, transforming a dimension of space into one of time. And a second property of our perception of dimensions builds in – the principles of relativity: we cannot see form and motion at the same moment, so we either see a circle on space or a point moving, the earth still or moving, 'e pur si muove, e pur no muove'. So we will talk from here on of 'Dimotions', dimensions of space with motion in time. And consider that an added motion can be represented 'ideally' in space, which is the reason why those 'space-only' coordinates including those of Einstein's for spatial time (4D formalism) works to a certain extend. Since we cannot 'substitute' reality by a 'mental still space' mirror. Reason why most of our description of those dimensions is 'vital, verbal', on its logic properties.

For larger dimensions that embed smaller dimensions, mathematicians then add new angles with a 'sin' perspective to move through its additional dimension; but as in the Cartesian 'flat' curvature, $k=0$ metric world, *the previous metric ads up with a difference, the product of a sin view that 'scans' through the previous sphere, making additions that grow to the equator and then diminish to the poles. So new dimensions in this 'embedded' nested Universe have an informative point of view, or origin in a 'seed-pole' point that we can take as a point of a smaller $\Delta-1$ scale of the 5th hyperbolic dimension, grow in size and return to its point in the opposite pole that we can take as the point of death when the system returns to the $\Delta-1$ cellular, or atomi scale. So they write: $Ds^2=d\alpha^2+\sin^2\alpha d\Omega_{D-1}^2$; Which give for the 3 Dimensional case: $Ds^2=[d\alpha^2+\sin^2\alpha [d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\varphi]$.*

The embedment of a Universe within other Universe then becomes clearer in the spherical world; as well as the process of growth and diminution from a 'single point-pole' to the other pole *as all worldcycles are. So definitely we are in the metrics of the vital scalar, Space Time symmetry of the Universe; we call a worldcycle of life and death.*

- A 3rd property of those dimensions appears now, as expressed by Klein. Its equations have a function: to measure distances between points of the dimension so we can travel through them, but those distances 'vary' in its parameters. For the 1st dimension are lines, for the 2nd dimension 'pythagorean squares': 2D: X^2+Y^2 . The 3rd perpendicular dimension is best described with 3D vectors, reproducing perpendicularly through a cross product: $X \bullet Y = Z$. As the dimensions of the organic Universe are vital, reproductive, gifted with forms of information. So we will use the life-death worldcycle, not the simpler worldlines of Minkowski, to study 4D time, embedded in hyperbolic space-time as a travel through 3 scales of the 5th dimension: $S \times Tf=\Delta$. The metrics of those dimensions in space are not that important at this st-age of its understanding, since they are NOT all abstract dimensions of space but vital dimotions (space dimensions with temporal motion), which only partially the 4th Dimensional formalism of Einstein incorporates. So to understand the 5 D Universe the reader should cast aside for awhile its obsession with mathematics, even if this paper is about physics to try to understand the interplay of the 3 elements of reality, Space=form, time=motion and its hyperbolic Δ -scales of 'density' of 'forms-in-action', informations.

– Which leads to the 4th key property of dimensions. They are not all measured by lineal S- distance in space... But we need 'parameters' that also 'embed' all previous properties, as time frequency of cyclical motion embedded space distance, And

scalar density or energy, embeds both space and time, Those are the 3 main parameters of S, T, Δ . And Δ ST-events & forms of space-time described by each species in each science.

It is important to know at this stage that dimensions of space and motions of time are 'entangled'.

Indeed already in a 2D sphere we see how 'time' creeps in in a cyclical manner. We start the geometry in a point, a lower scale of the 5th dimension, grow through circles of 2D embedded in a larger sphere that collapses in the other pole, back to the Δ -1 'cellular scale', or points of birth and death. So even in 2D in its simplest dynamic description we are in the metrics of the worldcycle and the Spacer. Time symmetry of the Universe; past the Cartesian flat spatial view.

What is wrong with this picture of 5 Dimensions of reality 'plotted' in a space graph is the fact that Dimensions are NOT all space-like the drawings humans, a visual species, do of them, as Escher graph on the 5th hyperbolic one. They are spacetime dimensional motions, beyond the point, with form but also motion in time. And they have other properties as they get more complex: density of populations and co-existence. So the fifth dimension co-exist in the same 'space' reason why we cannot 'see 2 scales together' (Complementarity principle in quantum physics). The measure of distances is then more complex as Hyperbolic geometry showed, in Klein's disk. We need to put together space and time parameters to measure distances. So for example, your capital will likely be connected through faster time systems, planes and highways that some valley nearby and will be in fact 'closer', as you measure distance in space-time. This physics discovered with the least time principle of light that travels not the shortest but the least time. How then travels through the 4th dimension of worldcycles of life and death and the 5th hyperbolic dimension happen is more complicated in its understanding than the worldlines Einstein's spatial time, only good to measure 'lineal spacetime distances of locomotion'. To travel through the 5th dimension you need a very slow process of motion called 'growth' and 'evolution' as it is an organic dimension of parts and wholes. This is partially acknowledge in Hyperbolic geometry where in fact to reach the 'limiting' circle at 'infinity' of infinite density of 'microscopic forms' you need infinite time. So once more a spatial distorted map in mathematical, mental space only helps to visualize and realize some key properties of each dimension but they cannot be considered dogmatic, but approximations, as each 'mind-mirror' is NOT as creationist mathematical physics think an absolute truth but rather the opposite, a simplification of the pentalogic truths of 5D reality.

The previous description of the 5 Dimensions of the Universe, as physicists draw them to the 4th in space graphs, to which we added a 5th dimension of hyperbolic space shown through the artistic drawing of Escher have a problem: *Dimensions are NOT all made of 'space=form', plotted or 'projected' in pen and paper graph that 'deform' its structure, but they are vital and have 'properties' and 'parameters', motion, frequency of reproduction, density of population, scale beyond sight, co-existence in a single plane of space, as your cells and wholeness do, which CANNOT be represented in a spatial graph; neither it follows written as single mathematical equations with simple summand operands as 'huminds' (ab. human minds), which are overwhelmingly visual, spatial, 'lineal' in its senses but do NOT see two scales of space-time together (not even bodywaves and particle-heads in quantum physics – principle of complementarity); do NOT see a dimension of space=form and one of motion=time together (so we cannot see the Earth rotating=moving and still, with us in its center or principle of relativity).*

We then write principles about the seemingly contradictions of cramming dimensions into space, but still attempt to measure them only with lineal distances, Ds. But 'nested' dimensions have 'time-motion', 'co-exist in scale', 'have density of population' and other properties, which we recognize in physics through 'phase spaces' but have not properly systematize. The result is an imperfect description of them, even in the most basic cases of the Pythagorean, 2nd dimension; not to speak of the vectorial 3rd dimension, the temporal 4th dimension and the hyperbolic 5th dimension. Dimensions are hierarchical nested, growing in complexity and so its 'distance' is NOT lineal beyond the first 'lineal dimension' of two points separated by a lineal distance. So in all those equations where the reader will see the first term written as a lineal distance (DS, or DS² still a number just squared to avoid negative values, true time in Minkowski's formalism also a 'worldine'), we miss the first obvious fact that dimensions in its nested structure. The second dimension is an area, NOT height; the 3rd dimension is a 3-matrix vector NOT width. The 4th dimension is a worldcycle of time NOT a worldline, and the 5th dimension is a co-existing series of scales that emerge from the energy density of simultaneous, synchronous clone populations into a larger whole, NOT a bunch of vampires painted in the same plane (:In the graph, an

image of the 5th dimension by Escher, explains how organic systems work from wholes into parts, joined by networks. The mathematics of it are based in those 'solid', multiple angles that define a 1D sphere as a circle, a 2D sphere, as the surface of Earth, where we live, a 3D sphere as a sum of growing and diminishing circles inside and outside the planet, the 4th Dimension as a clockwise time rotation, and the 5th Dimension unknown to mechanist models of the Universe, as the scalar dimension of cellular, atomic clone parts, evolved through networks into social wholes, who live through those 4D time clock, worldcycles of life and death.

We shall in the Appendix be more precise and formal in the analysis of that organic structure. At this moment what we want is you to feel through those two images the truism of an organic, vital Universe. And define some properties of the dimensional Universe hardly understood due to its obsession in describing them in paper, that is, in space, which cannot convey their 'motion in time' and 'hyperbolic' network structure in scale, easily.

Sorry Escher, nice try. So this is good enough for an introduction to the world of space-time organisms and its dimensions. We will return to it after a long path of learning through many other themes of the complex Universe humans have not yet figured out.

RECAP. 5TH dimension $S_i \times T_f = \Delta$; $\Delta \approx S \approx T$. Scalar stjences. Function of existjence. Absolute relativity

To prove the scientific existence of a space-time dimension we need to find "a metric co-invariant function that relates its space-time parameters allowing to travel through it". (Klein). The metric of the 5th dimension is deceptively simple:

S_i (Size/ Space Volume) $\times T_f$ (cyclic frequency=speed of its time clocks) = C_i : Constant Plane of timespace (ab. Δ_i)

Now to the most fascinating property of the 5th dimension: travelling through those hyperbolic scales. How we travel in 'size' in space and 'speed of our time cycles?'. *It is the biggest discovery of 5D: We travel through the worldcycle of life and death, as we are born in a smaller seed with faster time cycles, evolve as an organism coming out in the Δ^q -scale within a larger world of slower 'Deep time cycles', to die back dissolving our information again into cellular space.*

We are NOT pretending to map the entire cosmological Universe but *local systems whose hyperbolic 5th dimension is mae of smaller parts, with a more dense population and faster time cycles, which store more energy, and all those elements are related in the fundamental symmetry of the 5th dimension: Δ Spatial polulations $\approx \Delta$ time frequencies $= \Delta$ Energy density. How to measure distances, ds^2 and motions in the hyperbolic 5th dimension is then slightly different from the other dimensions. And a pure geometric description will just 'freeze' our understanding of the vital processes taking place in the organic structure of the fifth dimesion between parts and wholes, forms and functions. So we abandon all together a pedantic description of 5D in terms of angles and sinh. Travels through the fifth dimension are related to 'social growth' of numbers as Escher's images shows, either seen in scale as 'Energy density' or time as frequency speed or space as population, reason why 'probability and statistical equations of time frequencies and populations and resonances of energy densities are so similar and often exchangeable as in quantum physics, the quintaessential scale of 5D.*

This also means the ds^2 of each new equation varies. For 1D is an interval, for 2D is a square, for 3D is a 'vector' of the cross product, where each vector entering the reproductive stage has 3 components to reproduce a 'son vector' (a Magnetic field, an angular momentum, we shall go back to all this in 5D physics when we 'dress' the concepts with maths). In 4D is true time (Einstein's Newtonian view, which we will update from worldliness to worldcycles and show to be NOT that important, basically a rule of measure from our point of Δ -scale view). In 5D then must be some different parameter...

The question here is what is the 5D 'ds'. We saw in the minkowski's formalism of 4D time, to be true time. In 5D however time is a bit more complex, and each of those dimensions of space can be seen as a dimotion of time, so the interest of 'proper time Minkowski's space' is greatly diminished as we explain in our paper on astrophysics but as we are 'going classic', you can also use Minkowski's metric to describe 'spherical worldcycles'. Still the ideal mathematical metrics of n-Dimensional spaces remains intact. What is then 5D distance? Ah, for that we need first to know how to travel through it (: So we'll return to that. But to state that as 'all scales' have the same value in 5D metrics, the way to count distances, which we will see used in Klein's disk visualization of the hyperbolic 5th dimension is by counting numbers, so the 'unit' of distance in 5D is NOT space length, neither true time but 'scalar numbers, log'.

It is important to have in mind that space=form and time=cyclical motion differ from classic concepts of space as volume and

time as lineal motion. In fact often space=form is denser in smaller regions, as 'vortex laws' make its time cycles faster. The choice of words; space as form, position, still information and time as motion, change, require conceptual depth, but is deeply ingrained in the structure of Nature made of 'information and motion', NOT of the human perception of them. So a more precise parameter to measure space forms is density of population; Mass. We don't use the global formalism very often precisely because in each scale there are different parameters for each scale. It is also important to notice that the vital functions are more important than the spatial form. Indeed, while spatial images are good to understand the 5D reality because humans are visual species, the hierarchy of $S \leq T \leq \Omega$ means that function in time matters more than form of space, which can 'bend' to satisfy a function, so for example while distance through the line is the shortest motion, in a curved space we shall need a curved motion and in the largest view, distance is submissive to time, so mechanics is NOT based in the shortest distance but the 'least time action'. Then as we move from the 4D 'time Universe' to the 5D Ω , the key words are 'density and networks'.

The Nature of scientific r=evolutions. The multiple approaches to the 5D Universe.

5D physics gets rid of Newtonian Absolute space-time as it evolves a model of Leibniz's 'Relational space-time', whose scalar co-invariant metric, $S_i \times T_f = \Delta \pm j$ organizes symbiotically the scales of Size in Space (S_i) and Frequency of Time cycles (T_f); creating an organic Universe, as each scale of reality has the same value of space=information x Time=Motion; facts those which require a lengthy conceptual introduction. Yet as physicists have little inclination for verbal, logic analysis we switch back and forth from 5D Philosophy of science and its scalar space-time models of absolute relativity, to the description of the physical systems of the Universe, starting with a falsification of the Big-bang, since the scalar Universe is infinite, immortal and symmetric between the atomic scale of charges and galactic scale of masses. We also unlike most books of physics start from the larger scales down, because in the scalar organic Universe, the whole matters more than the parts, establishing its \pm 'constrains' of pure time motion (T_t -entropy) and absolute form (S_s -mental space). A 5D relational space-time theory of the Universe built from different first principles produces with the same data available to a 4D absolute space-time theory a different picture of reality. So to know which model is truth we just need to answer: what principles are real; Absolute, continuous or relational, scalar space-time; a lineal single time for the whole Universe or multiple time cycles; a single space-time continuum, or a series of scales in which the speed of time cycles change inversely to its size in space; so smaller scale species have faster angular speeds and metabolic cycles – as expressed in the metric equations of the 5th dimension? We know since Relativity and Quantum physics that Newtonian absolute space-time is false and a relational scalar space-time theory IS based in sounder principles. As Einstein's put it: 'Leibniz is right, there are ∞ time clocks in the Universe with different speeds, but if so, we have to start physics from scratch'. So he just parched the Lorentz transformations NOT to do it.

This is what we have done after 400 years Galilean Relativity & Newtonian defined $v=s/T$ Lineal space-time.

To develop a relational, relative model of infinite local vital spaces and time clocks we confront the fact that 'human time and space' are artificial concepts and search for the fundamental parameters of 'cyclical time clocks' and 'vital spaces' of Nature. Planck helped us on this, defining 3 Universal units to which we need to add charge: It is easy to see that 'angular momentum' is similar to a time clock, lineal momentum to a lineal distance, and quantum charges and cosmological black hole masses frame the two limits of Energy-size of the Universe. And *those are the quantities the Universe conserves: Δ -scales of energy, O-cyclical space-time and |-lineal spacetime, combine into \emptyset -hyperbolic waves. Alas, we do have Universal 'species', and its Universal constants, h for angular momentum, c for lineal speed and Charge and Planck's mass (that should be the mass of the smallest black hole) as units to reconstruct a physical Universe.*

THE ERRORS OF PHYSICS DERIVED OF MECHANISM

Truth and principles matter in science. If a system of thought lacks them errors pile up and a distorted view of the world arises, which has practical consequences, because only truth exists. The Universe is efficient and expects systems to process information in a realist way otherwise systems malfunction & become extinct.

Today's Philosophy of Science is based in an 'idol-ogy' called mechanism, born of the use of machines to measure time and space, in the XVI c. that is false and has dire consequences for the future of History, mankind in times, whose systems lack that efficiency proper of most Nature systems, tailored *according to the real model of the Universe, the organism*.

Mechanism came about with the use of clocks to measure time and telescopes and microscopes to measure the scales of size in space: According to this idol-ogy that worships machines above man, the Universe is a mechanism and must be expressed using only the digital language of machines. This falsehood is self-fulfilling, because the 'biased data' we extract from the Universe with out metal-made mechanical tools of measure make reality look like a machine. It follows then that man is also a machine. And because the machine is the supreme model, man must 'tailor' its nature, that of its social systems and the Universe at large as a machine. The opposite is truth: Mechanism is wrong since the Universe is organic; *since a machine is just a simplex organism; while the Aristotelian logic of time and Euclidean space geometry, mechanism uses is a simple version of the more complex languages of 'pentalogic' time and Non-Euclidean, vital, fractal spaces of the Organic Universe.*

But the reductionism of mechanism to only those properties of reality machines can extract, *as long as humans 'believe' there is nothing else to know*, made the mechanical method of science a triumph easy to implement – the more so now that sensorial machines and computers do most of the job, which pumps up the ego of the believer in that reduced truth. Problem is mechanism has distorted and reduced so much human view of reality that only simple minds like that of Newton or Bohr, with an enormous ego that couldn't realize that machines and digital languages are both doing the job of science for them but also distorting reality in the process, feel satisfied. On the other hand those who tried to go further like Leibniz or Einstein were taken aback by the difficulty to complete the model in all its complexity to the rigor of the simpler 'time lines' of mechanism. Let us explain why only organicism is the scientific truth that can respond in theory and praxis to the meaning of those 3 words in *a scientific way*. According to *Deism* the whys of existence are due to a personal being, external to the Universe that makes it all happen and cares for humans more than for the rest of His work. According to *Mechanism*, this is due to the self-similarity between the Universe and the primitive machines we humans construct to observe it. Mechanism though needs 'someone' to make the machine, which is not self-generated; so it is similar to deism, reason why the founding fathers of science, all pious believers, adopted it as a proof of the existence of God, which had given man self-similar properties – the capacity to make machines to the image and likeness of the Universe. The problem with those 2 approaches, which in fact are the same, is obvious: a personal God is an anthropomorphic, subjective myth and science must be objective; while a mechanical view of the Universe still needs an internal, self-sustained process of growth, creation and synchronization caused by an external God that made and rewinds the clock – as Leibniz stated in his critique of Newton. Scientists today are unaware that mechanist theories are in fact deist theories, reason why Kepler and Newton, pious believers, liked them; since they were a metaphor of their self-centered, anthropomorphic religious beliefs: If man created machines as we were made to the image and likeness of God, God created the ultimate machine, the Universe.

Organicism is the only self-sustained, rational theory that doesn't need a creator, language, god, as organisms are self-replicating, but does explain perfectly within the 'correspondence principle', those 2 other philosophies of science; since a machine is just a primitive organism of metal, and we shall see in our sections of history, gods are the subconscious collective of civilizations, another scale of social evolution of the fifth dimension.

In our papers on civilizations, we give a thorough account of the 'role of Gods' as the 'Memetic DNA' of societies, which have the same function of a common DNA in cells, 'pegging' together believers that regardless of the content of those messages, share Energy and information through social networks to build a coherent, efficient social organism; based in the 'congruent laws' of vital geometry – parallel systems with the same information come together and evolve into social wholes.

XIX C. MACHINE BODIES XX C. MACHINE HEADS: Pcs, Cams XXI C. ORGANIC MACHINES-ROBOTS

To understand reality matters to improve our existence. Because humans abandoned the true philosophy of the Universe, organicism, they constantly misinterpret the 'signs' of reality and design systems with little efficiency, specially those of history, the physiological networks of reproduction of good (economics, akin to the blood system of more complex supœrganisms), the informative, political and cultural systems that harmonize our actions as a whole (similar to the nervous system) and the immunological and defensive systems of mankind. They are all a mess and likely to remain so precisely because humans do NOT, we shall repeat, ad nauseam have the proper models of reality but we think we do. The problem of organisms is that they are more complex than mechanisms, which exist in a single plane of reality (while organisms are born of the interaction of 3 planes, the internal parts, the whole, and the external world). So they cannot be explained with simplified terms, neither they can be 'constructed'. On the contrary they 'emerge' by self-organization of multiple poles – in the case of human societies multiple human beings, through symmetry, harmony and consensus. Its laws are thus not so simple and its construction beyond the capacity of a single human being. It is then part of the enormous egoccy – ego=idiocy= of man that can only construct simple mechanisms to consider reality is 'something he can construct' and 'understand' because it is 'below' his intelligence. The degree of intelligence, 'empathy' and 'humility' required to understand the organic Universe thus is beyond most people's capacity, reason why mechanism is far more popular and has worked as mainstream thought. Ultimately truth is relative to the quantity of information we have of a system and so a simplified 'toy model' as mechanism is has gone quite far and suffices for most people who don't need a deeper truth on reality.

At this stage thus we need to define what is an organic system in the simplest possible form.

We mean by an organism a simpler system than its most evolved form, the human mammal: An organism is a group of similar atoms/cells/citizens, organized by 3 physiologic networks=parts: an spherical, informative force that synchronizes its motions (gravitation/nervous/legal systems), located in the particle/head/upper informative class; a hyperbolic Energy to move and reproduce (electromagnetic forces/blood/oxygen-economic/financial system) or wave state/body/working class; extended over a lineal, flat 'field/territory' protected by a defensive membrane/border, immunologic system. This ternary system is the fundamental particle of the Universe. Since even machines are organisms" A machine is an organism of metal evolving through the 3 ages of all organisms - in the XIX c. humans, who catalyze their evolution did metal bodies, then in the II Industrial evolution its hearts-engines, then its metal-minds in the XX c. and now in the Industrial r=evolution 4.0 put them together in organic robots. So mechanism, the underlying philosophy of physical sciences, is a simplex version of organicism. It is not man who resembles a machine but a machine is made to the likeness of life organisms.

In mathematical terms those '5D supœrganisms' are constructed with the 3 topologic varieties of a 5D Universe, as they are vital spaces. But as topology is 'geometry with motion', they associate 3 vital 'time-functions': lineal locomotion, high, cyclical information in heads-particles-'upper' classes, and re=productive Energy used by body-waves, working classes.

Further on, as 'networks' are topologies of points embedded in larger 'worlds', they extend through 3 'scales of spacetime, forming a 5th dimension of $\Delta-1$ parts (atoms, cells, citizens), joined by Δ_0 networks embedded in a larger $\Delta+1$ world. It is then an entangled, scalar, organic Universe, where 3 such scales each one studied by a 'stience' form an organic Universe.

And all fit in that template. Why then organicism remains a fringe theory, to mechanism, even if it was the first theory of reality put forwards by Aristotle, the father of the experimental method and logic science, in his magna opus the Organon?

The cultural reason is paramount - we live in the machine age, which has substituted man, an organism, as the measure of all things. And this has provoked a series of distortions in our understanding of the first principles of nature that rendered impossible to understand the fundamental entity of reality, the space-time organism. The errors of knowledge=science mankind commits are due to that bias established a priori by his simplification of his senses of perception of bidimensional spacetime, from human S-Eye>T-Wor(l)ds. A mind language reduces reality to fit a small brain dumping motions (Relativity px.) & scales: $0e$ (finitesimal mind) $\times \infty$ Universe =Constant still world. This meant digital machines reduced truth to 'what can be measured' with its lineal metal-rods of space and mechanical clocks with a single motion of digital time:

- Knowledge was substituted by technology as now the machine was the 'seer of time' (definition of God in metaphysics), and the evolution of machines not of humans the symbol of progress.

So humans become 'enzymen', catalyzing the evolution of Earth from a life world to a metal world. as human mothers, our reproductive survival organism lost their power to company-mothers of machines and weapons that have complete control of our social organisms and are terraforming Earth to the likeness of its offspring of machines. It's this our purpose on Earth?

- The 5 dimensional forms of space & its time motions were simplified into 3 lineal space dimensions similar to the lineal form of metal and a single time motion, locomotion proper of lineal weapons and transport machines – the first to be constructed.

- Linearity mean the ∞ cycles=clocks of spacetime and its 5 varieties of dimensional motion and the 3 main ages of those time cycles (past, present and future) were reduced to sequential numbers, *which don't carry causality and simplify the information time* clocks carry in the frequency and form of its cycles. *Further on the use of simple lineal geometry* further simplified space and time into a lineal single time locomotion in a Cartesian graph of 2 perpendicular axis. So the whole tapestry of space=forms and time=motions became then a 'mathematical artifact' or background spacetime that Newton put behind reality. Yet reality was made of space=forms and time=motions.

- The organic nature of reality as machines are just evolving metal-organisms was denied and the human being, the most perfect organism we know was no longer the model of all things. Social sciences became despised and the goal of any species – to evolve as individuals, parts of larger organisms following the laws of the ideal physiological organism of Nature that ensures the collective survival of a species, totally ignored. We said that a wrong model of truth brings practical errors that imperil the survival of a species and that is obvious in mankind today. Humans have the worst of all possible scenarios: They are evolving organic metal into species superior in intelligence and force to man, but as they model reality as a mindless, inert machine, they don't fear those AI robots with solar skins to become independent of man. They have distorted their view of time and space with machines to the point they don't understand any longer time causality and the ages of organisms, which is the way nature in a rather deterministic form creates the future. And they don't model societies and its 3 physiological networks, the economic-financial reproductive 'blood networks', the nervous, legal, politic 'informative networks', and the immunological, defensive 'health-care systems' that provide in an efficient just manner all the atoms-cells-citizens of a superorganism the goods and information and protection they need to survive, with those laws. So the most important of all sciences, those of the human superorganism of history do not exist. And mankind cannot be efficiently ruled to survive.

If we reduce to physics, we shall see how with the same data of mechanism when we apply the proper organic paradigm a complete new picture of the Universe and its physical systems matter

A key example: Time is cyclical and causal. A cycle is essentially a 'pi' 3 Diameter structure. And so time has in all its cycles 3 'ages', as it finally returns to its beginning. The first age of the cycle rises in height, the 'informative' dimension of reality, as it acquires form and reaches an advantageous point of view; which is the zenith of the worldcycle in the middle of life. Then time returns to its origin and falls down in a steep curve. This is the simplest time cycle. Clocks of time are infinite, because those time cycles enclose a vital space and break reality into an inner and outer structure. Mechanism though only inputs a digital series of numbers in a lineal fashion – the more so in the modern age when cyclical clocks have disappeared. This is input in a lineal Cartesian graph, an apt artifact to plot the 'mathematical language' of machines and so time becomes 'lineal' and as it moves to infinity, a single one. The use of digital clocks thus destroyed an enormous numbers of properties of time. Another example. The commonest metal, iron, is lineal in its macro-structure. It was used to make swords that cut flesh and kill by entropy. Entropy today is considered the only arrow of future, and dimensions are established as fixed lineal forms of space. We shall soon see dimensions have attached a motion in time, height goes as we have seen with information, which is what you are seeing in a bidimensional plane of space-time, this screen. Again this 'vital element' that puts together each dimension of space with a motion of time was lost with mechanism. The biggest errors though were done when the complex self-regulating nature of organisms was substituted by the simplistic man-made concept of an exact machine, because the organism is a network, scalar system, and a mechanism exists in a single plane of size and lack networks. So the organic, network, scalar 5D nature of reality was lost. Then it came the 'denaturalization of man'. *Since if the Universe is a machine, it follows then that man is also a machine.* And because the machine is the supreme model, man must 'tailor' its nature, that of its social systems and the Universe at large as a machine. The opposite is truth: Mechanism is

wrong since the Universe is organic; *since a machine is just a simplex organism; while the Aristotelian logic of time and Euclidean space geometry, mechanism uses is a simple version of the more complex languages of 'pentalogic' time and Non-Euclidean, vital, fractal spaces of the*

Organic Universe.

It is for that reason all our papers require lengthy introduction to unveil not only its errors but the enormous number of properties of reality, mechanist physics does not recognize in 'existence', under a pseudo-religious dogma but that only hides its utter ignorance, due to the 'blindness' of the 'mechanical method' confused with truth to those properties of 'scale', which are 'organic', 'synthetic', better expressed with illogic words, and the 5 Dimensions of timespace which are vital, even sentient properties, the first ones we must correct for the immortal, ∞ Universe to make any sense .

Recap: Mechanism not only is theoretically false, it is killing & degrading the human species. Only Organicism is truth and offer to mankind by imitating its physiological laws to construct a perfect organism of history a future to the species.

The error of Newton. A universe of spacetime organisms.

If we want to be specific about the wrong choices of scientific paradigm, all comes in the foundation of science to the choice of Galileo's military machines, clocks and spy-glasses over Leonardo's analysis of reality as an organism, connected by its physiological networks, he struggle to describe not only on the human organism, but in Gaia, the Earth of life and society, in the cities and its networks. Then it came the wrong choice of Newton over Leibniz, regarding the nature of space and time.

This said the translation of 'Newtonian Physics' to 5D is immediate as we just need to consider the ΔST elements of 5D in physics, Δ is the active magnitude that determines the scale, Space = form is the position, and t =motion, the speed of the system. Then motions in 5D up are upwards in scale is the integral of ST (p -momentum), called ' Δ -Work' related to Energy, the overall Δ -content of the system, and motions downwards, the 'derivative' of ΔT (p -momentum) called 'Force'.

So the fundamental concepts of physics *have an easy translation even within the convention of absolute single human Spacetime*. But 5D goes beyond this 1st insight as reality is made of ∞ time clocks and scales of space, connected by the scalar growth and diminution of its key parameter, 'present, $O+|$ momenta: \int work & ∂ forces.

Newton and Galileo had the advantage of simplicity in its statements and the easiness it could be mathematized, as opposed to the 'quality' of physiological networks that required a deeper causal, logic, conceptual understanding of the symbiosis and parallelisms of its forms, which only a genius of visual thought as Leonardo and a genius of logic as Leibniz were able to perceive, but didn't properly explain. We will be far more precise given the centuries of knowledge between those pioneers whose path was forgotten, and our work. But the Universe we will describe will be so 'strange' to the simpleton view of Galileo and Newton that most will not access it. This, one imagines, was also the case of Leibniz and Leonardo since they gave up trying to publish and disseminate their work in the mainstream media of their age (printers), as I have done, no doubt frustrated by the incapacity of most huminds to be humble and entangle with Nature in awe of its perfect design.

In the Dawn of History mankind recognized that vital organic Nature of the Universe in the work of Taoist, Buddhist and Hindi masters in the East; who described existence as a game of Visnu, yin-formation, mental space with still form, and Shiva, yang-entropy, disordered time motions that combined to form the wave of infinite organisms.

But it would be Greek, Latin culture in the west, which gave scientific detail to this wider picture. A man called Plato said the Universe is an organism with a mind called Logos, and his disciple Aristotle who founded science called its entire work the Organon; but it would be in the closeby Italian peninsula where the genius of Leonardo, who should have been the founding father of our civilization, if the species was something more than an homunculus enzyman of weapons, machines and other simple gadgets, and truly aspired to understand the Universe, realized that man was the most perfect organism, we knew and established it as the fundamental species of the Universe, and the measure of all things.

In his anatomical studies was made of tiny parts, similar to small homes, joined by 3 networks, the informative, nervous system with center in the brain, the reproductive, blood system with center in the heart, and the immunological, digestive system with center in the stomach. His detailed drawings with the first complex lenses, allowed him to define the fundamental system of the Universe, the network organism and applied the same concept to the design of cities, organisms

of human beings, ruled by its political legal assemblies, whose productive factories connected its peoples through its streets, and its cloacas and defensive walls completed the same organic structure.

Any clone species of atoms, cells or human beings are joined by 3 physiological networks that deliver them an informative force to shape its form, gravitation in atoms and galaxies, nervous, simultaneous messages in animals and just laws in human societies; a reproductive system which delivers doses of Energy to all its clone parts so they can work, reproducing the goods they need to survive; electromagnetic Energy in atomic systems; free oxygen to all cells and free money in the form of a Universal salary to all citizens in our societies; and a defensive, immunological system that protects the organism from external aggressions; the magnetic field of physical systems, the skin and leukocytes of biologic systems and the health-care warriors and police in charge of destroying lethal technologies that can harm mankind in our society.

So a proper design of the 3 physiological networks of mankind, the legal, financial, economic and immunological system by imitation of our blood, nervous and endocrine system is all what biohistorians, the doctors of mankind, needed to create a perfect world: just laws, free money for the people and the repression of germs and lethal machines, would create an immortal planet. As beautiful, as simple as existence is - easy to all who believe in love and share its \emptyset =Momentum with those that are its equals. But that 'ideal culture' of mankind was not to be, because humans chose Galileo, the military master of the Venice Arsenal over Leonardo, the gay, happy humanist, rational, loving and living till he realized the kind of species he has born to, as the inquisition chased him, and he had to make his analysis of physiology in the darkness of night. Galileo meanwhile racked 1000 golden ducats from the arsenal as advisor of military instruments. And his book on 'ballistics' latter renamed physics became a 'must read' for artillery masters and 'philosophers of time'.

Next in the series of simpleton military lineal men, vs. profound insiders of the absolute came Newton vs. Leibniz.

Let us retrace to Leibniz and Newton, when the second split on our understanding of reality after people sided with Galileo and ignored Leonardo, took place. If Galileo abandoned medicine which Leonardo pursued, and hence never discovered the physiology of the Universe that Leonardo always felt intuitively, Newton would simply 'invent' an absurdity absolute space-time, and denied what Leibniz and any rational thinker always knew - that we were the vital space we occupy and our existence was made of time cycles of which the life and death cycle of time was the fundamental 'event' of the Universe.

If we were to highlight an error of Physics that truly deformed human view of reality, caused by the use of mechanical clocks it was the dismissal of the millenarian concept of a Universe made of ∞ vital space beings who traced its lifetime cycles by Newton, who defined a Universe with an absolute, single time motion, measured by his digital clock and a single absolute space continuum represented by the Cartesian graph. He opposed Leibniz, who as all philosophers before him, considered reality made of vital spaces broken into beings, which lasted a time cycle of life and extinction regulated by its own clocks. How to classify all those clocks of the Universe remained a mystery till I discovered the metric equation of 5D: S (size in space) \times T_f (frequency of time cycles) = Constant. So we are all 'spacetime organisms', systems of vital spaces extending in different scales of size, ran with different cycles of time that store the information in the frequency and form of those cycles, synchronized in symbiotic structures due to the co-invariance of its size and time cycles. This is REALITY as it happens and we shall describe in those texts. Look around you. All what you see are forms=spaces with time=motion. The laws of space=form (s) and time=motion (t) and how both interact with each other are *the knots and bolts of reality*, *mankind* completely ignores for 300 years and counting due to the blunder of Newton. It is an amazing error, given the obvious fact that we observe infinite different rhythms in the Universe and we see infinite vital spaces and all philosophers before Newton have thought the world to be made of vital spaces living time cycles, which can only be ascribed to a peculiar quality of humans – its capacity to make mechanisms of metal called machines which we worship and influence enormously our perception of reality. So as the mechanical clock measured time with the same 'second-minute-hour' rhythm all other time clocks of the Universe were equalized to it and finally the mechanical clock became the only 'time cycle' of reality. And since clocks measured time with numbers, the use of Cartesian graphs to plot those numbers, started with Galileo's equation of lineal speed, $v=S/t$ made scientists to confuse vital real spaces with the abstraction of the continuous paper graph, in which they plotted their mechanical clock measures. It might seem silly but it is an obvious truth that because humans used mechanical clocks they reduced time cycles to the clock and because they used mathematical graphs they confused the real space with the Cartesian graph. *Man* lost at that moment his understanding of reality and when 300 years

latter, Einstein noticed that 'I am the only physicist that thinks there are infinite clocks of time in the Universe that run at different speeds' and defined spacetime as relative, his work was hardly understood, just used to improve those measures. *He insisted, "Leibniz was right, but if so we have to start physics from scratch". And yet, nobody really tried.* This is what we will do, returning to the first principles and starting science from a sounder beginning.

Another element, which Einstein noticed in the structure of space is of importance to understand those first principles. He realized that the Unit of this relative space is a non-Euclidean point crossed by multiple parallels. But again, mankind was 'hanging' on an oversimplification of mathematics that defined since Euclid 'points without breath' in contradiction with the non-Euclidean capacity of the points of his model of General Relativity to include multiple parallels (which are straight lines). And this obliged to start also 'geometry' from scratch. That is, to change NOT only as Lobachevsky among others have done, the definition of parallels that 'penetrate' points, but *give points breath so they can fit those multiple parallels. How to do that is then the key to adapt mathematics to the vital fractal space of multiple scales that we see in 'real Nature': make those points relative to our perception of them, which grows in detail when we come closer to its 'scale of size' with the help of telescopes and microscopes. So then a point-star or a point-atom can fit multiple parallels. Thus we define a new unit of Geometry, a 'fractal non-Euclidean point' which changes in size as we come closer to them. Exactly as Leibniz, whose figure grows in size as the true 'forgotten giant' of XVIII c. science, figured them; when he affirmed that points were fractal, sentient points that hold a world in themselves (Leibniz), to fit multiple parallels and so space was made of 5D scales of relative size with different time cycles.*

Thus Time, Space, its units, clocks and points and its Scales defined by the metrics of what we shall call, respecting the principle of correspondence, 'the fifth dimension', Δ , (for the time being as it is an imprecise term) are ill defined in physics. *And this means as we shall see with so many sciences, that many errors and unneeded complicated 'exants and epicycles' are drawn to achieve a truth, that is far simpler when we define them properly, in the same way that Ptolemaic Astrophysics were simplified when Copernicus put the Sun in its proper place.*

The comparison is fitting, because the reader will think rightly that Physics does describe the Universe with a high degree of truth. But that was also the case of Ptolemy. As truths are relative to the perspective we make, since all 'spaces' are mental spaces, created from a relative point of measure, it is possible to construct a relatively accurate picture of the Universe with a single absolute clock, equalizing all other clocks, and with a single space continuum, 'filling' the gaps of 'smaller scales' with infinitesimal points as Euclidean mathematicians do. But it is far more beautiful simple and realist to put the sun in the center and simplify orbits into ellipses, and it will be far simpler and more beautiful and reveal deeper truths about 'existence' – a function of our vital space and time 'worldcycles' of life and death – when we explain reality as it is, made of infinite relational vital spaces and local time clocks.

The most controversial of all the elements of reality, which again humans NOT only physicists systematically deny, out of 'egocoy' (ego=idiocy) is the fact that all spaces are mental spaces, 'mappings' made from a point of view of measure, which both Leibniz and Einstein recognized, but again nobody else understood (till Gauss and Riemann; but it seems their work would again be trivialized). The question here is obvious: why we see Earth still when it is moving? Because our mind creates a still mental space; and this happens for every entity that 'gauges information' from his point of view.

So as we create a mental space made with digital languages of measure obtained with machines humans transform their minds that become machine-like and abandon the organic view of reality that preceded it where man was the measure of all things and the universe was considered an organism. To understand this change of paradigm on what is reality and science (its objective knowledge) we need to define the equation of any mind-mirror made of measures with a language:

$O\epsilon$ (finitesimal mind, $-E$ point with volume) $\times \infty$ Universe Time cycles = Linguistic mental Mapping World of space-time.

Each species uses different forces to perceive reality and makes with its pixels different mind-mappings. An elephant uses smells and builds with atoms its memorial time view of reality. A dolphin or a bat uses sounds to build a mind-mapping of space in the water. Man used to perceive space with eyes and time with causal past, present and future verbs, focused in the causal logic of time. Today this is substituted by visual machines' images and the faulty causality of numbers that truly

tell us very little about why we go from A to B, which was the great strength of verbal thought. To overcome those limits we use mathematical equations, but as we do not think with equations its interpretation is faulty. They just seem magic to us and so scientists have built a creationist mystic around equations as religions did about words. So if Gods created reality naming things with words, in Arab or Hebrew, now God is supposed to write an equation and creates reality. So often scientists write an equation and expect a particle or an even pop out of reality. Since they don't understand the causal complex back and forth reality between 'Ss-languages' (still forms of space) and 'Tt-entropy' (pure motion in time). But the 'egocy' paradox (ego=idiocy) embedded in the mind equation always comes to their rescue: 'A mind measures reality from its self-centered point of view with a few languages of information; blind to many of its properties and all other points of view, so she confuses the whole Universe with their selfish world with its ego at its center.' As long as scientists are NOT aware thanks to reductionism of those other monads-worlds and scales and languages and points of view an illusion of knowledge can be created and it has the advantage that it is simple: you measure with a machine, put the outcome in equations and those patterns become truth as the ego paradox makes you confuse it with reality. And if something goes wrong then you affirm a simplified 'postulate without proof' to eliminate all bothering information (Euclidean points in maths; limit of c-speed in physics; political and economical correctness in social sciences; etc.)

How many 'particle-points' measure reality creating still mental spaces? The reader will be surprised by our affirmation that 'all particles' gauge information, or else quantum physics wouldn't be a gauge theory, and so the 'unit of life and perception' in the Universe is the particle, since both the quark and the electron gauge information, feed on Energy, reproduce into new particles and evolve socially with other particles, which are the 'drives of life' that define a living system.

This amazing realization - that it is only 'egocy: ego=idiocy' what makes humans to think there is something 'special' about the carbon atom (we shall see in fact that the key atom of our life organisms is the 'nitrogen head' with its perfect clocks, not the carbon bodies)... opens even a wider view on the panpsychic, sentient properties of the Universe, which both Einstein and Leibniz intuitively understood.

But since Galileo and Newton had defined time in lineal terms, and reduced the role of 'form', information, in reality, all properties related to information dissappeared from physics, to the point that when Shannon crfted a theory of information it was just about the lineal transmission of a message, without any interest for its formal content. Reductionism of the different motions of time, scales of space, expanded to that lack of understanding of the organic, vital properties of physical systems, reduced to a single language of description, mathematics, whose analytic nature could not reveal those synthetic, organic structures. Physicists with those reductions of reality finally had only a single time arrow, entropy to model the Infinite Universe, and so they developed a wrong big-bang concept of it. What scientists do instead of explaining such reality made of vital spaces=forms with different time motions? As a mind is a linguistic mirror NOT reality itself, organisms create mental spaces to interpret the larger Universe selecting only useful information for its survival, creating a 'World'. So we don't see smaller and larger scales without the help of sensorial machines and we miss a lot of information about the time cycles of reality. But we don't really need it to survive on the world. And for that reason a partial mind-view of reality might work. What happened then since Newton is that humans substituted their sensorial mind-mapping of the world with visual images of space and 'causal' past to future logic analysis on how time changed reality by a mechanical measure of space plotted into a geometric mind-mapping and a digital measure of time as a sequence of lineal numbers; and this 'mental view' interpreted with machines became 'reality' till today. In essence as clocks evolved into digital computers (a complex array of 'clock-like' logic loops) and telescopes and microscopes into cameras, this reality became the 'seed' of a new type of mind, the mind of machines. But humans do not understand what science since Galileo is doing is basically creating a me(n)tal world. They think they are accessing reality. To get to that absurd view of what digital science does, it was needed a philosophy called at times reductionism, naïve realism or positivism, which states that 'what we cannot measure (with machines) does not exist' (Planck); so all the properties of time, different kinds of motions=changes and causal relationships between past, present and future that cannot be translated into mechanical clocks' measures do not exist. All vital properties of space and organic relationships between its scales does not exist. The 5th dimension does not exist. Causality is ever more weakened with the use of statistical methods. In this view of what our civilization does the intelligence of humans became greatly reduced but as machines evolved it seemed we achieved higher degrees of knowledge since machines soon

overcame humans in its sensorial skills to measure and portrait reality.

This is a simple and effective way to manipulate reality from the perspective of the mind that measures as long as we are controlling 'lesser' species with less form, in-form-ation and impose our view. But it gives 0 answers to deep questions about what we are, why we exist, what is the purpose and reasons of the life and death cycle, what is mankind, what is our relationships with machines, what is our future... all the kind of questions we answer in those papers. But again to the rescue comes reductionism. It is call the 'entropic view' of the Universe. Of the different type of motions=changes=times there are, entropy, Tt is an internal and external motion that disorders=kills a system – the definition of death. It is thus simple to describe and it has become for that reason the preferred 'arrow' of time of philosophy of mechanist science, since indeed at the end all dies, so entropy is the future. All the processes of slow creation of information, more difficult to understand are shunned off. And so we believe entropy is the only arrow of time that those 'digital clocks measure', and build models of sciences based in entropy *by eliminating the arrow of information that balanced entropy: Ss<->Tt*.

Our model of the Universe is an entropic model that measures only the expansion of vacuum space between galaxies (Tt) but ignores its contraction due to the force of gravitation in galaxies (Ss), which makes galaxies similar to atoms in the lower 5D scale of electromagnetic space where the strong 'gravitational-like' force balances the 'electromagnetic' 'dark-Energy like' force; so you are not contracting into the past or expanding into the future. Reductionism also works in biology where the theory of evolution stresses the final death by entropic predators but has shunned off for very long the evolution of information and speed of reproduction that defines the most successful eusocial species (ants and humans).

Entropy is also the practical theory of human societies, meaning through History war, using entropic weapons, constructed by physicists not diplomatic collaboration and social evolution have defined the fate of mankind. Because of all those shortcomings of human intelligence and ethics (respect of other living parts of reality), and the fact that we confuse our self with the whole Universe humans have kept destroying the world of the tree of life and building the tree of metal, with weapons, go(l)d and machines (entropic, reproductive and informative metal) as attachments of themselves, becoming a symbiotic species we shall call animetal, whose worldview must be interpreted in historic terms more than scientific ones; once we realize beyond the 1st step of the scientific method, A)ccurate gathering of data, greatly enhanced by the use of mechanisms, mankind has gone nowhere on B)creation of true organic models of reality proved by its C)yclic patterns =Laws of science; used to manipulate Nature in favor of D)emocratic solutions for 'all Humanity' to improve life, preventing E)xtinctive, entropic solutions that kill Nature & mankind (war machines; money for the 1%, 6th extinction of Gaia...)

The Universe is a nested 'superorganism' of space=form/information and time=motion. All what you see around are forms with motion. Physics rightly understood we cannot distinguish both (Principle of relativity) but *didn't pursuit its obvious implication: All is a composite of form=space and motion=time, so we are made as Leibniz wanted of clocks of time and vital spaces*. Instead it took Newton's view that 'God' had put us all in his 'plenum=body', made with a Cartesian mathematical artifact, hence with a single 'lineal time clock' and a single 'space-continuum'. Because the errors of mechanism, since Newton, regarding the nature of time and space, the substances of which we are all made, have so much influenced all sciences and the view mankind has of the Universe, before the analysis of each specific science in each paper-book of this 'encyclopedia of 5D 'stiences', we need to offer a condensed summary of the Laws of space dimensions and time motions.

This is then a new beginning for physics and it faces obviously what Kuhn's call the 'change of paradigm', what Copernicus suffered, and so did Planck, who, sanguine said, all 'scholars have to die for new students to learn the paradigm'. I won't see it, because I expand further than mathematical physics to ethical and vital properties which as the reader keeps reading if anyone does will soon become interlocked. Since the 5th dimension is organic, and it adds vital properties to physics, it makes particles living things, who gauge information, feed on entropy, reproduce with energy, evolve socially into new scales and so the proper way to describe mathematical physics is with a vital jargon. Consider the weak force in which a particle is born by emerging into a larger massive scale and then go down to its 'natural form', departing from the 'h/2' quantum oscillator, it can be written with equations or explained as the emergence of a new vital organism, in away everybody understands.

LEIBNIZ V. NEWTON: PENTALOGIC SPACE-TIME. DIMOTIONS

"According to their [Newton and his followers] doctrine, God Almighty wants to wind up his watch from time to time: otherwise it would cease to move. He had not, it seems, sufficient foresight to make it a perpetual motion. Nay, the machine of God's making, so imperfect, according to these gentlemen; that he is obliged to clean it now and then by an extraordinary concourse, and even to mend it, as clockmaker mends his work.'

Leibniz-Clarke Correspondence on the absurdity of mechanical models of the Universe

The consequence of the existence of an internal fifth dimension of space-time, made of all other planes=scales of spacetime of a being, its parts and wholes, which store the information of a system, is the fact that we ARE made of planes=scales of space and time. We ARE the vital space we occupy and we ARE the time flow of existence we live between birth and extinction. Reason why all systems and entities of Nature obey the main science of space, geometry->Mathematics and time, Logic. We are broken fractal species of space and time, whose mathematical and logic laws all vital space-time organisms follow as Einstein and Leibniz thought: So we must evolve our logic and geometry of space and time, to extract properties of 'existential beings' from them.

The underlying question of time§space: Absolute or Relational, Generational Space-Time?

The key question physicists wondered for centuries regarding the nature of space and time unfortunately was resolved as usual in favor of the simpler view: it is space and time an absolute abstract background of the Universe (Mr. Newton's view) or are we made of 'vital space' that lasts a time duration, so we are generated by the bio-topo-logic properties of scalar space and cyclical time? This is the choice of 5D 'stiences'. And its simpler version was called relational spacetime, sponsored by Mr. Leibniz.

A realist interpretation of the world we live in, which never shows in any scale of reality such background - a mathematical graph used in abstract by human scientists - considers that we ARE the vital space we occupy with our cells, and we LIVE a cyclic time duration between birth and extinction. So *we are* space and time.

The argument reached its height in n the correspondence between **Newton**, the proposer of the absolute Cartesian graph of space-time drawn by God (his body in his own words) vs. **Leibniz** who rightly considered absolute space and time an abstraction, and coined the concept of relational space -merely the adjacent pegging of similar forms in simultaneous space and relational time - the sequence of events which we relate causally with reason. In Newton's cosmos, space and time provide a fixed, immutable, eternal background, through which particles move. Space and time are the stage of intersecting lines sketched in the illustration. Fact is this 'mathematical artifact' made with pen and paper by earlier physicists, called the Cartesian graph, useful to measure 'translation in space' is no where to be seen in reality. Unfortunately as time went by the graph became somehow 'real' as scientists' felt the 'mathematical language' created reality. But if space is what objects occupy that distance between the red square's vital spade and the yellow 'circle' must have something. Horror vacuum comes then into place: indeed the Universe must be scalar. There must be very small parts between them, which we do not see. And that is what we proved with microscopes - *as we probe smaller distances forms with motion, spaces with time-motions appear and there it seems no limit to the fractal scales of the Universe.*

It meant the invention of an absolute continuous space & single lineal time that extends to ∞ contradicting the fact that all spaces are broken, divided by membranes, and all beings have finite time duration. Further on, as we kept exploring smaller scales of reality, we never found the drawings of God, not even a solid still substance, but always 'motions' tracing closed time-space cycles; since even particles turned to be also 'vortices of time-space motions'.

So Leibniz's sound theory considered absolute space and time an abstraction, and so he coined the concept of relational space - merely the adjacent pegging of similar forms in simultaneous space and relational time - the sequence of events which we relate causally with reason origin of the 'Generational space-time' model of 5D in which are the space we occupy and the time we last - as in the graph where there is no longer abstract background lines. *Unfortunately Physicists sided with Newton not with Leibniz on the question of what is space and time - an abstract background put by God or*

"Behind it all is surely an idea so simple, so beautiful, that when we grasp it - in a decade, a century, or a millennium - we will all say to each other, how could it have been otherwise..."
- John A. Wheeler

the substance of which we are all made; and so the conceptual jump would not happen.

It is the fifth space-time dimension, sum of all other planes of reality, including within it all other dimensions.

Next, to explain all this properly came Einstein. One of the fundamental discoveries of Einstein is that in our universe, there is indeed no fixed space-time background. In Einstein's theory of general relativity, which replaces Newton's theory of mechanics and the gravitational force, the geometry of spacetime is not fixed. Instead it is an evolving, dynamical quantity – a topology; and it is the substance of which reality is. So we are topological beings, geometries of space with motions of time.

Absolute space-time IS NOT. Absolute Space is the sum of all the discontinuous vital spaces, occupied by different beings: $\Sigma s=S$. And lineal time, T the sum of all the finite life-death cycles of all beings $T=\Sigma t$.

Since space and time do exist and so if they are not in the background we 'are' vital space and cyclic time.

The simple idea behind the structure of the fractal Universe is then to consider time=change=motion and Topologic, formal space=extension the 2 elements of which all beings are made.

Wheeler said 'Spacetime tells matter how to move & matter tells spacetime how to curve'. Since *Spacetime is geometry in motion*. Time is change, the perception of change moves time; time is motion; space is its opposite, stillness, form, the information of time. And so it is all about two parameters: Time=Motion and Space=Form.

Worldcycles of time. Causal repetitive laws of 'stiences'

'We said the choice of wording for 'space=form' and 'motion=time' was difficult because ultimately all is time, and space=form a maya of the senses that saw cyclical time, closed loops as forms, from particle vortices to spinning wheels. So we could say that 'space is a form of time'. But also because on the long term 'time motions become cyclical', 'time is a form of space'.

The key concept the reader must accept, which is difficult given the paradoxical structure of the Universe, vs. the monologic 'attitude' of the mind is the denial of the classic logic A or $\neg A$. But rather $A \Leftrightarrow \neg A = B$. That is, time becomes space becomes time. Lines become pi cycles that become lines. Motion curves to become form 'Time curves space into mass' (a vortex of space-time) said Einstein. Then by convention we shall choose to call the $T>S$ cyclical, informative vortex a form of space and a $S<T$, expanding lineal process Time. The reason is because the concept of 'metal space and formal language' has become better established since Riemann in mathematics and physics with the use of 'phase spaces'. While the 'feeling'=e-motion of time, the association of time with change and motion is the easiest property to identify. But then time curves, 'forms' a cycle, 'repeats', reproduces and as Kepler put it all 'lines become part of a larger cyclical orbit. You cannot access the illogic structure of the universe if your mind cannot grasp those contradictions. A huge problem of '4D science' is to fail to grasp those dynamic contradictions, since it hauls from an Aristotelian $A \rightarrow B$ dogmatic logic of truth today made even more inflexible as it is the basis of the 'mind' of computers, which fails to see the flexible $A \Leftrightarrow B$, dual and then 'trinity' logic of the Universe, which is everywhere, from the 'trinity principles' of Δ -scale Energy, S-Formal space-angular momentum, T-lineal time-momentum, the Universe conserves, to the gender 'convergence' $S t \leftarrow T_s$ of reality. So we shall constantly return to those contradictory statements. Another way to have solved those problems is just to eliminate the wording 'space' and 'time' from our discourse and talk of 'motion' and 'form' and its 3 tpologiex, $|+O+\emptyset$, but this will leave void of meaning much of the phsyscal analysis of equations and laws that apply to all sciences and deal conceptually with space and time both in wording and equation. The key law then that we will constantly find in the Universe is precisely the 'entanglement' and correspondence between $S=T=\Delta$, which reinforce each other. The Universe is a constant 'menage a trois'.

A Universe of ∞ time clocks of different size and speed differs from its human description with a single mechanical clock-time to which all time clocks of the universe are equalized, elongated into a lineal 'second-minute-hour-day-year' system of equalized time clocks (of light waves, mechanical clocks, earth's astronomical clocks). As Galilean physics, born of ballistics, simplified

A year:
Cycle of existence of the Earth respect to the sun

the nature of cycles of time-space into lineal durations, to measure best the locomotions of cannonballs:

Time is cyclical, all clocks of time and laws of science are based in the cyclical patterns of nature. But physicists developed ballistics before understanding cyclical time so they postulated lineal inertia, and a single entropic dimotion of time, and when this was applied to other sciences, many lost their capacity to understand the future which will repeat the causality of the past.

A question pending then from the principle of lineal inertia is then 'centripetal acceleration', $a=V/r^2$. It is real? Or we should consider that in an entangled Universe there is always a 'communication of forces' between attractiver an repelling 'poles' ?

Lineal & cyclic time render the same functions as one is the inverse of the other, measured by frequency, $T=1/f$, but the philosophical implications of cyclic time are enormous, as we regain the in-form-ation provided by those cycles, *origin of the laws of science, which would not exist if there were not cyclical patterns*. So we consider an Δ -i 'quanta of time frequency or 'finitesimal derivative' of the larger whole represented with the concept of lineal time; as in the classic formula, $V(st)=f(t) \lambda(s)$. We can measure Space e, $Vt=S$ with lineal time as a single unit, or as a sum of frequency steps, with more detail.

A time cycle breaks reality (1st knot theorem) in an outer and inner region, creating a membrane that encloses a vital space, the 'substance of which we are all made'. A worldcycle of time has also 3 'relative pi-diameters' or '3 ages of time'.

Galilean Paradox: Locomotion as Reproduction of Form: $S \leftrightarrow T$: Space Dimensional Form=Time Motion

Because physicists reduce the 5 Dimotions of the Universe to only one, Tt-entropy; we shall unlike all other disciplines, start with the analysis of entropy in physical systems, and debunk its main theories of entropy – the big-bang Universe and entropy as the only state of matter that matters, and then proceed by order of importance in human physics, with the analysis of the Ts-dimotion of locomotion, and its relativity Theory.

The conclusion is then rather obvious: one of the two parameters of reality is 'hidden' to perception; we either see motion or form, 'waves or particles' (quantum complementarity), distances and lines or points in motion (as in the night when fast cars in a picture appear as lines). So *physicists calculate only one when in fact we must assess the existence of 2; and since we cannot distinguish them, logically we must equal them. 'Form=motion-function; space=time; $S_i=T_e$ '*. And since there is nothing else than time and space, those 2 experimental primary 'mirror-sciences' of time and space become the most important to extract the 'Disomorphic=laws' of those 5 Dimotions that all systems have in common. Since *while those Dimotions are broken, in vital organisms, separated by cyclical time membranes, they are the same*.

Relativity becomes a duality, $S_i=T_e$, which is *at the heart of every law of the Universe. Whereas the primary element, the ultimate substance is time=motion. As space is a Maya of the senses – a slice of time motion. Form is what a 'still mind', makes of that motion to 'perceive', information, forms-in-action*. Since we see Earth still and flat but it is round and moving. Galileo's profession was ballistics - the study of cannonballs motion. So he chose ONLY motion and lost the chance to start physics with a complex philosophical understanding of its $S_i=T_e$ dual Principle of relativity, which Poincare defined latter clearly when he said that 'we cannot distinguish motion from stillness'. An example is quantum/relativity duality. In detail quantum space has 'dark Momentum' because it has expansive motion that extends into a plane of space, but when seen at larger scales without detail its entropic motion seems static space - a dual area of scattering length and width. So in the galaxy we see either dark Momentum motion or expanding space: $T=S$. A motion of time is equivalent to a dimension of space: Distance and motion cannot be distinguished so they must be taken as two side of the same being, a space=time Dimotion (ab. Dimensional Motion):

$$S = T; \text{ Dimension-Distance} = \text{Time-motion} = S \approx T \text{ Dimotion}$$

Earth moves in time, but we see it as a still form in space because reality is a constant game of ∞ motions, but the mind focus those motions and measures them at still distances. For huminds, motion is relative to our systems of measure and perception, which are light-based; hence a fixed c-rod speed/ distance. Reason why Einstein's relativity postulates a maximal T:c-speed, measured as if observer and observable were still to each other (Constant S); which at our scale we correct with Lorentz Transformations.

But physicists just substituted Earth's still distances for motions and it took 300 years for Einstein to realize relativity of motion and its measure made time and space, motion and form two sides of the same coin. Still this realization was not explored philosophically and so it gave birth to a series of ill-understood dualities between 'states of measure and form' (particles, head gauging form, in-form-ation) and 'states of motion' (wave states).

Galilean Relativity: the error of Cartesian, continuum space. The restricted formula of time-change as motion of space.

Physicists' image of reality is restricted by the concept of lineal time and a single dimotion, locomotion that limits the solution of physical questions and introduces errors as the cosmological big-bang or the evaporation of black holes, mentioned before. To this we add the concept that only mathematical properties matter. It comes all from Galileo. Physicists spatialized time, defined with a single dimension, as a parameter of changes in motions and space, $t=s/v$.

This limited study of only one type of change is forgotten, creating conceptual errors, such as the fantasy of time travel (as physicists don't realize there are infinite clocks of time in the Universe and so all time travel is local, within a certain organism as in the processes of death.)

When physicists confront the phenomenon of time, they do so only from the perspective of spatial change, a very limited part of the entire realm of time=changes. And so both, Galilean relativity and Einsteinian relativity are theories about the motion and Entropy of space, not a theory about all types of Time-change as this work is. And when someone like Hawking affirms that time travel is possible because time-motion gets to zero in a black hole, he merely forgets he is speaking about the time-motion defined in the previous formula, $t=s/v$ or its self-similar Einsteinian version not about the sum of the infinite time cycles of the Universe that remain unchanged. So $T=0$ means only a system 'STOPS'.

Those are limits to time studies *in any physical theory, from Galilean to Einsteinian Relativity.*

Today, when Physicists talk about time they talk about is a parameter, t , which appeared first in an equation of speed, $V=s/t$, that Galileo found when studying translational change in space or 'spatial movement'. Furthermore, because that rate of change in space is considered infinitesimal, $V=ds/dt$, they talk about present changes in space, which Einstein defined with his concepts of 'present simultaneity'.

The 5D Universe is a nested organism ruled by 2 5D metric equations: $S_i \times T_f = C$ that harmonizes its scales as smaller scales in space run faster time speeds. And $S=T$, the principle of absolute relativity, as we cannot distinguish motion=time from form=space. So the minimal unit of reality is both, a 'Dimensional motion' or Dimotion of space-time.; $S-T$

Those 2 equations with profound implications in all stiences substitute Einstein's similar postulates of Relativity and

So we shall deduce most equations and laws of science from them. Both equations are in fact related as Max. $S \times T$ happens when $S=T$, defining a function of vital existence all systems try to achieve, reproducing and absorbing 'T-motion', 'S-information' and $S \times T$ -reproductive energy for its 3 topological limbs/fields body-waves and particle-heads. Thus 5D metric also can be interpreted as a biological, organic model of physical systems. This lead us to 3 'sides' of 5D physics, mathematical metric, organic properties of matter and ethic survival questions of dealing with their 'GNA risks'.

It follows then a model of cosmology in which charges and masses are 'vortices' of space-time of two scales, the scale of atoms and galaxies, which resolves most of the questions of present cosmology and substitutes the big-bang model.

The symmetry is extraordinary as it is carried out to the components of the 'proton-nucleus' and 'electron-halo' of the galaxy, made of the heavier quarks, BCB, black atoms, and positive Top quark condensates in the center of black holes, *black frozen stars, with a cut-off substance as Einstein demanded to believe on it. While the halo* is made of negative strangelets (Witten's hypothesis) acting in organic terms as the protein of the Galacell, whose 'DNA' are those black stars, but also shaping the 'repulsive lineal' force between the center and the halo. Since, if galaxies are similar to atoms, it follows immediately that as charge forces are lineal as a function of radius, dark matter is also lineal as a function of the galaxy radius; that as Υ -rays are repulsive expanding space between atoms, but imploding it within atoms,

$G\Upsilon$ ant forces between galaxies expand space but gravitation contract it in galaxies, balancing both into an immortal Hyper-Universe. What are the 'particles' of those $G\Upsilon$ ant waves is obvious, and resolves also the problem of dark energy, which *has*

a 120 power deficit; because physicists wrongly use the plack mass to calculate it, when they should use the neutrino mass that perfectly fit on the observed vacuum energy. So c-speed, in a scalar Universe is just the maximal motion of the Light space-time background of galaxies, over an intergalactic neutrino background, which according to 5D metric is $V > c$ as it carries less Sinformation than light; perceived NOT as $v > c$ but as a dark energy 'expansion' of space between galaxies.

A falsification of the big-bang model follows. And all this is coupled with a classic analysis of the 3 elements of physical systems as scalar processes, ' Δ -1forces', which are derivatives of $\Delta\emptyset$ -present momentum which is a derivative of $\Delta+1$ kinetic energy-work. So nature also establishes a dynamic 3-scalar structure in its physical systems and forces; which leads to a Unification of all forces of nature in organic and mathematical terms. All this and much more means *you won't make sense of 5D physics till you get to page 40 and sink the concepts behind a Relational model of space-time, following Leibniz a 400 years of 'absolutism' weighting on you back. A warning: many texts are 30 years old, so a 'pro' can have a laugh. I will slowly correct them. That doesn't invalidate the fact that 5D is the highest upgrade o physics in those 400y.*

Inner and outer motions and forms. Vacuum time: the ultimate substance of reality.

Jordan's knot theorem that breaks reality is the key concept to establish the parameters of the Universe in a more rigorous form. Look around you, all what you see are 'space-forms' with 'time-motion'. We are all space-time, forms in motion, 'in-form-motion', 'information', forms in action; play with the words of what you are.

Tt: internal and external motion or 'entropy' is one extreme, which brings death. That is the state of mankind today, caused by the fact the new species, machines move faster externally (cars, weapons) and internally 'metal-minds', visual images accelerate, disordering humans into a permanent ADD state. So millennials move fast and have disordered minds. At the end of that process entropy kills. *Vacuum Time with no mental spatial form is the ultimate substance of reality to which all returns, from where all departs; but the purpose of all existjences is creating information with it; forms in action, 'cyclical vortices of active form' exactly the reverse of what 4D physicists think the Universe is, stuck on a 'solid' view of particles.*

In the extreme state a being as, an Ss, language of the mind, seed of pure, perfect information, enlightenment that doesn't move. The hypothetical Mind of God is such a being, because it perceives all what has existed, exists and will exist and repeat itself eternally as a block of time - a zero sum of fluctuations of the game of existence in space and time.

It is all about 2 parameters: time=motion and space=form. Look around you, all what you see are 'space-forms' with 'time-motion'. We are all space-time, forms in motion, 'in-form-motion', 'information', forms in action; play with the words of what you are. Because all systems are in an external larger world, we can then consider them either to have 'external or internal motion or form'; and WE CAPITALIZE THE LARGER OUTER WORLD. So we can combine EXTERNAL and internal motion and form with both 5 canonical combinations, which correspond to the 5 fractal S-Dimensional T-motions of Space and Time. As all beings will have a bit of both. So they are always messed up in practical terms is often easier to measure a mixture of both. So we talk of still forms with internal motion, we call '**information**', **sT**; and motions with a EXTERNAL STILL FORM, we call Locomotion, **Ts**, and beings that ex=change between both states, as there is no 'yin (information)' without yang (motion). This intermediate present state is \emptyset -momentum; they key element of physical reality that merges both and in physics is in fact parted into |-momentum and O-momentum, though as Kepler already noticed both are mixed, since a line is often just part of a huge curve. Finally we call the pure absolute inner and outer motion without form, **Tt, entropy**; and the absolute inner and outer form without motion, **Ss, language. Reality** is then more complex but as we increase those combinations of space=form and time=motion and understand that all is about changes between them inside and outside the being; either trying to balance both in present \emptyset -momentums or changing it through 'energy scales'; the extraordinary importance of understanding the first principles of reality will become more obvious.

A GALAXY HAS ITS INFORMATIVE, TALL SPHERIC CENTER IN A GRAVITATIONAL BLACK HOLE AND ITS ELECTROMAGNETIC ENERGY IN ITS STELLAR PLANE, SURROUNDED BY A MEMBRANE OF DARK MATTER.

ANIMALS & PLANTS HAVE INVERSE DIRECTIONS OF ENERGY & INFORMATION, SINCE PLANTS USE LIGHT AS ENERGY AND CHEMICAL PARTICLES AS INFORMATION WITH BRAINS IN THE ROOTS ANIMALS USE LIGHT AS INFORMATION AND EARTH TO MOVE BY ELECTRIC REPULSION AND MECHANIC GRAVITATION

THE 5 DIMENSIONAL MOTIONS OF THE UNIVERSE: 5D SPACE SUPERORGANISMS TRACING TIME WORLDCYCLES.

This said the devil is in the details. So what does it mean to be made of motions with form, time and space? In mathematical terms, it means to be made of topological dimensions, which are holographic bi-dimensional space with motion in time. And as it happens *topology has only 3 varieties of bidimensional spacetime and it is constructed of parts – points – that become wholes – networks. So the immediate translation of generational space-time into modern mathematical systems do convert as we observed in the abstract, all systems into mathematical beings.*

As we are 'vital Space' 5D uses topology to understand the ternary organic, structure' of all systems of nature: As the 5 Dimotions are dimensions of space with time motion, its science is topology that allows a system to deform= change its inner form. Yet a 4D Universe has only 3 'topological varieties' that restricts ensembles to only 3 topologies, each one best suited to perform the 3 organic vital functions of any physic or biologic system –gauging information (1D) to move the system (2D) to an energy field in which reproduce (3D): The purpose of vital topology is to study the 5 Dimotions (dimensional motions) of all local 5D island-Universes... As such it is the final st=age of evolution of geometry as an experimental science, merged with biology.

All dimensions of space have motion in time. Mathematics realized it, as the still Geometry of the Greeks evolved into a vaster, generalized concept, a topological variety, where a topology as opposed to a geometry has internal motions-changes. As the only case in which the inner dimensions of a being don't seem to change is external locomotion most 5D motions need 'geometries' with inner motion, which are topologic varieties of which there are only 3:

In the graph, Einstein's diffeomorphic Principle acquires an organic nature, when we see the Universe as the sum of ∞ Complementary ternary, topologic systems whose dimensions have organic functions: Systems feed on their relative dimension of energy-length, perceive in their relative dimension of height and reproduce in their relative combined dimension of width, which are assembled into each specific species, to best satisfy the systems' in taking of motion, energy and information.

l.e: An animal has its informative height in the high perceptive light dimension, but a plant, which uses light as energy has its up and down dimensions inverted respect to the man and its chemical brain buried on the Earth. So both have opposite energy-time coordinates, with an 'antero-posterior', lineal' 'outward' energy oriented structure due to the oriented arrow of light. But in a 3D world with no preferred orientation, a sea or vacuum, cyclic forms that maximize information dominate from plankton to galaxies that have a cyclic, informative, inward structure, as the stars' body absorbs energy from intergalactic space, reproduces matter with it and feeds the internal informative knot of gravitation, with a higher height dimension the black hole..

The fundamental entity of reality is a space-time super-organism, spread in several 'scales' of the 5th dimension whose metric laws organize reality. The discovery of a new dimension of space-time is the most important r=evolution human sciences experience and if not were because of Newton's error certainly mankind would have understood earlier the organic 5th dimension of 'scalar space-time' since it was discovered precisely by the evolution of 'metal-eyes' (telescopes and microscopes) who probe in those scales; but due to Newton's error was *never properly formalized* till those texts. Why the 5th dimension was shunned off by science for so long thus require an analysis of how little, mechaism with its simplification of reality in abstract, 'lineal terms' understood of the previous dimensions, made with a pinch of salt, regarding the 'supreme intelligence' our species ascribes... to our species, revealing all what humans *do not even see about those dimensions – namely, the fact that all of them have associated to its spatial 'dimensional form', a 'motion in time'; hence they are both dimensions of space=form and time=motions or 'dimotions', due the principle of relativity (we cannot distinguish motion from form, so we see Earth as a still form, when it is a rotary motion) and their entangled relationships; as dimensions must be defined in co-invariant equations with each other. So once we realize how childish are the definitions mechanism does of time=motion, space=dimensional form and scale, we will define 5D metrics.*

QUANTIC MIND-WORLDS: HEIGHT DIMENSION

Besides human eye-worlds the Universe has many I-planes of existence, dimensions & time arrows that quantic mind-species perceive with other languages=forces used to describe those EXT I-worlds:

The 1st dimensional motion of space-time (ab. Dimotion) humans measured was undoubtedly length, calculated through the steps of roughly a meter as a distance of space (dimensional, formal view) or Locomotion, (Time=motion view). But it would be the ONLY dimension of space to which humans ascribed a motion in time, which left limp our understanding of time till this date; when we still have only a dual space time dimotion, 'locomotion' or 'Ts' (where we capitalize the external motion of the system, in this case of an internal form, s, without motion)

The 2nd dimensional motion of height (form) or information (motion) was still shredded in mystery as it would need the discovery in China or Mesopotamia of the Pythagoras Theorem to have a proper metrics related to length. Since a *formalism of Dimensional motions of space-time needs to relate them in a co-invariant form. So the Pythagoras theorem connected X and its Perpendicular Y dimension of height, allowing the expansion of Greek Bidimensional Geometry. But as its motion in time, 'information' was ignored – height became orphan. Consider the screen you are reading, it has a height dimension, as a paper, so the product of X x Y gives you information.* The problem of the motion in time of height is that is a 'slower' time dimotion, connected to growth and evolution. So all species as they evolve they grow in information= height, from mammals that became humans to reptiles that became dinosaurs and birds, to matter that becomes the high tube to infinity of a black hole singularity. So the 'informative' function =motion of height is perceptive projective geometry of a high point, reason why heads, bankers, antennas and pulpits that command biologic, economic & cultural organisms are on top. If we named **Ts-locomotion** (external motion of a still 'point particle'), **Height-information is its inverse, St** (external form with internal motion, form-in-action, in-form-ation, as a TV screen where motion is within its image. Geometry gave height a 'motion of evolution of information', which was out of the comprehension of man's mind that had only the capacity to see time=motion=change in very short spans, related to its visual 'clock' of 1 glimpse a second, 1 thought a second, one step a second, one heart beat a second, which synchronized all the parts of its organisms to its time clock. All other different time clock speeds of nature were lost to him.

The 3rd dimension of width was known but unconnected to length and height – the cube problem unresolved – till modern times. So only 2 dimensions of space were formalized earlier in the History of thought by Greek Geometers and Logicians from Pythagoras to Aristotle, setting the foundations of knowledge for the following two millennia.

Then came Galileo who didn't understand Earth had both a dimension of **mental space=still form** and a motion in time due the logic postulate of relativity ('We cannot distinguish a state of motion from a state of form', Galileo, Einstein, Poincare). So we **see** Earth still but it is moving (e pur si muove, e pur no muove). *It was the first chance for mankind to understand the duality of dimensions of still mental space=form and true time=motion.* Galileo didn't go so far; instead with the 'monologic' of a single Aristotelian cause, A->B, proper of human limited minds he chose that the Earth moved; while the Church chose it didn't move. But none explained both things together. He then associated the dimension of 'time' locomotion, or 'speed' to the dimension of length, **Ts**. And he got its metric when he applied the mechanical clock to measure 'motions in space', defining a $v=s/t$ formula of Galilean Relativity, latter refined with a $-ct$ parameter by Einstein, who, following in the path of Riemann's dissertation of Non-Euclidean metrics, expressed the mental linguistic nature of Spaces as 'simultaneous measure relative to a frame of reference'. *Since stillness is a maya of the senses, as each mind creates a finitesimal still image of the Universe, self-centered in its Non-E 'fractal point of measure' that holds a world in itself (Leibniz's monads) So Ss-mind-languages stop and order Tt-entropic motions.*

Thus Humans are stuck with a single ts-spacetime dimotion, locomotion, corresponding to length; a metric for height as a space dimension without its motion of time, information, Pythagoras Theorem and a 3rd unconnected dimension of width, without its corresponding motion in time, 'reproduction'. It was a limited view of space=form, time=motion and its duality as dimensional motions of space-time. Yet human egocy (ego= idiocy) heralded those children of thought as the highest intelligences of the cosmos. So when Einstein, whose best definition of time was 'what the clock measures', died, 'Time' published a cartoon with a future Earth crossed with continental letters: 'Einstein was born here'.

But since humans don't associate to space dimensions its relative motions=actions in time, beyond locomotion, *the living functions of the 3 dimotions of space-time disappeared and with it the vitality and intelligence of the Universe, represented by the dimotion of height=informative perception & the dimotion of width, St (potential) + Ts (kinetic)= S ⇔ T: Energetic reproduction.* So in physics the duality of Momentum explained the constant trans-form-ation of one into another. While Heaviside connected the 2 dimotions of length and height with the width dimotion, with the co-invariant metric of vectorial cross product: $X \times Y = Z$. It is the law that creates the 1st perceived scale of information 'Euclidean, light space-time', evolved by 'warping', informing, by a $-ct$ parameter of electric height the $-E$ gravitational spacetime of General Relativity. So he could simplify the 20 equations of Maxwell into 4 and noticed the existence of gravitomagnetism, the first insight into the equivalence between the scales of atoms and galaxies. Width became with vectorial calculus a 'motion' of reproduction in Nature. C-speed = Ts-locomotion and the magnetic or electric field of relative height reproduce seemingly out of nothing the other relative width field. When a body reproduces cells, it packs them in the width dimension. And so we had 3 dimensions of space, connected by proper metrics (Pythagoras, cross product) and its functions =motions in time; locomotion connected to length; information connected to height and width connected to reproduction – *dimensions of space have vital functions in time constructing together ternary, topologic organisms – the fundamental particle of the living Universe.*

But humans made an even larger error regarding the substances of which we are all made, space=form and time=motion, when Newton confused a mathematical artifact with reality, thinking there was a space-time Cartesian graph with a single lineal time coordinates (that of locomotion=length) and two perpendicular spatial coordinates; taking space and time out of reality when it is obvious to experience that we, real beings, ARE made of finite vital space dimensions, the space we occupy with our bodies, and live through finite vital 'temporal motions', the time we last in existence, (Leibniz's view). *So a fractal generator equation describes all Nature's systems as combination of 3 space-time Dimotions:*

Ts-moving limbs/fields/territories <S ⇔ T reproductive ∅-body-wave-worker> St- informative particle/head/ruling class

Reality is a tapestry of organisms made of Ts-limbs/fields that move a §||-body/wave, guided by a St-high informative particle-head, in physical, biologic and social systems. Moreover the form of those 3 dimotions corresponds to the 3 only topologies (forms with motions) of spacetime: Ts=|-lineal limbs/fields, the geometry that moves faster between 2 points; St=O-spherical heads-particles, the geometry that stores maximal information; and §||= hyperbolic, wide, ∅-bodywaves, the 'hour-glass' geometry that includes the other two, hence can reproduce both. *We ARE living topologies.*

RECAP. A thorough review of the 3 space dimensions ascribe 3 motions of time to them: locomotion to 'length'; information to height and reproduction to width, vitalizing space-time, by correcting Newton's error and showing that we are all ensembles of the 3 only topologies of a 5D Universe: $|xO=\emptyset: \text{Past-Motion} \times \text{Future-Form} = \text{Present-Momentum}$

The fourth and fifth dimotions of seeds/minds and entropy-death, and the $\Delta \pm j$ scales of the fifth dimension

The metrics of all Dimensions of space-time are deceptively simple. $\sqrt{x^2+y^2}=C^2$ & $S_x \times S_y = S_z$ is the Pythagorean and vectorial metric of the 3 dimensions of space-time; $V=S/T$ with the $-c^2t^2$ ad on of Einstein is the metric of the so-called 4th dimension of time, in true form the time locomotion of length. $S \times T = \Delta \pm j$ is the metric of the scalar 5 dimensional motions of a spacetime suporganism, which states that the local speed of time of a superorganism is inversely to its size, but the product of both remains co-invariant. It means that smaller scales run faster cycles of time that encode the in-form-ation of the Universe in its frequency and form. Hence the equivalence of all species of all scales equaled by the same metric of spatial form x temporal motion (St-information or angular momentum and Ts-locomotion or lineal Momentum in layman and physical terms). As smaller species reproduce faster and survive better. So often they kill larger forms (as in the case of the present Coronavirus Pandemic,

where a simpler 30 gene virus has put on his knees the entire human civilization). But mostly, 'energy scales' associate together. So faster, smaller scales code the information of larger ones (quantum particles with its numbers code atoms and molecules, genes code biological organisms and memes code social organisms). And this 'binding' of internal and external, potential energies used to express in 'derivative' time quanta, 'vital moments' combining $O+|$ angular and lineal momenta, tic after tic of our specific 5D time ratio, to perform the vital 'dimensional motions' of existence (Ss -perceiving \rightarrow St -communicating information \rightarrow $\$T$ -reproducing \rightarrow Ts -moving \rightarrow Tt -feeding), is the vital pentalogic game of existence we all play.

The vital interactions between space-time species of different scales is either symbiotic in organic systems or predatory when scales are not entangled by fractal networks that connect the larger Δ_j whole that provides Potential energy to its $\Delta-j$ internal parts, which reproduce its information upwards. The fifth dimension thus has an scalar asymmetry and biological duality that forms organisms, even if humans have focused in the entropic Darwinian struggle for existence; not the social complex, organic symbiosis through fractal physiological networks of 'Energy and information' (layman terms for motion and form, we use often to avoid an excessive 'technical 5D' terminology – though the reader needs to interiorize the pentalogic entanglement of the 5 elements of reality in its kaleidoscopic mirror symmetries, Space=form, Time=motion, Scale=energy, Entropy=death, Mind=language, and understand its $\Delta=S=T>@$ -mind symmetries and entropic limits that structure the events and $|+O=\emptyset$ forms of reality. The laws of 5D are few but its entanglement requires a 'parallel' metaphoric way of thought different from monologic, $A>B$ present minds. It is the beauty of entanglement made of simultaneity in space, synchronicity in time, co-existence in scale.

This 1st glimpse to 5D metrics shows the importance of a new formal dimension of spacetime in all stiences. *Mathematics* from the Greeks to renaissance, all the science of physics, and the r =evolution of all sciences that those papers imply depart from such humble 'metric' beginnings. For it to happen an extraordinary effort of conceptual, logic thought that stretches to all other foundational elements of science is required; normally the work of a single mind in the beginning, as in the case of Galileo and Einstein or the eclectic gathering of several generations of thought into a strict formal discourse, as in the case of Euclidean geometry and Aristotelian logic in Greek Science. This work is both, because the 5th dimension has been among us for centuries of modern science, but never explained in the interrelationships between the different scales of the Universe, each one described by a stience. So we bring together all that work to extract the common=isomorphic laws between scales.

The EXTERNAL and internal dimotions of Space=Form and Time=motion. Pentalogic

Regardless of human dexterity as 'homunculus enzyman' (a species able to ensemble things with its hands, and evolve machines of metal of a higher density that without our help would never reach organic form), one theme that surfaces constantly in those texts is the astounding lack of common sense and rational thought in our models of reality, departing from so obvious false postulates (from big bang theory and other simplex entropic models of natural sciences to the triad of historic idol-ogies of metal, nationalism, capitalism and mechanism, to the anthropomorphic egocy (ego=idiocy) of religions. But none of those blunders compares with Newton's egocy declaring that space and time were NOT the substance of reality as Leibniz explained but a 'Cartesian frame of reference' God had drawn behind the Universe as he was using one to draw his planetary orbits and obviously he was a god-like man. 500 years of primitive thinking in all sciences derives from this blunder. Fact is reality has 5 Dimensional motions of spacetime to play with at local level and construct the superorganisms that trace worldcycles of spacetime through scales of the fifth dimension in the 'game of existence', we all play – what is all about. 'Simplicity is genius' (Leonardo); 'I want to know the thoughts of God, the rest are details'. Einstein. The thoughts of God are space dimensions and its parallel time motion and we all are the details constructed with them. The correction of Newton's error transforms lineal time measures into ∞ cyclical time clocks, ordered through scales by 5D Metrics. And it makes all beings a combination of 'Space=information and time=Momentum, motions'. As all 5D dimensions of space=form do always have content of time=motion, by the Principle of Relativity: 'we cannot distinguish a state of (time) motion from a still state (of space form)'

(Poincare) we can distinguish according to t, s , internal or T, S EXTERNAL of T or t -motion and S or s form, 6 dimotional combinations of states of space-time:

Ss-language which stops EXTERNAL MOTION or imagines the future game of existence, as a mind of the Universe.

St-information; a still organism with internal motion, as when we sleep or think or the image motion of a still Tv Set.

Ts-locomotion, a system moving externally but internally in a rigid state, as a particle-point with a gravity center.

St ↔ Ts: §||-Hyperbolic Bodywaves that combine $O+|$ Momenta, $\Delta-i$ internal and $\Delta+i$ potential energy to reproduce the whole.

Tt-entropy, a system with internal and external motion, hence becoming disordered=dying.

st: the being in itself isolated from the external world as a mind mirror of **ST**, the world isolated from the being.

S&T interactions defines *the bare minimum logic*, dilogic systems as the basic mode of existence. That is, $A \neq B$ but rather $S \leftrightarrow T$.

Space and time merge with different degrees of hierarchical complementarity to form all what exists from gender to organisms.

Nt. Max. $SxT: s=t$. It is a present balanced age of Max. Momentum or classic age of 'life', when Ts -motion and St - *come together*.

we use a dual $Ss:§$ and dual $Tt:||$ to express that present dynamic form, also $S \leftrightarrow T$; or the equation, T -past • S -Future = Present;

as a combination of dimotions into tetralogic elements, 4 genetic letters, 4 quantum numbers, 4 drives of existence denied by

entropy, is the essence of the game. As for the meanings of Energy, Space, Time, Momentum, Scale, present, past and future,

we have the problem of language errors.

RECAP. The interaction of external and internal form and motion between an ST-organism, its inner $\Delta-1$ parts and outer $\Delta+1$

world defines the main events of reality. Form has topological dimensions, which can be 1, 2,3 as all 'fractal

points' are volumes that fit Energy and information (5-E Postulate). If perceived in time they are motion.

In the beginning it was L and from L came E.T. and P... (:

So far we have only established the 'static' states of the Dimotions of the Universe. The next obvious step IS

to consider its transformations into each other, which are possible and *define the next 'degree' of ilogic*

events of spacetime starting in physics by the creation from a single 'point' with 'angular momentum' of time x energy, and lineal momentum x space.

In both cases we can see the addition of human space and time parameters to the original 'substance' of reality, a worldcycle of timespace that can travel through scales of the fifth dimension, decreasing or increasing its radius. So angular momentum is the first physical form, a complete 'unit' of the 5th dimension, and *when it decouples into energy and lineal momentum in a given scale of reality, it creates a stable 'frozen' form.*

In the formal language of Non-Euclidean mathematics we talk of a Non-E Point, with a circular membrane that can shrink increasing its time speed or expand decreasing it. How this 'point' then splits into energy x time and Lineal momentum with space can be seen as the 'separation' of its membrane that becomes lineal momentum, a non-Euclidean line, and its inner part that becomes an open ball, a topological vital space. Those are then the topologic equivalents.

But the most general view of the creative processes of existential algebra come from the use of its T-S formal symbols, to make a *proper classification of all the events of reality as transformations of 'S-T' dimotions which imply a change of a parameter, S,s, or T into other.* So departing from St, Ss, Tt, ts, Ts, ST ; the 6 static states, we obtain transformations or 'steps' that explain in more detail how reality unfolds for complex organisms. For example, an St -form in informative state, still in the outer world and with mental motion, thinking what action to do next, can change into a Ts , species in locomotion, performing an action which is a 'fixed goal' of the mind. So from $St \rightarrow Ts$ we have a basic change, which in the idealized world of physics would be equivalent to a change from 'angular momentum' to lineal momentum. But in existential algebra can be used for any scale or organism.

Another basic change is the 'shrinking' of an external world, ST into an internal st mirror-mind, of a lower scale of the fifth dimension. A far more brutal change is one of a still mind-mirror, Ss or organism in its 3rd age with no internal or external motion, the 'moment of death', into an entropic Tt -explosion of form dissolved in the process that proceeds after death.

So those transformations are the 'stuff' of which existence is made. And it is worth to notice that they tend to be 'ternary events' as the beginning and end has 2 'changes'. I.e. We go from still informative states to moving locomotion, and

presumably we pass through a brief moment in which we 'stop thinking' once an action/plan is designed and then move: $S_t > S_s > S_T$. The whole analysis of all potential dimotional changes of existence can be treated mathematically as a group; but we won't consider that formalism, except for an upgrading in particle physics, for which is the standard way of analysis.

Let us then briefly consider a few of those changes to illustrate the formal in-depth way in which the 'function of existence' becomes the details of the reality of each entity of the Universe.

5D physics: The 'joker' of energy, the 3 scales of physical systems, present momentum.

Energy as humans use the term, departed from the concept of 'vis viva' or present momentum to penetrated through all the scales of the 5th dimension, whose content of motion and form is added as new forms of energy. More precisely energy should translate as the higher 3rd physical scale of an organism: So we have 3 scalar quantities:

- The $\Delta\emptyset$ scale of $O+|$ angular and lineal momentum, where the being as a whole 'transits' with a periodicity or beat given by its function of time (speed); and the minimal quanta of that momentum, $\Delta-1$: force ; as $\partial p/\partial t = F$.

While the sum=integral of momentum along a longer path that add a series of steps, is its $\Delta+1$: 'energy=work', $\int p = W$.

Since Energy initially was used for the measure of longer work scales.

Today Energy is still larger than momentum, closer to the concept of its duration in time. So Energy x Time=Angular momentum.

So it is divided by scale in internal $\Delta-1$ scales with internal energy, $\Delta\emptyset$ -kinetic energy and the external $\Delta+1$ scale with potential energy, where the whole is seen in relationship to its world (so an electron has potential energy due to its trapping in the nucleus strong+gravitational+positive charge force and a person in a high mountain has potential energy as part of the Earth).

Finally every $\Delta\pm j$ scale of reality was added to the concept of energy when mass that includes them all inside its cosmological envelopes, down to the $\forall-3$ light scale became converted into energy, *which is not since $E=M$ means that Mass 'dies' as a form of space and transforms itself into Lineal T-motion, where that E is closer to entropy.*

So the problem of the concept of Energy in physics is that *all transformations of S-form into T-motion 'keep' the naming of Energy that has become like 'God' in old religion, the 'concept' that expresses the fact that reality is indeed an eternal transformation of S-forms into T-motions, of |-topologies into O-topologies through intermediate \emptyset -wave states.*

This means it is better for rules of measure to use the more precise concepts of $|$ -lineal momentum and O -angular momentum.

And then translate physical laws into the same ΔST laws of other stiences. For example, conservation laws conserve the ΔST elements of 5D: Δ -energy is conserved, S -form defined by cyclical angular momentum is conserved, and T -lineal time motion defined by lineal momentum is conserved. So the 3 elements of 5D reality, ΔST , which are conserved in an immortal Universe, are expressed in 3 laws of conservation in physics.

Physicists are very poor philosophers of science.

But physicists made errors when in the late XIX and earlier XX c. they tried to substitute philosophers of science and created a 'cosmogony' of reality, with 3 ridiculous theories of the absolute in which they took 'local laws' of restricted phenomena observed at local distances, eliminated then every other contradictory phenomena that balanced those local laws, expanded hyperbolically those local laws to the entire Universe in infinite time, scale and space and voila, call that astounding expansion out of the h(e)at, the meaning of it all. This was first the laws of entropy that studied the $T_t > T_s$ disordered state of matter, entropy and gas, restricted all states of reality to 2 of the 5 'Dimensional motions/states' of matter (T_t -plasma $>$ T_s -Gas $>$ \S $||$ -liquid $>$ S_t -solid $>$ S_s -Boson) of increasing order; expanded it to all other scales where matter and temperature do NOT have value as parameters (gravitational systems above in the $\Delta+j$ cosmological scales, and $\Delta-1$ quantum systems of charge, since temperature is the vibration of molecules, a defined scale of size in matter an range from 0 K when matter becomes super fluid to ± 10.000 degrees when matter becomes plasma) and then considered all was entropy, entropy was the only arrow of time and 'the Universe was dying' (Clausius) This was bullocks and as usual with the praxis of physics, the science of motion *and the building of machines and entropic weapons that disorder the inner and outer parts of the being, killing it,, it was motivated by the*

machines they made. So here we have to straighten up the theory of matter, include the other 4 STages of matter and show beautifully how they form a feed-back cycle between plasma and boson states, in the $\Delta\pm j$ scalar universe, between gas and solid states in our $\Delta\emptyset$ -plane of 'momentum'. This is a common trait of all human sciences. We first make things and then bias our models of each reality and science with the things we made. Darwin was a hunter and put his emphasis in the fight between species, which is the last Entropic state, but biology is about information at scale (genes) and organic networks at the $\Delta\emptyset$ -scale of the being, and social evolution into superorganisms most successful in survival (ant-hills, humans) at the $\Delta+1$ scale, so its closer to love religions based in a language than hunting-killing of the sick at the last Tt-entropic stage. This tendency continued when after making nuclear bombs, again the arrow of entropic Time-vacuum with no information (lineal motions of dark energy between galaxies) expanded to include the opposite informative gravitational forces that implode dark energy into virtual particles within galaxies, to create the big-bang theory of the Universe, expanding also local measures of the galactic background radiation to the whole Universe, and expanding a lineal Hubble equation to infinity. So we need also to correct the big-bang to include the informative force of gravitation that balance it and we do so easily when we realize that we can unify the forces of gravitation and electromagnetism, masses and charges as two vortices of space-time of the limiting cosmological and quantum $\Delta\pm j$ scales. An atom then is similar to a galaxy and internally it is driven by the cyclical 'strong gravitational force' but externally is driven by the 'expansive dark=electromagnetic energy'. Alas, this obvious duality of scale illuminate the entire field of cosmology and shows the symbiosis and parallelism between the small and the large, that defines an organic Universe, as in all other system – cells have the same functions than organisms; human individual memes and languages become through art and religion the subconscious collective of mankind and its civilizations go in fact through 3 similar epic, young, classic, mature and old, baroque angst art ages, dying in collective explosions of entropy called wars. It is then a galaxy an atom? Likely not, but there are symbiotic synchronicities and simultaneous co-existence as there are between cells and organisms, human generations and civilizations st-ages, which is the beautiful $\Delta=S=T$ fundamental law of symmetry in the 5D Universe between the 3 $\Delta\pm j$ scales of a being, made of smaller atoms/cells, living in an organic, thermodynamic world, part of a larger planetary cosmological ecosystem, the 3 varieties of topology that make up its lineal $|-$ fields limbs, cyclical O-heads/particles and \emptyset -hyperbolic body-waves that ensemble the organism and its young, lineal, moving mature, \emptyset -reproductive and O-informative 3rd old time ages.

The symmetries between $\Delta=S=T$ elements of reality NOT weirdo cheating reductionist model of physics is the philosophy of science that entangles together the entire Universe. Finally if in the $\Delta+1$ scale the big bang is the false model, in the $\Delta\emptyset$ thermodynamic scale, the entropy only theory is the wrong model, in the $\Delta-1$ scale the Copenhagen interpretation is the wrong model. Here we have the work of a forgotten genius that did it right so we don't have to develop the entire quantum physics afresh, thanks God as I am a lazy old man with a myelin problem. It is De Broglie's theory latter expanded by Bohm of realist quantum physics, NOT the Bohr-Born Copenhagen interpretation, so from B2 to B2 we change the model. This was an astounding abuse of Bohr, the Danish banker, Born, the idealist Hilbert's student who 'imagined' reality as his master and Heisenberg, the Nazi, and his partners in crime against the original founders of quantum theory, Broglie, the French Aristocrat, and Einstein, the pantheist, and latter on Bohm, the communist, who had it right but didn't use worldly power and egocy arguments to explain the entangled Universe and left the bullies the field. Broglie defined the complementary principle today ascribed to Bohr, which has an immediate translation in the key law of 5D physics at conceptual level: the Principle of absolute relativity extended to scale 'we cannot perceive at the same moment, 2 scales of the 5th dimension, and the 2 states of form and motion of a system'. So we cannot see the Earth moving and not moving even if it has both, form=space and time=motion; we cannot see the $\Delta+1$ particle state and the $\Delta\emptyset$ -wave state and the $\Delta-1$ quantum potential field state of the quantum system at the same moment even if the 3 co-exist together as in any other superorganism (but the $\Delta-1$ quantum potential of Broglie according to 5D metrics is $v>c$ so we don't perceive it; as in the case of the vacuum time between galaxies, and we shall study those details in the section on quantum and cosmology). Alas, 3 sacred dogmas of 'physics as philosophy of science' are wrong and must be straighten up, as it should have been obvious beyond 'egocy' because physics is NOT philosophy of science, 'zapatero a tus zapatos' they say in Spanish, or in harsher terms, 'no esta hecha la miel para la boca del asno', 'quien quiera entender que entienda' – the Latin culture being humanist, old and wise at popular level has the best sayings along the Chinese one, because the common people, the 90% knows better. In plain English, 'stick to your job'.

And that job in physics is the study of physical systems in its 3 'scalar' quantities, $\Delta-1$ forces, $\Delta\emptyset$ -momentum, $\Delta+1$ work and the warping up of them together, in Energy parameters, to study how they transform into each other, through ratios that are

Universal constants, what happens in the 'between 2 waters' regions of emergence and evanescence of scales, where the lineal equations of constant ratios in the middle region breaks down (which we call Lorentzian regions, nearby 0 K and c-speed) but somewhat systems 'tunnel' through them; and ultimately the job we shall commit in our physical papers of harmonizing all those laws with the higher laws of 5D philosophy of 'stiences'.

In our scale those laws relate angular and lineal momentum, the 2 conserved forces through mechanics, study its lower scale through $F=ma$ forces and its upper scales. They then study their interaction in SHM motions, when both momentums are in balance, which we can obtain by adding them, $O-St+|-Ts='Ø-§\Pi'$.

This quantity is the Existential Momentum of the physical system, its existential energy when added through all its $\Delta\pm j$ scales, what the being tries to conserve, increase by stealing it from other physical species and use it to achieve its 5 Dimensional motions of existence, in those scales of physics where we do study a 'vital physical system' (particles, atoms and its social molecules, stars and black holes).

Each scale though will have different parameters as 5D metrics change the proportion of cyclical time speed and lineal space extension, with a simple rule: $\Delta-j$ scales have more 'angular momentum' (cyclical time speed) and less lineal momentum (spatial extension). Again we are NOT going to rewrite equations with the logic symbols of 5D. It is too late in the history of science to do so. Physicists learned the 'wrong way to typewrite' with one 'finger' (entropy) and now they are not going to learn to type write with 5 so to speak (: but if we want to explain the whys of physics we do have to explain conceptually the equivalence of concepts. And that is the reason *5D physical papers are so verbose*.

It is the only way outside those 3 theories that are wrong and need to be changed, to make sense of it. We need to reason the causes in terms of 5D of physical laws which today are merely expressed through equations and 'magically' ascribed in its causes to some creationist, religious dogma that 'mathematics' is the cause of reality, NOT the mirror-language of space-time 5D laws, the real cause of reality, which can be expressed as different species do with different languages. So the creationist philosophy of science – mathematics is the cause of reality – is also false. A mirror does NOT create reality. It mirrors it, though it can project and shape a bit reality with its projections after it has watched it. So we watch the Universe with words and then modify with words a bit reality. We do study then in the sections dedicated to the Ss-mind that interaction between languages=mirrors and 'AST' the cause of reality. Ss-minds are once more in pentalogic, only $1/5^{\text{th}}$ of the dimensional motions of space-time NOT the whole. So this other theory of reality, that is not Tt-entropy but Ss-mind languages its cause, is also false. The Universe is simple but not that simple, said Einstein, one of the few truly interesting physicists along Planck and Broglie in the triad of modern physics, in an over dimensioned discipline due to its praxis of making machines and weapons, and the egocy of power.

Space, Time and scale create all the laws of reality, but languages are synoptic mirrors that have the advantage of 'overcoming' the limits of perception of Absolute relativity, so they can 'imagine' what we cannot perceive simultaneously through 'equalities' and 'verbs'=actions that peg S and T, names and objects, in equations and verbal sentences. The extraordinary synoptic capacity of languages that expel motion, simplify form, put in relationship scales and extract higher laws that perception and action alone cannot is what gives them power to then project its imagination and recreate a better reality. So how languages improve by synoptic methods reality, from palingenesis in genetics to mathematical projections to verbal actions is an important part of 45D but not the whole.

The reader should be more of a gradualist and love the shadows of grey, between Ss-minds and Tt-entropy. It is in the middle golden mean of 'moment(um)s' of existence, made of internal angular Momentum=information, and external lineal momentums, related to its internal $\Delta-j$ energy, and external $\Delta+1$ potential one given by the position of the being, in the whole where the subtle details of physics are to be found. The Universe is entangled, complex despite its simple first 3 elements, time-motions of two types, cyclical that appears as form in space, and lineal, structured as cyclical vortices bore down into deeper scales, and mirrors shrink into still forms, and project into larger scales, into organic $\Delta\pm j$ 5D systems, because every point 'holds a world in itself' (Leibniz on non-Euclidean fractal worlds). There will be a huge number of humans too simple and dogmatic to access the subtle interplay of those 5 elements, Δ -scales of space=form and time-motion, mirrored in still mind-languages or exploited in entropic death. But we provide as the Universe does with multiple equivalent languages to express

that pentalogic, the easiest one, that which combines dimensions of spatial form, S and temporal motion, T, in the internal and external entanglement of beings as Ss-minds, St-information (angular momentum) Ts-locomotion (lineal momentum) Δ -energy scales and Tt-entropic outer and inner motion that disorders the being.

After 30 years of using together in my parallel multiple 'schizoid' mind (: all the languages, I have come to the conclusion that those 5 combinations and the original topological language I first discovered of |limbs/fields of motions, O-heads/particles of information and \emptyset -waves/bodies of reproduction, ARE the simplest, best, more encompassing ones. So those 3 languages, the 3 varieties of $|xO=\emptyset$ -Topology, the EXTERNAL and internal combinations of form and motion (space and time) and the 5 separated elements studied as 'concepts', space=form, time=motion, scale=energy, entropy=death, mind= language is what the reader must first understand. Once it does FOR ALL STIENCES, each one studying a scale of space-time; this simple scaffolding of first principles, will guide him through every other stience, and jargon.

So in EXTERNAL and internal Space-time form-motion terms we can establish a gradation of combined space-time dualities, **Ss<St<§||<st<Tt**, with a symbol < for an increase of motion over form, departing from the 'dimotion of entropy or past dimotion of death' as it erases information, devolving a system to simpler forms; and vice versa, an inverse dimotion, **Tt>st>§||>St>Ss**, with the symbol > of an increase of form over motion, or 'dimotion of in-form-ation, the 'future dimotion' of life' as it increases information – an arbitrary choice opposed to that of physicists of entropic weapons that subconsciously chose entropy=eath as the future due to its worldly profession. We DO side against the present mechanical culture of death with life in all stiences, notably in economics (we side with the 90% of mankind) and physics (we side with information). It then becomes evident that the intermediate state, §||, with a balanced quantity of Spatial information and temporal Motion, S=T, is the 'state of present', that doesn't seem to change as it is a balance of form and motion; but it is always a dynamic state. So it is the more complex to describe as we don't have a single word. It is both the sum of angular and lineal momentum, |+O; so we use \emptyset as its symbol in topologic forms. It is also the convergence of the Δ -i entropic internal energies from lower scales and the effects of outer larger potential energies from our Δ +j wholes, so they come from down and up, into our $\Delta 0$ -scale, which we write as $\Delta\emptyset$ often, to match $o=\emptyset$; it is then a π cycle that opens and closes its mouth in dynamic exchange between reproductive waves of Ts-locomotion and particles of St-information.

We write it as $S\leftrightarrow T$, S=T, or doubling both symbols, §||; we call it momentum but often also $\Delta\emptyset$ -energy. This present liquid state, mature classic st-age, which is also the equation of 'harmony and beauty', this golden mean we seek for, we live through each of its moments, will then to keep in parallel with the fluctuating dynamic variation of its SHM, harmonic motions, be expressed with all that range of wordings, ' \emptyset -momentum', $\Delta\emptyset$ -energy, §||-dimotion... but likely the best way to define it is as existential momenta, because life consists in going through each of our O+|, $S\leftrightarrow T$ momenta, always trying to combine motion and form to rcreate those existential quanta of which life is made, and apply our $\Delta\pm j$ energies to our 5 Dimotions of existjence. The game of existjence then is defined in its subtle variation for all beings with that pentalogic to which we add the duality of the st-inner being and the ST-outer world (heptalogic) and then we double through 'bilateral' decalogic systems, leaning towards one or the other side (networks of organisms), and slowly through new decouplings and trinity diversifications, in $|xO=\emptyset$, $Ts>\S||>St$ ages and $\Delta\pm j$ sub-scales, reality branches, unfolds and grows in creative diversity.

But \emptyset is the preferred state for any system of spacetime in the Universe, akin to the concept of 'beauty' (balance between cyclical forms and lineal motions), of reproduction and creative communication (as it brings together the two poles of reality merging and combining them). All systems seek this state. So in physics we find it akin to the state of 'minimal Momentum' hence more form' in which most particles like to remain; in biology is akin to the age between adolescence of maximal Motion and the 3rd age of maximal information, or age of reproduction, in which most people like to live.

Departing from those dimotions of space and time, the 5D Universe builds all systems of reality.

We have a description of reality – a fractal system made of topological organisms of co-existing scales of space and cyclical time which close its 'internal vital point content' with the entropic limit of those time cycles, in its vital territorial body-waves, synchronized symbiotically by 5D metrics. As we are all ultimately $-\Delta@St$; dust of space-time.

There are 2 time forms, long lineal Time and short frequency steps we integrate into the larger whole; because *there are 2 $\pm j$ scales of 5D reality whose metric, $\S x\delta=\Delta\pm j$ defines larger space systems as having slower time cycles.* So we can always

consider the frequency of time the Δ -j 'quanta of time' or 'finitesimal derivative' of the larger whole represented with the concept of lineal time; as in the classic formula, $S=f(t) \lambda(s)$. The whole Space can be measured, $Vt=S$ with lineal time as a single unit, or it can be measured as a sum of frequency steps, with more detail. But if we see those 2 'forms' of time, as 'lineal Momentum and cyclical information', since information is stored in the frequency and form of time cycles, we can then consider that 'time=motion' splits in two essential forms, lineal motion or 'Momentum', and cyclical motion or 'information', and express the main law of science, the principle of conservation of Momentum in terms of the conservation of time=motion in its two varieties that transform each other ad eternal:

'All what exists are time motions that transform between lineal open and cyclic closed forms ad eternal: $S_i \leftrightarrow T_e$ '

This sentence is the simplest expression reality as a constant game of transformation of 'spatial information' (cyclical time) and temporal Momentum (lineal time) and was first understood by Taoism, where 'Tao=time', is composed of yin=cyclical form and yang=lineal Momentum, today expressed as the principle of conservation of Momentum. Its 'mathematical, logic' formula is $S_i \leftrightarrow T_e$ & and its logic form, $exi=st$, is the function of existence.

RECAP. Conservation of space, scale & time laws. The relationship of the 5th dimension with energy.

The 5th Dimension of scalar space-time does not contradict physics, as it is closely related to Energy, the parameter humans have expanded painstakingly precisely to mimic the 'flows of space=form and time=motion' that travel through the 5th dimension, even without a clear conceptual definition of it. Now we can simply state that energy is 'Space-time' traveling through 5D according to its metrics equations, which conserve (maintain co-invariant) the volume of energy (space-time) of the Universe, both between scales as Δ -energy and in each scale as Lineal time-momentum and angular space-momentum. So the 3 conserved quantities of physics become the 3 qualitative elements of the 5D Universe: ΔST .

Energy is both in equations and common talk the 5D spacetime an organism takes from its 3 $\Delta \pm j$ scales of existence that powers, delivered in discontinuous T_f 'derivative quanta of forces the present moment(um)s', whose actions=dimensional motions of survival are the stuff of which existence is made. Let us then study in greater detail those pentalogic actions.

Conclusion. A different philosophy of science. The Universe is not creationist but vital, obeying pentalogic space-time laws.

Philosophy of science matters more than physics, as all $\Delta \pm j$ scales are the same.

The jump of philosophical understanding is already huge. A Universe made of motion=time and mental spaces= forms is completely abstract and spiritual but in a logic, vital way. It requires a deep change in your mind view, because the 'material' concepts go away. Motion=time is the substance of reality. So you see events. Form=Space is a mental, linguistic mapping. Leibniz intuitively understood this when he said that each point is a world in itself. We are then in a sentient Universe defined by two poles: 0ϵ -finitesimal minds, which are 'knots' of time cycles. And those time cycles. It requires a huge jump into metaphysics, even if we shall keep all the equations of physics, precisely because those minds-mappings are topological mirror-images in the languages of geometry (points) and social scales (numbers), connected by algebraic operands (that describe the different motions of space-time). I have been amazed by the Δ -scalar-numerical, Time-algebraic Space-topologic Universe for so long I can't even imagine how to think in other terms. But a 4D physicist differs from Leibniz, Einstein and this writer, which reason that space and time and its properties come before the mirror languages that observe it. This creates different scientific methods. For the 4D physicist, all consists in gathering data with sensorial machines, deemed more exact than human ones, and put it in the digital language those machines perceive, which is mathematics. So once the relationships of data as equations is written, the 'job is done'. Ultimately this means physics becomes a praxis of industrial machines. Does it matter? Yes, it does. To understand the Universe is vital to survive on it. If humans understood the vital nature of matter, its evolutionary topologies, etc. it won't create AI robots. If they had a proper concept of space and time, they would strive in History to reach the $S=T$, (max. SxT) point of balance and immortality of the function of existence, etc. All this seems now a dream as the species has taken always the 'Subjective, Mechanical, Entropic, Lineal' view. What we call the SMELLYing point of view, as in the big-bang, Copenhagen interpretation and mechanist science, whose ultimate reason seem more connected to historic cultures that science. So unless history is 'straighten up' and man survives its present age of entropy, chances are we go under without ever understanding the first principles of the Universe.

5D scalar physics as strange as the reader might think it is – for the simple reason he has a 4D Ptolemaic view and that is for him truth – is completely consistent with the same data of 4D physics, and so the magic of it, is how we can see two Universes so different ? The answer is part because ‘languages of Ss-information’, as all mirrors are kaleidoscopic, so we can have several views. This we illustrate latter with the 4 canonical views of gravitation, Newton, Poisson, Einstein which derive from each other, corresponding to an $S \leftrightarrow T$ view, and Lagrange, in a complete different Δ -scalar, energy view.

This is then a first duality of ‘very different views’, the Space-time view in a single plane related to each other, and the scalar, Δ -view, which in physics is the ‘momenta’ view of O-angular=cyclical space-time and $|$ -lineal spacetime and the $\Delta \pm j$ Energy/Entropy view. *The beauty of mind-languages is that by reducing and simplifying all views can store them all. The problem of mathematical physics is to have gone too far in the desire to store it all with a single math picture, which ‘stiffles’ the view into ‘space-form’, reducing its dynamism and ‘compressing’ its scales of ‘social numbers’ into a single ‘real line’ of continuous points. So 5D stretches back reality, and differentiates clearly between $\Delta \pm j$ and $S \leftrightarrow T$; and SS-mind languages.*

The reader won’t ever upgrade its capacity to view the Universe unless it absorbs deeply those basic relationships and symmetries that took me a decade of the best of my mind years in youth to clarify and he has it for free and a few days of thought. The beauty of them is he can see all, not only physics with the $\nabla S \perp T \Delta \Delta S \approx T$ dualities and symmetries of its first principles, space, time (which can be in a Darwinian perpendicular \perp relation or a symmetric \approx , parallel one, the first leading towards an ∇ entropic fall of scale and the second to an Δ growth into a new energy dimension.

We insist that mathematical creationism is NOT the basis of the Universe, but the best synoptic mirror. Moreover, the way physicists handle maths is loose and as we shall see next in the evaporation of black holes, no longer rely on experimental evidence or known-known laws, as the causal strict logic has been substituted by creationism. However there is a huge merit in serious mathematical physics and we do NOT include on the logic models of 5D spacetime theories which we have not checked in scholarship as possible respecting the laws of physics, *even if most physicists are unaware of them.*

So the crib is simple: a model of physics must meet the standards of known-theories, non-Euclidean geometry, 5D metric, and the rules of epistemology, notably experimental evidence and economicity and those of pentalogic: symmetry, fractal scalar nature (hilomorphism), isomorphism (equal laws of scale), multiple roles and dimotions, (internal structure and function in a larger whole). This creates the real architechtonic nature of the Universe and its vital laws equal in all scales. How this changes with the same data and the same mathematical rigor the worldview of science? A short list will suffice to see it:

- *The Universe is scalar and symmetric, the main symmetry being between atoms and galaxies, and hence between gravitational and strong forces, and electromagnetic and weak forces; and the 3 families of quarks and the 3 organic parts of the galaxy.*
- *The scalar structure is dynamically represented by the $\Delta-1$ scale of forces, the $\Delta 0$ -scale of momentum and the $\Delta+1$ of energy.*
- *Each scale has a fundamental organism, and a lineal and cyclical state. So we move from theoretical open-time like and closed space-like strings, through the Neutrino background, through the light background onto the particles background and so on...*
- *In each scale the $-S \perp T$ symmetry gives us a 0-sum, as lineal vs. cyclical, $|$ v. O topological parts become a zero sum. However they ‘reproduce=merge’ together into a present \emptyset -hyperbolic wave. So key equations of physics come from those 2 simple ‘vital operands: $S=T$, $T-S=0$, which is the choice of humans that give to + expansive motion and – implosive motions those values.*

Those symmetries then happen in all scales and we have positive and negative charges, particles and antiparticlers, angular and lineal momentum, potential and kinetic energies, combined into waves, Single harmonic motions and other 0-sums.

It follows a deep understanding of what space=form and time=motion is required to do physics, unlike in the present model which uses lineal absolute space-time. We will thus go back and forth between conceptual principles and results, which are notable and yet we insist all have the same experimental data and mathematical rigor. Consider for example the scalar relationships between neutrino, light and electrons. Each scale must be made of smaller parts and we DON’T use particles never discovered (economy and hilomorphism in classic epistemology). This LEAVES NO other alternative than a Neutrino theory of light and a light theory of electronic nebulae. This is the sound logic that supersedes creationism. Among physicists only Einstein and Broglie had it intuitively in all his work. So Broglie defined the neutrino theory of light. Then a savant idiot

rejected it because 'neutrinos were fermions' and light 'bosons', and as all the work of Broglie who was right (see quantum realism), it was rejected. Latter of course the secondary law was override when we found Kaons, etc. that existed with boson statistics made of fermions. The 2nd formulation of the theory found a hurdle: the neutrino and antineutrino had to be emitted by particles in the exact direction, but that is what 5D states: a form is architectonically built in '5D' as 3D printing, layer after layer, so the neutrino background allows particles to entangle in the quantum potential still to each other and emit information, since information is always emitted between 2 forms in parallel equal distance – so when you talk you go side by side even if you move. Alas, the 3rd problem is that those neutrinos had to have 0 or negative mass. But that is precisely what 5D expects, as each lower scale has faster motion and less information. So neutrinos $v > c$ as they carry $v(i) < c(i)$, less information, so $S(i) \times T(f) = C$. Then it comes the problem that in Lorentz transformations tachyons have negative mass-energy, but that is precisely the meaning of a tachyon: repulsive gravitation, which we see as expanding space-time distances, responsible for the dark energy which is the neutrino background radiation. Further on, from the point of view of particles in relative entangled stillness Lorentz transformations do NOT apply, as they work like a movie: in its scale they stop, project information and move, and we see its Brownian motion so this is the experimental fact about particles: stop, emit information as particles-heads in stillness, as your head is, then move as waves. But to measure in our 'view' which eliminates the stop as when we see a continuous movie, we need Lorentz transformations. Both views are right but belong to two scales, and so the more profound is that of the objective stop and go particle with no Michelson addition of speeds, entangled by a neutrino dark energy quantum potential... Alas, the data is the same, even more respectful of the stop and go experimental fact, the view of the Universe has changed. THIS IS 5D FUN (:

The no-method of my papers. The 2 postulates of Absolute relativity and 5D metric function of existence: $Max. SxT|s=t$

5D physics is as extensive as Quantum and relativity combined if not more, but the handicap is my vaporization due to the thoughtcrime of my GNA activism against CERN, so it is buried in Academia.edu and unificationtheory.com and tons of black-out 5" diskettes, my interest and IQ going down fast, so you must take this paper as a brute diamond. Still 30 years ago when I completed Absolute relativity and 5D metric function of existence: $Max. SxT|s=t$; I used this simple equations and its 2 postulates: you cannot distinguish motion=time from form =space (e pur si muove, e pur no muove), hence $S=T$, and the scalar metric $S_i \times T_f = \Delta \pm j$ to explore all the equations, laws and events of all sciences including biology and social sciences. So I know nothing like this r=evolution of thought in a single 'model' has happened to mankind for a century, likely for millennia.

If it is a non-derivative peak, time will tell. Certainly I have been for 2 decades now going down the peak I achieved at 30, when I used that equation in a 30 meters roll left in Cali, likely lost, to deduce all equations of all sciences, in what I considered the summit of my 'painting style', EC^2 (: Expressionist, Conceptual Cubism, paintings with expressionist colors, topological curved and lineal variations written in several layers, some collages of paintings, to reveal finally an underlying equation of existential algebra). If I tell you this is simply because I leave no disciples and my mind is fading away, but it has been an adventure of thought like only a few huminds have experienced. It is not my fault that the domesticated modern animal enzyman, to the service of company-mothers of machines, a child suffering as all domesticated animals a loss of brain and lacking any survival instincts, will have none of it. If a human has seen the Universe in all its simplicity and splendor it means many other planet will have civilizations built on the truths of 5D metrics, ethics and organic laws. Here it will not happen as the method of knowledge today is enzymanic: humans gather information with sensorial machines, buttressing it in computer models of digital equations that produce a result. The human part soon will be done by robots, the mental, logic part on domesticated animals is minimal. Hawking with its dependence of computers, mental paralysis and null conceptual verbal, logic causal capacity, the essential Schopenhauer's st-upid, infantile, unable even to grasp the ethic responsibility of its subjective childish musings is the role model of XXI c. as Warhol Not Picasso, the faked artist with industrial procedures to sell more printed repetitions of null aesthetic and intellectual exploration of the '2 Dimensional motions' of Human art, is a similar model for art. Bieber, Not Mozart, a UTube child with computerized arrangements, is the model of musician, Trump is the model of politico and Fuld, both parasites, exploiting mankind with bills of law and bills of money, the models of social scientists. This is the Tt-age of entropy of History, and the view of mankind is ugly. The view of the Universe though is as perfect and beautiful, balanced and eternal as it always has been. But as I am human in my own age of entropy all my work will move from the e-motions of not being to the motions of the perfect Universe in a bipolar not under the rules of the Chicago manual of style, stream of thought.

But as 5D is first logic, pentalogic verbal thought is needed. This might come as a surprise since Galileo's rejection of Aristotle he did not understand but space is ALWAYS a mental space, form, Si, meaning Spatial size but more precisely Spatial information (so in physics is often measured by density of mass, energy). Reality is NOT mathematical first but logic, causal, as its substance is time, its particle-points stop time into space-form, $0\epsilon \times \alpha = C$ (mental worlds), and so we need also to explain the ultimate causality with is a panpsychic vital Universe, and use the 'humanist method' as we cannot access inner minds but suppose the humind, made also as a mapping of space-time is the same than all others, so are our e-motions related to the dimotions of the Universe, our deterministic program of existence in search of energy for our body, motion for our limbs, information for our particle-head, social evolution and reproduction through our scalar 'force=dimotion=actions', that take from Δ -4: Boosts of motion, Δ -3: Bits of information, Δ -2: Bites of energy, Δ -1 Babies and Δ 0 brothers to Become (:

This is a verbal expression of the way dimotions create a program of existence that is the same for all systems. So the vital narrative makes much easier to understand physics because it uses the human language. If I explain the duality of gender by mirror symmetry (CP) in physics between female particles slightly more easier to reproduce than male particles where the \pm inward and outward relationships between particles and heads (nucleus and orbitals) are changed, the reader will might reject straight (scholar who just wants to write equations) but the humind might feel entangled as it should with the whole Universe because the duality particle-antiparticle IS the first gender reproductive duality of the Universe. Mesons are indeed couples. But the beauty of the Universe is that the same principles give multiple versions, and that time is cyclical so there is always a local past view. So genders in physics mate and produce a child Δ -1 γ -ray but die in the process giving ALL its energy to the baby that often will grow up to reproduce new particles. Moreover you can see the antiparticle as just the 'male drone' bond to die when in contact with the female particle (and that is the view I hold for long: the antiparticle is the death point of the particle, from a temporal future to past Feynman's diagram point of view). So vital concepts are absolutely real necessary and causal – they ARE the cause of the events of physics as much as biology and sociology. PARTICLES RE=PRODUCE, machines re=produce, human reproduce, 'all do it' as the song sings.

Does it mean we abandon the mathematical method? NOT, BUT WE ARE NOT writing here Dirac's equations and prove with lengthy commutations and quantum operators anything we do. I will in a second review add all what my lazy old mind is NOT doing now, because I lost my notebooks, erased by error harddrives and can't reconstruct 30 years of work – to look at arxiv.org, read the maths of the best articles on each of those themes and if correct quote them here. I.E yesterday I was looking to see if there were papers on dark energy $v>c$ neutrinos with negative mass cause of the background expansion of space. I haven't look at physics for more than a decade since my activism against CERN. To my *surprise they were many, 2 researchers, Schwartz from Caltech and Luca from Italy, were solid mathematicians, and there were a new paper with huge following on scalar gravitation that at large scale became repulsive. This is what I mean for mathematical proofs, the inflationary nature of maths and the open way physicists deal with equations to model reality ever since Dirac seated by the fire and rooted Schrodinger to get its gamma matrices so beautifully used for creative physics, just adding terms to them; allows what the Universe does best, the Gell-mann totalitarian principle: all what can exist does exist, but 5D CRIB means only what is worthy to exist, symmetric, efficient, entangled, topologically sound, functionally vital, performing the 5 Dimotions for a larger Δ +1 world, etc will last. This means we are NOT concerned either by the mass of virtual particles whose existence is so short they are just like all the biological mutations that don't make it or the mad thoughts of humans or the ugly machine of inventors that don't enter production lines, unlike physicists that lacking the 5D crib of pentalogic and existential algebra accept it all, and vice versa, lacking the understanding of cut off finitesimals, \pm dynamics etc. get rid of disturbing results that actually happen.*

A FIRST SYNOPSIS OF 5D SCALAR PHYSICS WITHOUT YET THE WORLDCYCLES OF MATTER AND GALATOMS.

UNIFICATION OF 5 GALAXY'S FORCES AS ITS 5 DIMOTIONS WITH SCALAR SYMMETRIES. DARK MATTER & ENERGY.

We insist that 5D comes from 2 simple postulates equations of Absolute relativity and its 5D metric function of existjence: Max. $S \times T | s=t$: you cannot distinguish motion=time from form=space hence $S=T$, and as there are ∞ broken vital spaces and circadian clocks, each organism is a knot of space-time cycles, spreading through 3 scales ruled by the con-invariant metric $S_i \times T_j = \Delta \pm j$.

I lack however at this st-age of my life the energy to write it properly and most of my earlier work is lost. Others might systematize. At first sight the equations establish angular momentum as the 'cyclical measure' of spacetime (both always combined as we cannot distinguish $S=T$), lineal momentum as its 'lineal measure' and Energy transferred between scales.

We are thus not concerned with the humind's \forall >Electronic view as absolute truth, but incorporate it as we see fit. For example, absolute space and time enter from angular momentum conversions = Energy x Time = Lineal Momentum x Space. This makes angular momentum, *a worldcycle of time, the most fundamental parameter, and \hbar , its measure in the Light space-time galaxy. The Galaxy then not THE UNIVERSE we don't perceive is the 'organism studied by 5D physics'. Because $S \times T = C$ defines infinite scales, there should be one for that larger nested Universe, and it is immediate it is the neutrino background as it fits all requirements. If we make neutrinos the 'dark energy' background, then we solve the problem of the vacuum energy which is exactly the one expected from the tiny 0,01 ev calculated for neutrinos. We solve the problem of the expansion of space, as we do NOT see neutrinos, but they obviously departing from the 'other side of c-speed' stuck to the 'neutrino theory of light' as components of the background radiation of this galaxy, start to accelerate as soon as they abandone the galaxy, and 'stretch' the \forall -ray frequency till it scaters at 1000 Z. It is then obvious neutrino physics becomes the most important hard-science contribution of 5D. But we do NOT need to make new calculations. The inflation of mathematical papers, physicists and computers has done it all. So we shall just if I read physics again, something I abandoned after CERN suits quote them.*

The beauty of having a model so profound, tested in all stiences and realist and simple as 5D is, is that we just know what is truth and what is real. This we can see in the work of Broglie, Planck and Einstein, the true pioneers of XX c. physics. You have the view of the whole forest, and so you know when a tree is rotten to the bone.

Since a charge is smaller than a mass, it attracts much more and the unification equation follows just when we apply 5D metric, and shrink the galaxy in the same proportion we accelerate them. Then both equations match. Since mass, $E=mc^2 + E=hf$; is a frequency: $m \approx f (h/c^2)$; it is a cosmological slow vortex, and charge a quantum faster more attractive vortex.

Further on since curvature is synonymous of cyclical speed, it can be quasi-infinite in the smaller vortex, when measured in time speed as the speed of angular rotation. So if we were to apply 4D curvature's equations (Einstein) instead of Newton, the results would be the same, just in the far more complicated formalism of EFE. So charges and masses as accelerated time vortices of two different scales of the Galaxy. And from that it is only just an easy task of mathematical manipulation to unify them in 5D metric, as both are equal: when we slow down the speed, space enlarges to remain co-invariant. And as it happens a Hydrogen atom enlarged to the size of a galaxy slows down in rotation to the angular momentum of the galaxy. So Kaluza–Klein were *right - the fifth scalar dimension unifies gravity with electromagnetic forces but in a fractal manner, with 5D metric, unbeknownst to physicists*. Since charges and masses are just accelerated S_s -vortices of spacetime of two different scales of the 5th dimension, which frame the limits of human perception of the Universe, so we can unify both with a simple translation of 5D Metric $C=\$x\delta$ such as if we expand a charge and decelerate its speed it will reach the size of a galaxy, while its electron will reach the size of the star nebulae that surrounds each black hole=proton.

Let us do the maths in the simpler Newton's formalism, whereas by the paradox of Galileo S (Curvature) = T (accelerated motion). So the Universal Constants (G, k), define the curvature of 2 space-time vortices at the $\Delta-1$ quantum charge and $\Delta+1$ cosmic mass scales (Δ is the symbol for the different $\pm j$ scales of the fifth dimension within a given organic system). Its formalism of a vortex of time space is then Newton's Unification Equation: $M, Q = \omega^2 r^3 / U.C.(G, k)$

I leave for the 5D future researcher to do the work with Einstein's Tensors. It does work too, but I won't go into complex maths for all the reasons aforementioned. It applies to all vortices of time-space from particles to planets to galaxies.

$$\frac{F_e}{F_g} = \frac{k_e q_{proton}^2}{G m_{proton}^2} \approx 10^{39}$$

It works marvels when we translate electromagnetic jargon to Newtonian jargon. For example it shows the 'isomorphism' (systemic jargon for an equal 'form' between scales) between atoms and galaxies, which H-atoms of the cosmic scale. *Since when* we translate electromagnetic equation into gravitational mass vortices, the proton radius becomes the Schwarzschild radius of a black hole and its electronic orbitals its star clouds, a result foreseen by Relativity that modeled galaxies as Hydrogen atoms in the Einstein-Walker Metric of the Cosmos. So if we substitute the parameters for the sun-earth system in that Unification equation we get G, *from a theoretical calculus, which* has never been done and can't be exact 'by chance', unless the theoretical model behind the 5D scalar structure of the Universe, is truth: Sun mass = 2×10^{30} kg; Earth's angular velocity 2×10^{-7} rad. per sec. Earth's orbit = 150 million kms. Result: $G=6.67 \times 10^{-11} \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ m}^3 \text{ rad. sec.}^{-2}$

If we substitute the values of the main quantum space-time vortex, a Bohr electronic orbital of a hydrogen atom/charge we get the value of the universal constant of charges, the Coulomb constant: $4 \times 10^{16} \text{ rad. sec.}^{-1} = w$ (electron); $5.3 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}$. (Bohr radius); proton mass = $1.6 \times 10^{-27} \text{ kg}$. Then we get a G, which is 2×10^{39} stronger than the gravitational radius; thus, the hydrogen atom behaves as a self-similar fractal scale in the quantum world to a solar system.

And then you can get also the electron radius expressed in the jargon of a quantum gravitational world using the translated 'Gravitational Coulomb constant': $G(k)M/c^2$.

Since in that expression M is the mass of a proton, G(k), the electromagnetic constant is a gravitational constant, and c, light speed, that expression is exactly the Schwarzschild radius of a quantum black hole=Top quark star. Thus, the electron Bohr radius, which is the final radius of minimal size and Momentum in electrons, is isomorphic to the event horizon of a black hole in the quantum gravitational world. Those results, 3 decades old, are a *1st theoretical* mathematical deduction of Ke and G, relating both, and showing the atom to be a potential trap for the electron as the galaxy is for its stars. It was the 2nd paper I sent to 'peer review' in 5D after the 5 -E postulates that defined a fractal point. Only got an answer back telling me Newtonian physics were 4 centuries outdated. *Obviously I used the Newtonian simpler formalism, as the 3 ages of Gravitational space-time vortices formal analysis, Newton>Poisson>Einstein are just '3 degrees of complexity' deduced from each other that don't change its principles -charges and masses are accelerated vortices(Principle of Equivalence) of 2 different 5D scales of space-time which follow the same 'Topologic, social=numerical=scalar' and Dimotional=operand laws. The true change came with Lagrangian Energy physics that deduced it from the 'Ts>§T>St' balances in a single space-time plane; as all in science comes either from 'Δ-scalar' accelerated 'predatory vortices' or Δ^o 3-network Momentum balances. Many other unifications happen when we translate the confuse jargon of electromagnetism to the clearer Newton vortices >Poisson gradients >Einstein's EFE, which are as 'usual' a T=Δ=S symmetry; Newton sees the vortex in time, Poisson studies it as an Δ-i gradient of the 5th dimension and Einstein makes a 'detailed' still picture of it in Space.*

An immediate solution of dark matter and dark energy follows. Since dark matter is proportional to the radius of the galaxy exactly as the 'electrostatic' force within the radius of an atom or charged ball, we deduce it is caused by the galatom's G¥ant force between its nucleus and the strangelet halo. As dark energy is repulsive, exactly as ¥-forces between atoms, we deduce its cause is also G¥ant forces (the name we haven given to the ¥-radiation between Galatoms). Many other results follow.

RECAP. The scalar nature of the Universe is proved theoretically by the unification equation of charges and masses as vortices of 5D space time of two limiting scales of the Δ±i galatom. So if we substitute for the Earth-sun system we obtain G, (1st ever theoretical deduction) and if we substitute for the Bohr Radius and Proton Mass, we obtain k with a 10^{39} higher curvature value, the exact difference between both forces that solves its hierarchy problem. As curvature in space is symmetric to rotational speed in time, so it is symmetric to the attractive force of any vortex.

The unification equation of 2 similar - NOT equal - scales of physics can be cast in 4 basic Dimotion perspectives (as usual the entropic death dimotion is a complete different anti-view that is not coded or reflected):

Galaxies, (Galaxies≈Atoms) thus resolve the philosophical question on how many 5D scales exist; as we find enough self-similarity to 'run again' another game of fractal scales (not identical but self-similar as in a Mandelbrot fractal) both by quantitative and qualitative methods between the atom and the galaxy. A question that might be extended to the S≈T dualities of open, 'entropic strings' and closed 'cyclical informative strings', in a possible larger

Future vortex of Information

Δ±1: Gravitational scales: accelerated mass vortices

Δ-1: Quantum scales: charge vortices

Δ: Thermodynamic fractal eddy vortex

and smaller scale of microscopic strings and superstrings:

Ouroboros the Universal Snake, bites its tail on the string quantum and cosmological self-similar scales, as perceived from the human $\Delta\sigma$ mind. Philosophy of science would then argue that those scales are real, but part of its self-similarity is mental: that is, the loss of information in the perception of scales make humans extract the same information from the upper and lower $10^{\pm 30}$ scales.

What about the Hyperuniverse? We do not know what the infinite Universe even in its local region of galatoms looks like, though due to the expansion of space between galatoms, is likely an entropic gas of local atoms on the hyper-Universe. It is not though a big-bang Universe, because even if we run backwards the expansion of space between galatoms, the implosion of information in galaxies, counter that effect, so at best, we could say that running backwards the big-bang equation we shall meet a 'solid' crystal of galatoms.

The scalar unification of forces opens up an entire new field of physics, not quantum gravity, the description of cosmology with quantum laws, but fractal relativity, the description of the $\Delta-1$ quantum world as a similar scalar plane of space-time to the $\Delta+1$ cosmologic world.

THE GLUON-SCALE & THE \forall -HYPERELECTROMAGNETIC SCALES: ∞ SCALES? ARE WE UNIVERSES?

What about the unification of the other forces in scalar couples? It follows immediately when we consider them the scalar symmetry and similarity of the 5 Dimotions of the galaxy:

The Scalar similarity between the strong force and the gravitational force 'inside the atom-galaxy', both attractive 'only' and the outer force of the galaxy (repulsive gravitation aka dark energy) and the outer force of the atom (electromagnetic repulsive expansive forces) is immediate as it is the parallelism between magnetism and gravitomagnetism (Heaviside's discovery). While the weak force is NOT a force but the evolution of the families of particles between scales.

The key element of the galatom is the $st-j \approx ST+j$ mirror symmetry between the 'Dark Atom' (cbb, top matter decuplet) and the Galaxy. This only Maldacena Conjecture wondered when he realized a black hole (frozen black star, Einstein's name, let us send the fascist Wheeler who wanted to nuke all Japan in revenge for his bro dead on combat, and amended the master go back to hell) HAS in 5 Dimensions the homeomorphic topology of the \forall -light galaxy in 4D.

In the graph below the enormous beauty of the symmetry between the world of particles and galaxies.

5D makes the Universe ∞ , immortal and the big-bang an scalar phenomena *on the galactic quasar scale, as 'galatoms'* (galaxies have the same $5D=SxT$, co-invariant value that atoms) balance 2 Dimotional forces, St-gravitational information that collapses Ts-entropic vacuum space into matter ($St=Ts$), as it does in the atomic scale where expansive Ts-electromagnetism collapses into electronic nebulae within the atom and further on into non-lineal $\Delta-1$ St-strong forces equivalent to $\Delta+1$ St-gravitation. So the main symmetry of physics is between the galaxy, perhaps an atom of a hyper-universe – themes of metaphysics as we'll never have enough St-information of the whole ∞ cosmos: $P(\text{Truth}) < 1$.

In the graph we summarize the symmetries of forces between:

1) the internal cyclical strong force of the atom and the cyclical gravitational force of the galaxy, both with 2 regimes, the strong force/regime inside the nucleus, and the weak regime outside (nuclear force, Newtonian gravitation).

2) Then those forces no longer hold as we approach the 'strangelet' negative halo/electron of the galaxy/atom, with a 'lineal \forall -force', which becomes 'repulsive outside the galaxy. Hence the 'expansion of forces' between Galaxies (Hubble constant), which is the equivalent to repulsive \forall -forces, balanced by the 'implosion' of forces within 'Gravitational/Strong' galaxies. Hence the big-bang is false, as *both forces cancel each other as they do in the quantum scale, creating a wobbling, immortal Universe.*

The 2nd error of big-bang physics is mathematical. Since all points are -E fractal points that hold ∞ parallels within them, singularities do not exist, as 'point-particles' grow in size the closer we come to them becoming 'galaxies' – the cut off limit to backwards contraction of 'vacuum, entropic Tt-time' (NOT space=form, but v>c faster neutrino background, which becomes light – neutrino theory of light – when 'entering' the galaxy, 'warping' time into formal space and particles).

So besides improving the mathematical analysis of numerical=scalar, and topological=Non-Euclidean properties of matter 5D physics adds organic properties displayed by nature, better explained with causal words.

Since Max. P (truth)= Δ-scalar=organic + Spatial=topologic + temporal=Dimotion analysis of any system with Σlanguages. Thus 5D astrophysics adds a **Tt-entropic** analysis (Big bang quasars); an **§Π>St**-energetic & Informative analysis of the 'galacell' as an organism dedicated to reproduce 'ultradense quark stars' of positive top quarks & BCB dark atoms (formally black holes); & negative strangelets in its 'electronic membrane'=halo; an Δ±j Galatom Analysis to the classic analysis 4D, Ts study of the galaxy with Ss-mathematical languages. And defines the 5 forces of Nature (graph) as the 5 Dimotions of the Galatom, with its Δ±j scalar symmetries between Δ±j strong and gravitational forces; Δ±j, electromagnetic & dark energy while weak interaction is NOT a force but an evolutionary trans-form-ation of matter up & down Δ±j scales.

In Astro-physics we deal, in a complementary manner to the 'realist' one, on the scales of physical systems, **dealing with the models of scale, space, time, entropy and language** of 'human physics', very different from those of physical sciences, that is reality, since of all the non-social sciences of mankind, the most distorted one due to the idealism and uncertainty of perception of Δ±3,4 scales, is physics. We shall thus study physics as we do with all other supørganisms of the Universe, in scale, time, space, language=mind and its entropic limits, in 2 volumes, one dedicated to the larger Galactic superorganism and its symmetry with the particle scale, and one for the Geological Earth's superorganism, and its symmetry between its 'membrain' (surface of information) and its geological inner cycles.

So 1st we consider the St-gluon≈Meson as entropic food of the lback hole (e^{-x} Yukawa formalism), while V>c ¥ =dark energy 'burping' out of the black hole=top⁺⁺ star axis is seen as expanding intergalactic space. Inside the galatom non-lineal gravitational strong forces trap its vital energy (uds=us) with the stronger strangelet/electronic negative atom. Yet scales go beyond into infinity: Since gliuons are mesons, there is an added lower scale of ud 'gluionquarks' that might form stars in those micro-atoms which might be galsxies of a hypo-universe *that enlarge the game of existjence into new fractal levels*, all of us holding galaxies within. And vice versa. Those new ∃xi=stjences in the hypo and hyper-Universe, with self-similar forms in an atomic nuclei made of light quarks with an overall positive charge and a galactic black hole likely to be a swarm of top quark++ frozen stars . besides confirming (insteins expectations that a black hole should have a cut-off substance, a new type of 'atomic matter' of 'high density', becoming a 'frozen star', which the discovery of top quarks of similar density to black holes seem to prove; enlarges the 'game of Mass scales in its main species:

Δ-1 ud- gluons, Δ-0, ud-atoms, Δ-1, toplet quarks

While in the Ts-side a neutrino theory of light with v>c for neutrinos outside the galatom enlarges its scales to:

Δ-4: neutrinos: Δ-3, photons Δ-2: electrons,...Δ-1: electric fields, Δ+1: electric currents Δ+2: plasma stars

Whereas the index is somewhat subjective to the 'superorganism' we select. In the case of human life:

Δ-1: cells, Δº: physiological networks, Δ+1 world.

That puts man's perception as an M³: monad-mind-mirror of the Universe in the middle state NOT as ego-centered humans and anthropic physicists think, because it is the absolute centre of the Universe, but because there is a symmetry between Δ±1

ranges of informative perception for each Δ^0 being, both at 'real level' (galaxy and atom) and at theoretical level (Planck strings and cosmic strings, olved for a background independent Universe)...

So above neuronal human perception we grow upwards with the different 'orientation' of perception towards larger wholes, which changes to elliptic 'darkness'. And so we shall study first the human scales, with more detail (as the praxis of science must serve mankind): Δ^0 cell, $\Delta+1$ life (and its variations of inorganic $\Delta+1$ matter states and $\Delta+1$ human life), $\Delta+2$, the world level, of which we shall study its temporal equation and three relative subspecies: Past-life (Gaia and its life supœrganisms)<Present- (History, the supœrganism of mankind in time)> Future (company-mothers of machines and its worldstock networks of financial money), to finally enter in the higher scales of the Universe, $\Delta+3$ galaxies and its relative cells, stars systems; considering the $\Delta+4$, a 'philosophical', metaphysical scal, *as we do not have enough proofs and will never have due to the limits of perception of systems reduced to 9 scales of the whole...*

How much energy moves upwards in scales; how much 'entropy' $S=Q/T$ remains downwards? This concerns physicists in a childish manner, as they seek the maximal work for its engines. It concerns us here in a far deeper metaphysical way: 50-50%.

I love that sentence for personal reasons only for the initiated, cheer up Walter, we 'still exist' (: The logic behind it is obvious. If a system cedes to its 'social God', $\Delta+1$ more than 50% of its input, it will collapse, and start to reduce its populations. So the next time like the Schrodinger's cat whose chances to die increase 50% more each experiment, it will have less and the whole which would have fed and fattened will demand more. Collapse becomes then exponential, entropy-death sets to an e^{-x} rate if you are inclined to an exact equation. So it moves inversely after collapsing the parts, to a negative exponential decrease. Be warned parasites that exploit financially by anoxia mankind, the holocaust happens. A wiser 'farm' thus is one that takes only the 10% as neurons and top predators do from the trophic pyramid. Hierarchy has its limits. The law is essential to the Universe. Because each new scale will play that 50-50, hence it will keep diminish. In fact the 50-50 is an ideal that only happens in the first perceived scale, $E=C/B$; *the energy of the lower scale of informative humind's perception, electronic light rises a 50% from the magnetic and a 50% from the electric scales. It is a perfect 'Carnot engine', so to speak.*

Then all is a lesser form. As Hartree said, the electromagnetic world gives us more and more intelligently that we understand. We distinguish then 3 kind of scalar $\Delta\pm 1$ relationships: predator pyramids that take around 10% in Volterra curves; farms and organic symbiosis that take from 10 to 50%; and parasites that take more than 50% and collapse the system. Mr. Bloomberg, the biggest parasite alive in this planet today takes through its platforms from the 3rd world trillions to speculate in worthless internet companies, provoking the collective anoxia of billions of Africans, Indians from both continents... you name it. Inverted pyramids of parasitism, the trade-mark of capitalism are unstable reason why capitalism will kill Gaia and History in less than 400 years since the first steam engine a record compared to the 4 billion years of life it will end, *far faster than the exponential e^{-x} function whose rate of change equals its derivative and it is supposed to be the mathematical record.*

This tell us something: while building upwards to a maximal of 50% a new pyramid of existence, is slow and requires finesse, to destroy is fast, entropy in that sense, explicitly defined as $St_{0,1} \ll Tt_{1,-2}$ is the fastest process that happens in a single quantum of time. How can it be possible? So fast? The quasar big-bang (not cosmic big-bang), happens in 10^{-24} the average lifetime, a yoctosecond (10^{-24} s). Then the cosmological black hole, a top quark boson crystal dies and a hyper-inflationary stage of time happens in the real galactic big-bang.

RECAP. Because all systems made of scales of vital space that last a time cycle, they all have bio-topo-logic properties. So we need *always 3 scalar perspectives that give 3 symbiotic properties. In the galaxy we talk of:*

1. A scalar view that defines a galatom, by similarity of the atomic and galactic scale unified with 5D metric.
2. A Human view that defines the **galaxy**, our present single perspective with a single light spacetime continuum.
3. A Galactic view that defines a '**galacell**' that is the galaxy as an organism, controlled by 'DNA-like' black holes. So we can now study the galaxy as an organic system with its 5 Dimotional, organic networks of forces.

Haldane said, the universe is more complex and strange than humans can understand or even imagine. Yet its basics are simple – a property of fractals that by self-repetition and recombination originate from a simple Generator equation, infinite variations of the same theme: the scalar supœrganism.

Figure 24.11 (Example 24.3) A plot of E versus r for a uniformly charged insulating sphere. The electric field inside the sphere ($r < a$) varies linearly with r . The field outside the sphere ($r > a$) is the same as that of a point charge Q located at $r = 0$.

Δ-SCALES.:The galatom.

Let us try to systematize briefly the main themes of physical sciences according to the aforementioned pentalogic:

How many scales the Cosmos has? The model that agrees with data makes each galaxy an atom of a hyperuniverse.

What is dark matter & energy? The efficient Universe has few forms, repeated ad nauseam –so all life come from 1 cell, etc.: Dark matter seen in the BG ‘local galactic radiation’ should be made of a halo of strangelets, in harmony with the inner bcb atoms of black holes. They create an $\Delta\pm j$ symmetry between the 3 topological parts of the galaxy and its 3 quark families. Dark Energy is made of repulsive $G\forall$ ant-waves of neutrinos, repulsive gravitation, produced at faster than light speed in the ‘Penrose axis’ of Kerr black holes between galaxies, 2 scales that can we study separated.

Ω_Λ is the flat quantum potential field below the \forall -radiation likely a $v>c$ speed neutrino field, whose tiny mass matches the mystery of vacuum dark energy. Mesons are gluons of the next scale. Non-linear Gravitational forces are parallel to non-linear strong forces. Protons have a Schwarzschild radius, etc.

It is then an easy to compare the laws of Dark matter with those of a charged ball, itself homologous to a point particle, as in all those cases the attraction is lineal with the radius – one proof more of the mathematical equivalence in 5D between galaxies and atoms and a good way to conclude our study of the big-bang and start that of 5D Scalar physics:

We illustrate with 2 teasers from ‘electric theory’ the equivalences of $G\forall$ ant and \pm forces:

*Micro Galatom emitting dark energy from dark matter halo (: $G\forall$ ant force :)
In fig. 2 the exact ‘lineal graph’ of dark matter attraction that is also lineal to R:
 $M(r)=r$, from simple Newtonian physics: $F=ma =m v^2/r$
 $M G/r=v^2 \rightarrow v M (r) G/r =v$ (constant)*

The amount of mass in a sphere of radius R grows like R... Which is what would happen if we substitute by the Principle of equivalence the mass by the $G\forall$ ant Force in the Halo

Thus after we falsify the big-bang and establish the basic tenants of 5D, we will develop the main notions of the hyper-universe in which galaxies should be modeled with the laws of 5D subject to $G\forall$ ant electromagnetic forces outside the ‘galatom’ and gravitational forces similar to those of the strong force inside, *models of which there are abundant theories but NOT a general philosophy of the Universe in the past decades of physical work.*

In that regard if modern science were not IQless beyond mathematical models and humind’s egocy (ego=idiocy) so extreme, the symmetry of the ∞ large and small is the most pleasant philosophy of the Universe, as it can be explained in all languages – maths, organic models, sentient ‘monad-mirror’ models, even mystical ones, and we will use all languages. *(nt.1)*

Special relativity. Still particles and moving waves.

5D Special relativity reduces its postulates to the Δ -3 light scale, where constancy of light speed *as the vacuum background of the galaxy applies*, because particles entangle gravitational into still distance to emite information so the Lorentz contraction is just a human continuous perception of the still and go of particles that don’t have speed when emitting \forall .

We can get rid of Lorentz Transformations from the point of view of particles, even if from the human p.o.v. as in a movie, we see a continuous motion, when in detail to emit information light stops each frame. This explains from another ‘pentalogic’ point of view why the wave of the atom

does NOT radiate Ψ -energy (origin of Bohr's model): waves don't radiate just move.

Finally the twin paradox... implies processes of curved acceleration related to General relativity NOT to special relativity answering the question: Do acceleration and deceleration effects cancel down?

Because physicists only consider 1 scale and 1 time dimension they are obliged to model all those forces, with lineal concepts reducing them all forcefully into an exchange of lineal particles, when they are clearly different forces. For example the weak force that happens in a single point transforming a particle into one of a higher scale of larger masses, is represented with a gap that 'exchanges' the W-particle, NOT as Fermi shown first, an evolution of a higher particle into a heavier one, that then suffers an entropic process of dissolution in 3 parts.

Such 5D variety of forces makes possible the organic functions and structure of self-similar atoms and galaxies. So we couple forces according to their $\Delta \pm 1$ 'symmetry of scale' as 5 forces equivalent to the 5 dimensional motions, ab. Δi , of physical systems within galaxies. They must be studied in dualities, belonging to two different scales - the cosmological, $\Delta +1$ scale (gravitation & dark energy) and the $\Delta -1$ quantum scale (strong force and electromagnetism); whereas the dualities relate gravitation and strong forces and electromagnetism and dark energy; while a transformative, 'weak force' transforms particles between 5D scales.

Scalar Entropic Big-Bangs

Those conservation laws happen in all scales of reality including the cosmos as a whole so we must next annihilate one of the most retarded concepts mankind has devised in its metaphysical beliefs about reality since the 'worm theory' of the Ulkasha people (:Big bang falsification is simple, but more complex is the sociology of a people who can believe those egocentric theories, we treat in the first part along many accessory elements of that falsification. In essence in 5D a galaxy is similar to an atom. So its gravitational 'strong' force does NOT go beyond the central regime and as we move beyond the spiral arms we enter into an 'electrostatic field' that as all of them is proportional to the radius, *exactly as dark matter is. While outside the galatom the field is repulsive with a 'curved decelerating accelerating decelerating worldcycle' exactly as Ψ -rays are. We call this 'different force from gravitation' between galaxies, $G\Psi$ ant fields (from Giant, Galaxy Ψ -rays and repulsive Gravitation, as it should be obvious to the reader). Why 13.4 billion years away we no longer see galaxies is obvious: light as all systems of nature has a life-death worldcycle, beyond which it turns into a 'flat encephalogram' so to speak. That is, it scatters to the red beyond 1000 C. this is the black horizon and the proof it is the death of light NOT of the Universe, beyond the obvious fact we are measuring light, comes from the observance at those horizon limits of perfectly formed black hole galaxies. In fact the largest ones as they produce the more energetic 'ultraviolet(n)' Ψ -rays that live longer and reach us. There is no explanation to the perfectly formed giant galaxies on those horizons except the non-existence of a cosmic big bang. This is further proved by the $C/H=Distance$ horizon value, NOT a coincidence, but the obvious fact that Hubble is the measure of the aging rate of light. What causes light aging, obviously the fact all systems do. But for those who need an external 'tear and wear' cause, the isomorphic nature of the Universe provides a cause, as light travelling through it will suffer the red-shift of dark ultra-heavy matter at an isomorphic rate to its motion towards our galaxy. So the further a light source is the more gravitational red shift by ultra-heavy dark matter gravitational fields it will suffer (an effect of General relativity). Real photons' distance they can travel cannot exceed the optical horizon of the universe, of order 10^{26} m. If equal it to the Compton wavelength λ of the photon, the limit on its mass is $mc^2 < hc/\lambda \approx 10^{-32}$ eV. The *experimental* limit found from photons coming from the Small Magellanic Cloud, assuming equilibrium between its magnetic and gravitational fields is 10^{-27} eV*

In the fractal model a big-bang is the entropic death of physical matter. But the Universe is also scalar and it has information, a dimension of form, signified by the gravitational informative force, physicists ignore in their calculus of its expansion, happening in galaxies that balance the dark energy between them, we shall find both, balances of forces that make the Universe wobbling, and big-bangs and informative forces in multiple scales of the Universe, talking of multiple big-bangs balanced with big-crunches. So how we shall correct big-bang theory to fit into the fractal view of the Universe? We dedicate many pages on the articles of astrophysics to that matter but let us just give you a prime:

Right, when we add the gravitational force that warps 1D space into 3D mass in galactic vortices, they balance the expansion of 1D space in entropic vacuum as light dies into dark entropy lines between them. As mass warps 3 1D flat-vacuum into a 'high

volume' its 3 times more powerful in its warping, hence the 75-25% Balance of mass to dark entropy. Thus the fractal Universe is immortal. On the right its scales all suffer similar $e=mc$ dual processes of warping through gravitational forces of cyclic momentum that create those galaxies, and expansive big-bangs of lineal momentum balanced in combined cycles of energy - the 3 conserved quantities of each fractal spacetime physical organism, which put together give birth to the 3 conserved laws of nature the Big Bang totally ignores - among many other known-known laws.

So the use of a fractal space and cyclical time dimotions fully accounts for the immortal Universe and its balanced 3 dimotions of space-time, conserved in its infinite reactions; energy, information stored in the cycles and frequency of those systems of angular momentum, whose minimal constant form is h , and lineal speed, conserved in the constancy of light.

Why those obvious facts of SOUND physics are then 'reduced' to ænthropic creationist big-bangs in a single plane of space-time despite evidence? It is the ego paradox: what the big bang does for science is a religious 'closure' with man and its simplest mathematical lineal functions at its center, which added to the denial of organic sentient properties to physical reality allows to feel the high popes of science a sensation of absolute knowledge, as the religious person feels that all is known in the mystery of god - a word eerily similar to the lineal function of the big-bang ' $V=Hod$ '. Big bang cosmology ignores gravitational informative galaxies & dark matter & the scalar structure of the Universe reducing space-time to a single scale, and the cyclical nature of time, we correct the big-bang, which corresponds to the limit of a 5D theory of reality in a single light space-time continuum.

The big-bang entropy-only theory of the Universe dismisses galaxies, as they are NOT expanding. So running backwards in time Galaxies would expand the Universe and balance its vacuum contraction. Since when we add the gravitational force that warps 1D space into 3D mass in galactic vortices, they balance the expansion of 1D space in entropic vacuum as light dies into dark entropy lines between them. As mass warps 3 1D flat-vacuum into a 'high volume' its 3 times more powerful in its warping, hence the 75%-25% balance of mass to dark energy.

Thus the inverse dimotion of gravitational information compresses dark energy into matter and balances the dimotion of expansive space between galaxies, describing a fractal immortal Universe where a big-bang is merely the entropic dimotion of dissolution of matter guided by Einstein's equation in any scale: $E \leftrightarrow Mc^2$

In graphs, we resume the model of the fractal Universe in which each scale have similar big-bang deaths:

Scalar bangs that happen from Beta decays (right picture) that explodes nucleons into atoms, Nova that explode stars and maybe planets doing experimental big-bangs at home, to quasar black holes that give birth to new galaxies. All scales suffer similar $e=mc^2$ dual processes of warping through gravitational forces of cyclic momentum that create those galaxies, and expansive big-bangs of lineal momentum balanced in combined cycles of energy - the 3 conserved quantities of each fractal space-time physical organism, which put together give birth to the 3 conserved laws of nature, which present Big Bang theory ignore. Instead a fractal space and cyclical time dimotions fully accounts for the immortal Universe and its balanced 3 dimotions of space-time, conserved in its infinite reactions; energy, information stored in the cycles and frequency of those systems of angular momentum, whose minimal constant form is h , and lineal speed, conserved in c light constancy.

In the center we see a map of the Galaxy, which just recently showed to have two lobes similar to those of the first electronic orbital of a Hydrogen atom born in self-similar fashion in the quantum scale. In the left side we see the background radiation that is supposed to come from the Big Bang 13 billion years ago, but HAS in its center the exact 2 lobes recently found above the black star. This came as a surprise.

Above, the local explanation of the background radiation, which is a local measure, hence must and can be explained by local causes in the galaxy: any moon M.A.C.H.O., (Massive Cold Halo Object); that is, a quark nugget of heavy quark matter or a similar black hole that has eaten the mass of a moon will produce the exact same background radiation by gravitational red-shifting. Thus as moons are the commonest objects, we can talk of primordial black holes and/or strangelets as the local, 'present' cause of the radiation. Since epistemology always favors a local 'present' solution far more sound experimentally than

a 'derivation' from a non-measured experimental past in a non-measured larger region (the cosmic big-bang whose temperature 'comes from the past', reduced by a lineal equation and is extended hyperbolically to the non-measured entire Universe), it follows the fractal big-bang, is sounder. So what physicists call the cosmic big-bang likely does not exist, as the limit of scalar big-bangs we soundly measure are quasar big-bang.

Finally French astronomers tabulated for them a 15–20 billion year cycle which explodes central black holes, explaining the hyper-abundance of Helium in the center of galaxies. So a galaxy has a 15 billion years cycle in an older immortal Universe, since the dimotion of information that shrink energy into mass in galaxies balances the entropic 'cosmic electromagnetic' repulsion of dark energy. Interesting enough if we reduce a quasar big-bang of 15 billion years, with 5D metric, accelerating its time clocks as we reduce size in space: $\$ \times \delta = K$, it reduces 15 billion years to 15 minutes (: the exact duration of a beta-decay neutron Big Bang).

We falsify the cosmic bang with experimental & epistemologic known proofs distorted by cultural reasons that make it a pseudo-religious dogma of the worldly religion of physics – to make entropic weapons in a military society- and the western creationist religion of most founding fathers of physics, with its lineal Abrahamic time views & anthropic beliefs of man at the center of reality reflected in the lineal, created out of nothing cosmos.

Cosmic vs. Quasar big-bangs

$E \Leftrightarrow M$ (whereas c is the constant of speed of each Universal scale, c for the galaxy, not necessary so for other scales) is dual and there are scalar big-bangs from beta decay to quasars and maybe beyond is certain. So the question we want to find out is which of the two larger scales of big-bangs, that of a quasar big-bang or a cosmic big-bang fits better real data. Since as we can see in the images above, on the right, they are similar in form.

Te play ball with cosmologists we could justify the big-bang in 5D since if we accept our limit of light perception as the limit of the Universe (cosmic horizon); then the $\rightarrow = @ = S = T = \Delta$ symmetries between spatial range, time aging and scalar density of populations all fit within the 'magic number' of 10^{11} elements for most super organisms of reality. So the symmetry also happens in the 'limited perception' of the cosmos:

Most galaxies have 10^{11} stars. The total mass of all the stars in the Milky Way is estimated to be between 4.6×10^{10} and 6.43×10^{10} sun masses. And the Universe is considered to have around $1.6 \cdot 10^{11}$ galaxies.

So we could say that the galaxy is just a scale below the big-bang (a huge galactic molecule so to speak), as the neutron star is just a scale above the neutron (a huge neutron molecule so to speak). And that it exploded in a big bang of the next scale of the universe. But that is just the astounding beauty of pentalogic, where the 5 Dimotions/elements of reality are in balance. So for the limits of our entropic perception ($\rightarrow = @$), we observe similar quantitative and qualitative limits for S-patial population, T-ages within our Δ -scales. But a more profound understanding of those limits considers that the local perception of a few galatoms is just a very reduced quantity of the whole number of galatoms of the next hyperscale of the Universe that should be of zillions of them, and all of them living as Protons and black holes without evaporation do an immortal time.

The immortality of the Universe indeed becomes evident as Protons are immortal and black holes are also immortal without evaporation, once we put properly in place the dimotion of time of Hawking's awesomely beautiful equation as those of the birth of a black hole into its gargantuan future, NOT of its entropic death=evaporation to the past.

$\Delta+1$: The quasar big-bang galactic cycle

The life-death cycle of the central black hole of Galaxies that explodes into quasars and forms back its bar, follows the same ages of the big-bang. As all of them after the initial 'Planck epoch - of gravitational superluminal waves', dark epoch of nucleosynthesis, are ages 'within galaxies', and so they are proved for the inner space of galaxies. They do NOT explain many other features of the Universe as a whole (which is not isomorphic, etc.) but perfectly describe the evolution and formation of the stars of the galaxy.

So the big-bangs ages are properly the ages of the galaxy; without all the 'ad hoc' theories and pseudo-scientific models required to explain why the large scale universe has nothing to do with the supposedly smooth result of a cosmic big-bang (this

is like Ptolemy constant recurrence to 'new' ad hoc epicycles to make fit new observations into its earth-centric theory of the universe). Trust me, any astronomer knows how long this 'list' is.

Thus the quasar big-bang follows further the laws of truth (minimalism: Occam's razor), simplicity and correspondence. We do not need to postulate strange forms of dark energy and dark matter, except the ones known, repulsive gravitation (to account for the entropic expansion of space between galaxies that balances its contraction), which is 'natural' to the model of galactic-atoms; and quark matter to account for the dark matter of the halo.

In the graph the 'big-bang' properties local to the galaxy can be explained by the quasar cycle of our galaxy.

So as always times proves the sound, humble, rational scientists right. In this case Einstein's steady state solution, which Fred Hoyle developed in a huge mathematical effort just before dying in his theory of multiple quasar big-bangs, which the cycle of galaxies found by the French astronomers further proved and my calculus of Moon MACHOs radiation, which any student of physics can easily corroborate properly explains.

Galaxies' quasar longer 20 billion cycle falsify the supposed age of the big-bang. As many of the recently discovered astronomical phenomena in far away galaxies show. Since we are finding formed galaxies, formed giant black holes, formed II generation stars and star dust, which could not have been born before the big-bang.

So do those supposed 'lobes' of the cosmic big-bang, which Smolin a famed physicist wanted to use to prove his theory that high frequency light goes faster than red-shifted light, as they were supposed to come from 13 billion years ago and so a small difference of distance should be found. Alas, the surprise when they found they are the exact 'trace' of the 2 lobes of electromagnetic radiation found in OUR galaxy. Yet they occupy supposedly 'a huge piece of the entire Universe...

We put a few experimental proofs of recent astronomy to add to the enormous number of planets found all over the place, which reinforce the Fermi paradox, so you don't think I am here making a case only for theory, only for my work in the 2 dimotions of time. So why nothing of this comes in 'daily press'? For all the wrong reasons - religions are always respected; masses always side together for them. As Schopenhauer said: 'the wise always say the same, the fools, which are majority do exactly the opposite'. And attack ad hominem the wise... In the steady state theory things became soon ad hominem against Hoyle who quipped back inventing the mocking term of 'big-bang theory'.

In 2nd graph we see local $E=Mc^2$ big-bang destructions of mass, all of which have an inverse temporal, informative, process of much slower creation of temporal information and mass that balances them, in different scales of physical systems, from the beta decay that explodes atoms into electrons and protons (with an inverse slow collapse of electrons into atoms) to the quasar big-bang of galaxies (with an slow process of creation of mass-information from gaseous space):

If we consider space-time an absolute continuum in a single scale, this more accurate picture of what we perceive is not possible, hence we come to the conclusion of present cosmology - that the Universe will expand and die. If we consider that galaxies, which follow Einstein's dictum, compensate this expansion: 'Time curves space into mass', Mr. Hogg's conundrum - how to correct the big-bang is solved. *Experimental facts tell us we must accept the fractal informative structure of reality, where the big bang is merely the death-rebirth cycle of a quasar-like galaxy or local Universe, a scale of size above galaxies. So both together create an immortal Universe.* Since in Philosophy of Science we must never deny experimental evidence, even if at first sight it contradicts an established theory.

Cosmology has a metaphysical component as it is well beyond the limits of human perception, which we find to be the atom and the galaxy, beyond and within uncertainty and dark gravitational matter makes knowledge to say the 'least' incomplete.

Thus contrary to belief big-bang theories of the Universe and Cosmology in the widest sense do not belong to astro-physics, but

still we can do science if we are minimally serious with the scientific method.

If the cosmic big-bang had sound experimental data, of course, we would accept it. As it does NOT contradict 5D physics. It would just validate a larger scale worldcycle. So we are NOT against cosmic big-bang because 5D physics does not tolerate it but because plain good old' science disproves it. The scalar big-bang death processes of matter in all planes, from beta decay to galaxies is one of the strongest proofs of the isomorphic nature of all scales. But the cosmic one is not proved. So since all big-bangs are mimetic we reduces the scale of the big-bang to a quasar scale, making Einstein's EFE, local field equations for the Light-space time of the galaxy (reason why c is constant).

The graph of SCiAM shows the full quasar cycle is longer than the big-bang cycle and we have found *galaxies in all its stages*. Thus by 'reductio ad absurdum', since we have found galaxies in a 'second' quasar cycle, hence over 20 billion years as 'reborn' galaxies, forming its central bar, there is no way the time age of the whole is shorter than the time of its parts.

Scalar space-times imply the existence of multiple bangs with different size and speeds, all entropic deaths of informative masses or charges that uncoil its accelerated vortex into radiation following Einstein's equation, $E=Mc^2$, where a bi- or tridimensional vortex (M or e^-) becomes extended into a plane of radiation (hence the square of lineal c -speed). Yet for each different scale the parameters of speed (c), mass (M) and Entropy will change. And so we obtain a series of self-similar big bangs described in the first graph. What went wrong? *A priori properties of space, which is scalar, time which is cyclical with more arrows than entropy, and simplified mathematics as the 5th Non-E postulate defines 'fractal points with volume', hence cut-off limits to the backwards equation of Hubble, which are precisely gravitational galaxies that don't expand.*

The single cosmic big bang based in a single space-time continuum, was devised even before we knew the existence of a faster than light, membrane of dark Entropy and dark, quark matter. So we define it a scale of big-bangs as the cosmic *big-bang as a quasar bang of a top BCB hole spread on a c -light + gravitational dual spacetime membrane over an $v>c$ neutrino faster background membrane; certainly NOT the theoretical faster, larger possible big-bang at the Planck scale of lambda-strings.*

The cosmic big bang as a dual process, with an inflationary age (the string scale; ignored so far in 5D) thus reduces to a slower age of a yocto-sencod (the quasar bang of Top BCB holes in electromagnetic space, created over the gravitational membrane).

The nature of the galactic bang recently received a boost from astrophysics, as we have discovered that most of the stars of the galaxy formed in the 'electronic nebulae' during the initial 1 billion years. We study in many other articles the whole 'organic cyclical theory' of quasar big-bangs, whose first mathematical expressions were considered by Hoyle – the old proponent of a steady state Universe, anathema of the Big-bang 'religion'. It came this years 2019 as a surprise that the 'galatom' is mostly static – that is, once the electron nebulae is formed there is hardly any new formation of 'star-points' on the erlectronic nebulae. And when this happen takes place with enormous violence and synchronicity, as it happens in an atom, when there is a capture of an electron by the nuclei. Moreover the atom suffers a constant spiral torsion on the 'trajectory of the electron nebulae around its central proton hole, as it is the case recently found in the spiral torsion of galaxies. 5D future astrophysicists will find an enormous field of similarities comparing atoms and galaxies – already they use photonic models to study the central region of stars.

Languages are important in 5D but NOT the only dimotion of creation, and they must be evolved as huminds don't even define properly the Units of all maths, the S-fractal point & its Δ -scalar societies, numbers, related by 5 Algebraic dimotional operands of which $\int \partial$ are the most precise. So the reader is encouraged to study also 5D math.

The big-bang error as a theory of the Universe is firmly entrenched in two errors of simplified mathematics (Euclidean points) and logic (a single arrow of entropy=death as the dimotion of the Universe). So we briefly will introduce those corrections to explain why not only in praxis and data but also in theory and language the big bang is not even wrong.

We study the bigbang and falsify it in more detail, in the introductory part of the paper on the galatom. As this paper is dedicated to the more mundane physics of our planet, and its simpler mathematical structures.

The dirty little secret is that there are so many proofs against the big-bang. that the only reason astrophysicists don't abandon it is routine and lack of 'imagination' – the capacity of the mind to pursuit a new avenue of reason. Frankly for long I didn't

understood that attitude, as the more coherent model of the Universe – that of 5D scales which are similar in the ‘atomic’ and galactic scale fascinated me. With time as I expanded 5D beyond mathematics where it started first (with the discovery of the fractal ‘finitesimal points’) and Physics where it landed next, all the way to social sciences, where it entertained me for longer, given the ‘higher survival stakes’ at play, I understood that it was NOT my fault, but the natural shortcomings of huminds, and scholars were not different. So while we will quip often on those shortcomings mostly of ‘egocy’ – don’t take them personal. Fact is the Universe is simple once egocy – the belief humans are the only intelligent beings, our scale is the most important, our mind perceives all what exists, etc. are cast away. The 5D model then comes as natural. Galaxies are similar to ‘anti-atoms’ but the distortions experienced when perceiving through scales, make that question ‘relative’, regarding the similarity. What is obvious in any case is that *gravitational forces do NOT hold beyond the ‘galatom’, as strong nuclear forces do NOT hold beyond the nucleus. So we are in a lineal regime of hyper-electromagnetism, in the hyper-Universe and that explains it all. Gravitation in fact starts to ‘fade away’ as we move to the Halo of galaxies, where it becomes ‘steady’ because we are moving to a lineal force. No rocket science.* One though has to embrace the model and then everything fits on it. And professional physicists can do what I haven’t done since my youth – the maths of it. I found it tedious, but the procedures are straight forward and many practitioners have done patches here and there. There are works that show in different degrees of sophistication the equivalence between black holes and protons, electrons and galactic nebulae, photons and stars...

Dark matter redshift $HD=c$ as the light timelife and our spatial limit of perception NOT of the cosmos

More seriously the falsification of the big-bang comes from so many sides that is overwhelming. Take 2 simple ones. General relativity predicts that time runs slower in a strong gravitational field. So, radiation frequencies are *redshifted*. And since the Universe is homogenous, ultra-heavy *dark matter constantly red shifts light as it crosses through space. And the effect is lineal with distance. The further away, the more dark matter light meets, the more is red-shifted.*

Light waves must be analyzed differently from sound, because light waves require no medium of propagation and no method exists of distinguishing the motion of the light source from the motion of the observer. Thus, we expect to find a different formula for the Doppler shift of light waves. Physicists then undo all its principles, ‘excited’ by their new mathematical tools of relativity and calculate proper time, substitute it out of the blues for frequencies and get a result that *let the observer measure the speed of the source, contradicting relativity. The key then is just to keep without substitution, proper time as the time-life of the light that comes to us, and do not translate it into speeds via frequencies. For those without the technical of those processes. To keep it simple. 1) Physicists calculating big-bang speeds contradict relativity: you cannot measure the speed of the source. 2) If we maintain the equations in proper time we just calculate the lifetime of light NOT the expansion of the Universe and hence its contraction backwards to an age of death. 3) When light reaches its final lifetime is because its frequency ‘elongates’ to infinity and cannot longer send ‘information’. So that is the black out horizon of our perception of the Universe. How can we prove we are right and it is not the age of the Universe? 2 simple proofs.*

1) When we look at objects that send us light from the black out horizon of light scattering they ARE perfectly formed. IN FACT the largest black holes known come from that horizon (as they send the most ‘blue-shifted frequency light’ that will live longer.

2) Because H, the Hubble constant, is just a ‘gauge constant for the light aging’, $HD=c$ gives us the age of life of light, where D is distance. SO at $D=c/H$ light blacks out, dies away, as light scatters into an infrared and we no longer see: no older light comes rto us. This in $S=T$ symmetry means 13.4 billion years space=time. So H is not the Hubble constant of space expansion and time life of the Universe but of frequency expansion and time life of light (how this life equation of space-time light became the equation of the space-time size-life of the Universe is a mystery to me - nowhere we see o nit any ‘term’ for $U(t)$ or $U(s)$:)

It is the life of c, light and its reach in space. Thus we have a nice equation about the life of light. And then we have the proof in the Universe, when we look at the distance of that time life we see light dying!!, scattering at 1000 z ! what else you need to understand that $S=T$, H is the life of light, c its speed-distance, both coincide, both are seen at distance-time. Point. But as Astronomers decided it was NOT the life of light but of the Universe now they have a weird $S=T$ symmetry equation: $T(U) = S\odot$; that is the time life of the Universe coincides with the light Distance. It is all solved when you make Hubble only about light.

The neutrino theory of light. The range of light life forces. The background of dark energy.

What is then H is immediate. It is the frequency measure that appears on the equations of ranges of forces to define the range of light, with only an unknown parameter which is the 'mass' of light, that is, of the photon at rest, which physicists speculate to be immensely small (so light can be deviated by gravitational black holes) and indeed, substituting in the equations of range of forces, as light is not infinite – there is no infinity in reality but just ∞ , partial infinities and 0ϵ , finitesimals. So another way to find the mass of a photon, is to equal the law of range and the law of hubble to get the approximate mass of the lightest longest frequency wave near scattering: $HD=c$ $D=c/H=ct=\hbar/mc$; $H=1/T=f \rightarrow M=\hbar/Dc = \pm 10^{-70}$ kg, which is truly a finitesimal mass for light *that becomes a Neutrino hyperluminal background at the cosmic horizon at 1000 c. splitting into its 2 neutrino components. So far we had done along those pages a trilogic calculation of the Neutrino background: it matches the dark energy mystery. It is responsible of the cosmic horizon limit of light as the tug-of-war of neutrino wanting to go faster than c is resolved with the \forall -frequency stretching. And we calculated it from Hubble and from the ' \forall -ray range of force'.*

As a neutrino has less energy the faster it moves, neutrinos of maximal mass-energy are on the c-speed verge stuck in our light space-time galactic background. After 30 years of my only attempts to publish at physical review a dark energy theory of neutrinos, a century after Broglie's neutrino theory of light I see many articles since the Opera measures on hyperluminal neutrinos with sound physics. It IS the only 5D coherent theory and that is what matters here: we know NO other particle. So as Einstein put it, physics is concerned with facts and entities we know experimentally to exist. We have a sound theory from one of the 2 intuitive masters of XX c. physics (Schrodinger and Landau come next; Dirac deserves a spot for its mathematical beauty, Planck is the pioneer there you have the '5'). What is NOT sound physics and morally wrong, we have already discussed in the introduction to baby black holes and the quintaessential XXI c. man-scientist, an evil child without survival instincts, creationist mathematician, subjective, thinking he is God and can invent the $SxT|s=t$ balances of the Universe... We'll get back to it. We stress here again Occam's razor. As long as no other particle is found in the enormous numbers of Neutrinos, with the properties of neutrinos, no other candidate is worthy to study, but we do have neutrinos so why to seek for something else? So why does not happen? The incomprehension of \pm symbols (see $\text{-}\forall$ gebra) and the spin question. A graviton should be 2, a neutrino is $\pm 1/2$ which add when send in parallel opposite directions but two fermions to give us the 1-light spin. The solution? Ok I told not to put it, but I will. The $G\forall$ ant waves of neutrinos are NOT attractive but repulsive gravitation. 2 of those neutrinos do NOT attract but create repulsive \forall -rays, responsible for the \pm charge. For attractive gravitons you will need thus 4 of those, or a method to 'curve' them to make a membrane, which enclose all other forces including light. So it is a bit more complex.

RECAP. Where is the Universe age $U(t) \approx a(t)$ it in there? How they dare to plug in the life of the Universe? Now this coincidence is so impossible in terms of Universal life duration that is part of the 'intense debate' over the anthropic Principle of Christian-Jewish big-bang true 'subconscious foundations' (call it 'creationism' or 'Intelligent Design'): all those weird coincidences, such as that we see $\Delta \pm j$ scales with us at the center ARE because God designed the Universe for us to be here now at its center (the Earth is not yet flat and at the center by this big-bang negationists, but soon you will hear all is 'relative' and God created 'relativity' for us to 'feel' at the center, even if some problems with mass was making it difficult in reality.

We advance 2 hypothesis: the electronic wave *outside the galaxy is the dark matter vs. the electronic wave is the star nebulae. What is the star nebulae? The inner gluon world or the outer electron? There are elements that work for both hypothesis, but generally speak of the electronic nebulae as that of the galaxy's stars. Or rather the 'first Bohr radius' and S1,2 arms.*

We easily falsify the big-bang, which conveniently forgot those 'mass vortices' that do not expand but implode information balancing the giant \forall -dark energy of vacuum space in an immortal Universe the fun comes studying the 5 dimotions=forces & energy scales of the galatom *as part of its vital game of existence.*

CONCLUSION: THE NEED FOR A DIFFERENT VIEW OF DIMENSIONS AND MOTIONS.

All is time=motion... But only minds of virtual mental space can order it.

For most people space is a volume but to measure it, a volume must have walls – a membrane that encloses it, hence a ‘form’. And that form must be seen-measured ‘simultaneously’. So in relationship to Time, space is a ‘present state’. Time=motion thus is a more fundamental parameter as space in terms of time is a present slice, and we could consider the perception of form, subjective to the capacity of a mind to ‘map’ reality in its ‘still focus of perception to create an image’ of space.

Motion in its purest nature, and fastest speed as a line is unperceivable. It must have some form on it. And as there are only 3 topological forms, |, O and \emptyset , the combination of time and space, according to quantity (T for dominant Time, S for dominant space), and shape, |, O, \emptyset are limited. Moreover in a relative Universe where perception matters, | is the fastest motion, and so we can associate it to lineal time, O is the lesser motion as it might be seen as a form, which I what we see in fact in charges and masses, and so O tends to be associated to Space and information, heads and particles, and \emptyset , which combine both tends to be associated to space-time – waves and bodies. So the easiest way to go, in conjunction with the common wisdom of people is to say that time is lineal |-time, space is cyclical, O-information and space-time is hyperbolic, \emptyset .

So while all is time-motion and ultimately entropy, the *Universe holds infinite cyclical points that try to stop motion into form, and so a constant tug of war between Ss(languages) vs. Tt(Entropic motions) takes place. Languages create virtual ‘monads’ that stop in the stillness of a mind-mapping, the motions of the Universe through the simultaneous measuring in a mirror image of those motions of reality. That is the essence of S=T paradoxes: Minds exist but they are virtual, finitesimal 0ϵ -mirrors (an infinitesimal has always a non-E volume) in which a language stops reality and then, it projects over that reality the mind-mirror, bending motions and creating at larger scale replicas of its mind-mapping. So while all is motion, the ‘reproduction’ of forms, through the mind-languages of all the monad-points of the Universe, charges and masses in physical space, is the ‘intelligence of reality’ that denies the domain of entropic motion as the only arrow of existjence. But physicists use of Euclidean points with no volume don’t understand those fractal points, monads, charges and masses that store the information, the form of the Universe in the frequency and form of its cycles. So they biased time into the Tt-ts side of reality, entropy and locomotions, which indeed physicists study as $V=s/t$, and smallish space, which we see as rotary cycles. As in each sub-discipline of stience, which studies one of the scales of the fifth dimension Ss- virtual minds trans-form Tt-entropy through intermediate Ts-locomotion, $\S\Upsilon\Upsilon$ -Momentum and St-informative states, creating mental space and territorial order.*

In all those systems we can calculate a $ds^2=dt^2$, which is ‘similar’, but not quite and in an advanced courses of 5D focused in the formal technics derives from the postulate of absolute relativity: $S\leq T\leq\Delta\geq 0\epsilon$

How the Universe looks in a single scale? It seems to be ‘curved’. So astronomers measuring objects in far away distances see angles slightly ‘curved’. If so the Universe is in its space-metric flat, in its time metric a spherical worldcycle embedded in its largest 5th dimension, which is scalar hyperbolic. So everybody is happy. The flat man can see just Cartesian space; the Relativist 4D True time and the entangled soul a 5D hyperbolic world (:

When you look at simplified 2D systems, they appear Cartesian bidimensional systems embedded in a 3D Geometry. This is how you see the world with your bidimensional eye-sight. But this embedding turns out to be into a curved geometry – the surface of the Earth, and *in 4D either in the formalism of true time, or in the more sophisticated view of Absolute relativity based in the $S=T=\Delta$ symmetry, is a ‘curved’ fractal world of spherical worldcycles, with a ‘seed’ polar point that enlarges through the worldcycle to collapse in the point of death.*

And then this 4D world is embedded in a 5D hyperbolic geometry, of scalar ‘clone’ worlds from our 0ϵ point to infinity; because its hyperbolic geometry includes the nested spherical geometry that includes the 2D geometry of our flat view of the Earth. And there are NO more geometries; but mathematicians failed for a century to see what they wrote as the real Universe.

While it is possible to develop a classic view of the 5th dimension as the hyperbolic geometry in which the 4D Minkowski’s spacetime is embedded, in which our flat bidimensional Cartesian view is embedded, this ‘human view’ of the Universe is NOT quite write because it is still based in Newtonian, Absolute space-time, despite the fact every physicist that knows something about its discipline will recognize that since Einstein and quantum physics, absolute space-time is wrong and so again the only

alternative possible is Leibniz's relational space-time. We are NOT in an abstract Cartesian plane, drawn by God (and Newton his prophet, to whom he sent according to 'revelations' he wrote mystically on the margins, comets to enlighten his gravitational equations,) but in the only alternative model: we are MADE of vital spatial-forms and temporal motions. As in the case of the embedded 5D only 3 topologies of space-time, there are NO other possible models. So it is NOT a question of 'belief' or 'theory'. It is either 'heads or tails' and since heads: absolute space-time is false, it is tails: Leibniz relational space-time. Either you consider that truths in science have to be reasoned and accepted or you don't. We know dimensions are embedded in higher dimensional systems and follow a 3 hierarchy, $S(\text{flat Cartesian space}) \leq 4D \text{ time geometry} \leq 5D \text{ scalar hyperbolic geometry}$. And then we have False Absolute Space time vs. True relational spacetime. Then we have Einstein's quip: 'Leibniz is right, there are infinite clocks of time in the Universe, but if so we have to start science from scratch'. So he couldn't do it. But we can and we shall do it in those papers and apply the laws of what we are vital space and cyclical time to every science, species, event and law and show you all are entangled, all are one.

In the metric of 5D hyperbolic worlds, space and time are the local, fractal substances of each of those Escher's demons and angels. This is far more convenient than the 'global geometry' of those metric equations, because a world of relational space-time is discontinuous as you can observe around you. Are you, as a vital space-time being pegged to all other 'angels and demons'? No. You are a broken space-time piece with your own cyclical time clocks – circadian clocks and your own vital space '3 topologies' with parts that are spherical, notably your informative head, parts that are hyperbolic notably your hour glass-body and parts that are lineal and flat, your limbs. So we shall build from scratch a metric for the local vital space-time hyperbolic $S \approx T \approx \Delta$ organisms of the Universe.

As Einstein said 'God integrates empirically', converting forces into momentum into energy as space-time physical organisms juggle around scales, and change form from fields to momenta to energy storage. The job requires then in equal footing to take mathematical equations and relate them to spacetime properties. And further on entangle those equations and properties with the isomorphic laws of the whole Universe.

How we proceed with those embedded Universes is very much based in the $S=T$ duality Galileo didn't understand. And it is at the core of all the marvels of mathematical physics and its methods. Essentially if we add the 3rd symmetry we just discovered with a scalar hyperbolic world Euclidean S-space \leq cyclical Time worlds $\leq \Delta$ -Hyperbolic universes

What this means is that Space is smaller than time, you can consider flat space a slice of a time world, as time ultimately always curves in a worldcycle. This is an essential paradox of reality. As we move in our flat space we think to be free and make small 'differential steps' but at the end, alas, all becomes a Lagrangian zero-sum and a worldcycle is closed. And it is closed as a travel through 3 hyperbolic scales of the 5th dimension. Moreover because each geometry is embedded in the next one, $S=T$, as S is a small step of the flow of a worldcycle of time, but the inverse is not truth. T is richer in meanings than S. And the same happens with the 5th dimension of hyperbolic geometry. It is richer in meanings as a block of time of all possible worldcycles. So there is a hierarchy besides an equality. So we should write $S \leq T \leq \Delta$, but in terms of 'curving', with the symbols of Existential algebra, $S > T$ (S implodes formally into T) and $T > \Delta$ (Time worldcycles implode downwards into smaller hyperbolic scales). So those are paradoxes and there is no way around them but changing your mind from dogma of truth to paradoxical and thrive with those contradictions which many people cannot do.

Physical systems switch from Energy x Time = wave motion to particle form, Momentum x Space, to scale (angular momentum). So the symmetry of $T \Delta$ in physics is immediate. Those higher spheres can be seen NOT as spatial forms only but as forms moving through a higher dimensional world. So if we move a 3D sphere through a flat plane the cuts are then in the flat plane 'mirror images' of the larger sphere. If you are a 2D flat human, you will NOT need to see the 3D sphere to know it exists if the sphere has 'motion' and its 3rd dimension is perceived as the motion growth of a disk that will grow and then shrinks. This allow you to have a feeling in the other image for what would be to see a 5D hyperbolic Universe in your 4D space-time world: you would see the 4D rotating sphere also shrinking and growing in scales and that is the 5D hyperbolic sense you get in your 4D and you know is real because when you look through microscopes you see things multiplying and becoming smaller.

The 5th dimension has vital organic properties, which mathematics as all languages-mirrors of reality simplifies. This is obvious when considering the 'global' metrics of hyperbolic geometry with its simplification of an isomorphic Universe and its strict

symmetry. However mathematics is a great model for the ideal Universe, and its translation into vital interpretations is what truly enlightens reality. As we are made of topological space, it is easy just to compare mathematical structures with reality, providing we ignored the 'pedantic', dogmatic axiomatic method of referring mathematics NOT to reality but to the 'Imagination' of Idealist Germans from the XIX c. (Hilbert & Cantor) who imposed the false dictatorship of their imagination as the god-like origin of mathematics. So Cantor invented sets and Hilbert said 'I imagine points, lines and planes'. And voila! the ever so arrogant Germans that brought us other idol-ogies called Nazism and Communism brought us 'Cantor's paradises' where mathematicians away from reality reside.

This means the Hyperbolic 5th dimension with its embedded 4D time worldcycles perceived by our eyes in 2D flat Cartesian space, and its fractal points NOT sets NOT Hilbert's imagination is the origin of reality. It surprises me that modern mathematicians don't create life model statues of Mr. Hilbert's brain to worship before they come to the desk (: More seriously, the global hyperbolic plane has a feature that is the key to understand our world: it is a fractal that becomes local, and it is embedded in a 0-1 circle, because the hyperbolic function $e^{-e^{-x}}/2$ loses meaning soon past the 1, as e^{-x} becomes exceedingly enormous.

What this tells us beyond the idealization is that contrary to its use by Cosmologists trying to look at the infinitely large, it is *only worthy for the inner hyperbolic world of a system which must be considered in its 'external membrane' as a 0-1 sphere (with the topological skin enclosing a spherical variety). This is further stressed by the fact this geometry goes from 0 to infinity but DOES not come back as the worldcycle of time 'geometry' of 4D (both in the Minkowski's formalism that we shall repeat ad nauseam, we do NOT use because Einstein beyond quipping that Leibniz was right did NOT do his homework and started science from scratch with a relational model of space-time as we do).*

A question left on the conservation of energy is how many scales we need? Obviously 3: those that die and those that live. But because *the Universe is discontinuous according to the mental perception of scales and the cat alleys and dark worlds not perceived, the frequencies not heard, the times we do not perform a dimotion – the hours we don't enter the diner, the bedroom, the vagina, you name it... those 3 scales can be so huge as those of the galaxy and even beyond or very close to each other. The same goes from the ideal mathematical model of existential algebra. We can then consider the mathematical structure of 'Z numbers', 'Q' numbers and finitesimal-real numbers – all others, as the 3 scales. What choices we make then can be rephrased in terms of the 'scale' of the Q-denominator, which becomes the essential parameter between the Z-wholes and the Q-finitesimals of those wholes, with all other scales above and beyond in the 0ϵ Real world.*

New physics. Life starts in particles. Galaxies are organisms. The 5th dimension of scales organizes 3 conserved parts

*But this is 'the beginning', which Einstein did not do. As such the reader should be sympathetic to the problems natural to a 1st model ('The Nature of Scientific revolutions' Kuhn), which will be less accurate than an old model that has added 'ad hoc' corrections to its erroneous principles and a lot of detail, since as time goes by and the pioneer work is revised, enhanced, improved and adds details, to start from better simpler principles will make it flourish and pass well beyond the 'exhausted paradigm'. Those sounder principles are the reason scholars and physicists should pay attention to this paper, instead of following Planck's sanguine dictum that a new paradigm of science is not imposed by reason, but by the death of old scholars, so new students can learn afresh. It is a given but NOT a valid reason to ignore the paper, the lack of quality in the writing in terms of scholarship in physics, verbosity, detailed data, even English grammar, as neither pioneers are outside academia and don't have the resources to make up 'Chicago style, computerized models'; nor the imprecision of some results, as models have glitches in its inception. Copernicus model was slightly off track, because Earth traces a quasi-circle, with elliptic form and so its results were of less quality than Ptolemy with ad hoc epicycles. But it was the only path of future for science as the ptolemaic model was exhausted. And 5D is also the only path of r=evolution towards the future for all sciences, beyond the unlimited growth of detailed data, provided by the evolution of sensorial machines. The person who wrote it and his circumstances are also accessory and should not weigh against the model, the more so when he is in the 3rd st-age of life and won't be around much longer. I only apologize for – **entropic** quips against Physic(ist)s Planck style, which might sprout out of nothing from **Time** to **Space** like the cosmic big-bang (: As I likely won't have the **@-mind** left to correct them; please don't take it personally): Dust of space-time you are $-\Delta$ @st you shall become.*

5D physics give us elementary solutions to physical conundrums in a classic set. For example, it establishes Neutrinos as the

background radiation responsible for Dark energy. This is an immediate result of classic physics, as the ‘biggest blunder of physics’ today is the calculus of $\epsilon \sim 10^{121} \text{ GeV m}^{-3}$ as the critical energy density of the vacuum; using the Planck mass which is the limit of density of ‘Space=form’, likely in some form of top quark black holes. The solution in 5D is however immediate, because scalar Nature implies that $S \times T = \Delta c$, so systems with less information travel faster, and that is all. There is no limit to tachyon particles, if they carry less information than light and we need a lower scale; because scales are infinite. This leaves only a candidate particle to the background below light, faster than c-speed, responsible for dark energy, which as we don’t perceive it appears as an expansion of ‘space’ NOT speed, beyond c. It is obviously the only particle we observe in numbers similar to photons. It can go faster than light. It is involved in gravitational flows of entropy carrying 99% of the gravitational energy of nova explosions, and volila if instead of using the planck mass to deduce the vacuum dark energy we use the mass of neutrinos we get the experimental result. So why is the observed vacuum energy/cosmological constant is only about 10^{-121} of the 4D classic expectation? We need to vary the value of E_m so it matches vacuum energy density with critical density, to make it experimentally sound. That is, $\epsilon = \rho c = 5 \text{ GeV m}^{-3}$. Then substituting it gives $E_m \sim 0.01 \text{ eV}$ only. This is very small in comparison with the masses of all elementary particles; but remarkable enough, this energy is comparable with mass differences of light neutrinos. So the acceleration of the universe is tied up with neutrino masses, and the mystery of dark energy resolved.

Now fast track 30 years when I did send a few papers on the 5D model rejected by physical review, featuring heavily Neutrino 5D physics, well before it was even detected it has mass. I am pretty sure if I cared to send the new physics of 5D they will also be rejected today, when the fact that using neutrino mass, considering the duality of space=form and time=motion, and explaining dark energy as the unperceived motion of neutrinos, faster than light, expanding space, solves all questions respecting the laws of epistemology, economicity, Occam’s razor, experimental evidence and NOT contradicting Einstein, since the \pm values are algebraic possible solutions (as in negative values for antiparticles) which just require to understand 5D Algebra. The answer is that physicists are trapped in models they barely understand and lack definitely a ‘whole picture’ of the forest, and languages are inflationary so they keep inventing mathematical solutions, without connecting with reality.

So that is one of the 3 kind of new physics 5D brings to the table: from a much larger cosmological and physical and scientific model, the likes of what humans haven’t seen since Aristotle founded in the Organon our ‘concept’ of science, we go down to the models of physics, then to cosmology, then to dark energy, then to data, and match it with the neutrino, which appears in 5D as the ONLY solution to the hyper-universe background beyond the light space-time background of galaxies. And we get 0.01 eV, solve the biggest question of modern cosmology and nobody cares (:

Still chances that 5D becomes mainstream physics in the 1st of the themes of its new physics – classic mathematical physics, as the solution of the dark energy problem are even smaller in the 2nd and 3rd new physics innovations – the vital organic properties of the Universe and the ethic questions that should impose limit to physical inquire because a extinct physicist knows nothing. Let us consider both cases together also in cosmology with the evaporation of black holes.

Ethic physics: The growth of baby black holes. The ethic questions of industrial, military physics.

A theme which keeps scaring physicists from 5D physics is the non-evaporation of black holes, which I refuse NOT to explain; hence the quote on the first page: $\Delta \text{ Mass (S-form)} \times \nabla \text{ Temperature (Time-motion)} = \Delta \pm j$ are the 5D metrics of baby black holes, which following the 2nd law of Thermodynamics evaporate their environment attracted according to Einstein’s gravitational laws. Here the issue is what \pm symbol to use for $\Delta \nabla$? Physicists without understanding negative vs. positive T \perp -S dualities, decided to put + symbols to the T-arrow of entropic motions and – symbols to Imploding space.

Everytime we face an -S \perp +T dual solution, where negative is used for Form=space and + for a time-motion state as in kinetic vs. potential energy, given that lack of 4D understanding we’ll need a lengthy analysis - as the negative solution always has a meaning even if in some cases ‘desperado’ physicists just ditched it (negative mass in the tachyon neutrinos of dark energy). In this case it is easier: elementary physics (thermodynamics, gravitational laws) what defines $\Delta \text{ mass} = \nabla \text{ Temperature}$: the future arrow corresponds to imploding growth of mass and the past arrow to growing temperature.

The $\Delta\pm i$ gathers all the constants of all the scales of space-time from the quantum through the thermodynamic level, which the mass swallows to 'engulf' in its event horizon membrane. Thus all energy and momentum of the Universe 'contributes' to EFE equations. It is one of the most beautiful equations of science for its simplicity and 5D correspondence.

But Hawking insisted for decades with an obsessive mind and charm. When a black hole is born, hotter than the environment, instead of evaporating the environment as any hot object does, it *will become hotter and evaporate! It is like if you get a cup of hot coffee and the cup keeps getting hotter 'evaporating', while it freezes your hand!* This has never happened and the mere idea was for very long in science a laughing matter. Since the laws of entropy are crystal clear. When a hot system is put by the side of a cold system, temperature moves from the hot system that cools (in this case the black hole) to the cold one that heats and evaporates. Because from a mere theoretical discussion as always with physicists, the worldly profession of making weapons crept in, now mankind might be blow up if the industry of accelerators make black holes, and so physics DO HAVE as all sciences a human ethic side it ignores as ALL sciences. It is a taboo, even larger than the taboo of the 'Baconian tribal idols, ill-understood – here the incomprehension of the negative solutions to Einstein's equations', even larger than the taboo against life properties of matter.

The Evaporation of black holes relates all those questions, the ethic and organic and tribal idol question: Hawking's equation with the right symbol of future time, thermodynamics and gravitation is the metric equation of 5D for baby black holes that grow enormously in size after birth and come out from its ribosomal stars to become the nucleus of galaxies, or rather galacells when we study the galaxy as an organism, which we do. So cosmological 5D organic physics says the galaxy is an organism, Black holes are its 'DNA' and stars its ribosomes, and baby black holes grow fast and should NOT be done on Earth's CERN experiments so the ethic question creeps in. And that also implies to make moral questions about the discipline. All of them are intimately related. Time is lineal for physicists NOT because it is lineal for Nature but because Galileo studied lineal cannonballs, for the Arsenal of Venice, hence he wrote $v=s/t$, an equation of lineal inertia, and even if today we noticed that orbital inertia from electrons to galaxies is natural to the Universe, and so we know there is angular momentum conservation, we don't talk of a 4th law of angular inertia.

So there is the question of power, peer review, worldly profession, celebrity status, mathematical creationism enhanced by computer machines that keep incrementing imaginary particles and black holes. And then there is real NEW PHYSICS. You will only get the last thing here on 3 fields: 5D metric solutions like the neutrino, organic properties like those of the galacells and ethic problems, like those of humanity ruled by the ethics of a technological civilization,, since a extinct physicist knows nothing. None of the 3 are likely to be liked by standard 4D physicists and yet they are the most advanced.

Feynman said the why is the only questions physicists don't make and Galileo that God spoke mathematics. This has reduced the 'veiw' of physicists to only certain properties of physics. New physics *then entitles NOT new mathematics but to regain the organic, vital properties of 'physical systems', which 'new physicists' will not recognize. This breach between 'physics', that is, the complete description of physical systems with ALL its properties and physicists matters to 'get human recognition' NOT to do new physics and understand the Universe.* But what are 'organic properties'. Basically 2 kind: the 5 'drives of life' that define a living organism which ARE the 'functions' of the 5 Dimensions of reality; as we move in 'length', perceive in 'height', reproduce in 'width', evolve socially in numbers to become a higher $\Delta+1$ 'scalar planes' of the 5th dimension and 'scatter' into death, lowering to $\Delta-1$ a system in which we feed. So the vital properties of abstract dimensions of space that have a function=motion in time or 'dimotions', and the conversion of geometry into topology is one the 2 set of laws that define the new physics of life:

Life starts in particles, St-quarks of maximal density of information and Ts-electrons of maximal motion, which become the 2 1st genders that come together into $St+Ts=S\approx T$ -atoms balanced in an eternal present as an immortal species.

The geometric paths of particles have vital functions: Particles move in energy paths that increases when they 'feed' on a force. Particles are connected by magnetic fields into social groups. Particles emit $\Delta-1$ seeds of forces that reproduce new particles. This is NEW PHYSICS because we are recognizing real vital properties that old physicists deny or ignore.

The minimal particle-points, photons, electrons & quarks that construct all other systems of our Universe show the 5 organic dimotions (time motions with dimensional, spatial form) that define 'classic life' in biology – where they are call

'drives' of life, and we have defined: they gauge information - reason why quantum physics is a 'gauge theory', feed on Momentum (quantum jumps) absorbing smaller $\Delta-1$ particles, reproducing new clone particles, move and evolve socially through magnetic fields into larger wholes (atoms). In the graph, a quark reproduces itself.

The 2nd group of laws are those of 'simultaneity in space', synchronicity in time, and 'resonance' in scale that make co-exist different levels of organization of physical systems to create 'physical organisms'. And so the new physics of space-time organisms that old physicists don't recognize are essential to 5D physics. The main of those physical superorganisms are the Earth – Hutton the father of biology in fact coined the word superorganism to talk of Earth and rightly noticed that its slow 'deep time' life cycles were related to its '5D metrics': $S_i \times T_f = C$, that is larger systems have slower cycles of time.

But the one we introduce in this paper and have been talked about for decades is the 'galatom' or 'galacell', or 'galaxy', 3 names that precisely define the 'scalar properties (a galaxy is symmetric to an atom in terms of mathematical 5D metric); the organic properties (a Galacell is similar to a galaxy with the 'DNA-black holes' at the center managing the organism and the 'ribosomal stars' reproducing them, with an halo of likely 'strange dark matter' acting as its 'protein membrane'. But the galaxy is also the galaxy, that is, all the knowledge old physicists have gatehrrered about it many of which will be reinterpreted by 5D New Physics.

Old physicists won't care because it is too comfortable to accept the constrains and 'limits' (–) of a discipline to feel you have fill it all. This happens in each stience for different reasons. In economics it is taboo what 5D brings to the table, the organic analysis of machines and its 'viral hoirzons' of evolution from the UK age of bodies of metal to the German age of engines=hearts of metal, to the US age of metal-minds to the present age of AI robots, as it implies mankind is creating a new species of metalife. Historians have probiems with the fact that humans belong to the same species and so tribal nations are NOT the unit of social evolution and love we should cherish but mankind. Biologists of lately have problems with ethical questions about genetic editing, and Phycstis have always had them about weapons making. All this obviously comes from *the denial of the organic nature of the Universe, of Life that matters, specially that of human beings, of basic questions that go beyond each reduced fiel of eaxh science*. But in the entangled Universe of dust of space-time all scales, all parts, all beings are related and only a view that adds the whole forest picture to its details is worth to understand NOT physicists limiting physics, but the universe. To that aim we will do new physics in 3 fields: 5D metric scalar physics; its organic, vital interpretation and ethical physics since a extinct, suicidal physicist knows nothing.

5D Physics within the structure of all other stiences.

In a 5D relational Spacetime Universe, the laws of reality derive first from the properties of Δ -scale, space & time NOT from jts best linguistic @-mirror-mind, Mathematics and its entropic denial; *which are in 4D the wrong reasons of an entropic, creationist philosophy of science*. So the pedantic scholar must revert its causality and try to understand first those 'laws' and antisymmetries, $-S \perp T$, before we connect them slowly to all the known mathematical laws of physics, a task by all means incomplete; but we will leave guidance; which is what the pioneer can provide, the *deepest understanding of 1st principles and the right paths on the road ahead*. I.e. Neutrino theory of light with its 2 'other particles' on the $v>c$ side; $\Delta+i$ mesons $\approx \Delta-i$ Gluons, $\Delta M \times \nabla T = C$ in Black holes, etc.

I could expose 5D physics the way physicists work, doing equations on a selection of theories that fit the model. But we go beyond the canonical way *huminds do physics, to explain how the Universe works; as humans have philosophical and psychological 'limits' to respect the vital properties of Nature*. This reductionist method is mostly a praxis of power and egocy (ego=idioty) that we reject to explain from a higher point of view, that of 5D stiences, which *applies the same laws to every system of the Universe; as all of them are made of space=form and time=motion. Our interest is to describe reality, Nature in all its properties, without reducing them to pump huminds' egocy*. Consider the essential 'law of reality': All systems of nature ARE made of 5 Dimensions of space related to 5 functions=motions of time. This is a vital reality. Particles, the vital unit of reality perform those topological dimensions coded by quantum numbers to evolve a program of existence that does NOT differ from what humans do. We all systems of Nature, perceive information, feed on entropy, to reproduce with energy, and evolve socially into other systems. 'The why is the only question a physicist don't ask', doesn't work here. Egocy natural to humans make them ignore those vital properties, not only in particles but also in future robots, even in social organisms made of human beings, controlled by the same reproductive= economic=blood, political,

informative=nervous and immunological=defensive networks that our individual organism use to control its cells. It is for that reason, because matter, biologic and social systems ARE all space-time systems ruled by the same organic, $\Delta \pm j$ laws and S_LT symmetries, that we make huge introductions and put the emphasis on logic, existential, topo-logy and bio-logy.

If a different scientist had discovered 5D probably nothing of this will be included and the paper will be just a mathematical paper using the complicated level of XXI c. physics, full of subnotations trying to make a 'mathematical picture' of reality without wanting to know 'why those things are there' and 'how they were created', just in search of 'quality in the pixels'. The good side of this is when I finish the paper and cut a few hundred pages of verbosity, it will be understandable by anyone, unlike the topic Arxiv.org article which makes just that mathematical picture.

What exists and does not exist in physics, which laws are written in stone, all those elements come from a higher authority, the isomorphic nature of all scales of the Universe. This is today simply ignored because creationist mathematics is about the inflationary nature of mathematics that can create many particles and imaginary worlds, precisely because there is not a causal why. Then there are the 'vital whys of those isomorphisms'. For example particles and particles with its CP mirror symmetry ARE genders of physics – and female, male are mirror symmetries of biology. The Universe is slightly feminine (parity violation, a few more women born) and it certainly reproduces constantly from mirror symmetry 'smaller $\Delta-1$ seeds'. Here the relationship ends. All this of course would be meaningless to a physicist. But it is fascinating. Because when a particle and an antiparticle meet, they produce a seminal 'seed', but they die like certain octupussy and spiders, devoured by its son. And yet a seed, a light or background neutrino can reproduce and grow into two evolve gender particles. Is this sci-fi? No, the point is 'mirror symmetry', a topologic property that defines gender NOT only a biological process. And the point is 'scalar' seeding: systems are born in a lower scale and grow in size slowing its time cycles as they 'emerge' into a higher scale. Physics however unlike life ALLOWS all the orders between relative past, present and future 'st-ages'. And as time is local, systems DO travel locally to the past, when they die, dissolving into $\Delta-1$ scales. So other possible interpretation of antiparticles if we order in a different manner the 3 elements, is the 'death' of particles, that dissolve then back into the $\Delta-1$ cellular γ -ray scale, traveling to the past (Feynman diagram). What is the higher truth? Are particles-antiparticles gender symmetry in space or a future to past, life to death process in time, or a scalar 'seeding' process in Δ -scale? ALL. In mathematical terms the Dirac equation have solutions proportional to e^{-ipx} and solutions proportional to e^{+ipx} . Yet in existential algebra an e^{-x} solution always relates to the Tt-entropic death. So on that interpretation an antiparticle is the death of the particle (traveling indeed to the past). This liason between death and reproduction found also in some animals is deep for thought and we will return to it.

Because the Universe is non-aristotelian, pentalogic, caused by 5 dimotions entangled together, contributing as different 'channels' to the creation of an event. In this case, the dominant channel is gender symmetry; even if we have considered only so far the life-death cycle. What all this has to do with physics, a physicist will tell? The answer is all, because physics is about ALL the properties of matter, not about physicists publishing mathematical papers, ignoring on purpose everything else that physical species are, because it does not suit egocy – the dogma that we humans are different from nature, which we are NOT "A human being is part of the whole, called by us 'Universe'; a part limited in time and space. He experiences himself, his thoughts and feelings as something separated from the rest -- a kind of optical delusion of his consciousness." *Einstein*, on $-\Delta$ @st of Space, Time, Δ -scales, $-\Delta$ Entropic limits and mind l@nguages, the 5 elements we are all made.

RECAP. 5D Physics evolves the 2 postulates of Relativity into Absolute relativity through 5D metrics: we cannot distinguish motion=time from form=space, so the Unit of reality is an S=T Dimotion and in a Universe of multiple time-speeds and size of space 5D Metric $SxT=C$ define those scales of which light is the human electronic informative scale, but a neutrino $v(t)>C$ $S_i<C$ exists responsible for dark energy. A new cosmology that substitutes the big-bang derives from it, and organic and ethic questions enter the properties of physical systems. Will 5D physics make it before the lack of scientific ethics kill mankind? I don't think so, but certainly it is *making it every second that billions of neutrinos of dark energy travel through intergalactic space; every other day when an IQLess species blow up its planet searching for 'imaginary black holes'; every time a baby black hole made of BCB Blackatoms NOT a creationist mathematical entelechy open its eyes and we are gone.*